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Table of contents

PLENARY CONFERENCES	4
AEROPALYNOLOGY:	11
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS	11
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS	28
ARCHEOPALYNOLOGY:	35
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS	35
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS	41
MELISSOPALYNOLOGY:	46
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS	46
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS	55
PALEOPALYNOLOGY:	62
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS	62
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS	80
POLLEN BIOLOGY:	93
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS	93
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS	101
List of authors	107

PLENARY CONFERENCES

Mediterranean plants and land uses on the move: palaeoenvironmental and archaeological evidence of transported landscapes

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Background. The Mediterranean Sea has been a route of contact for ancient civilizations whose mobility and interactions have given rise to the configuration of a rich landscape heritage. When human communities move to a new territory, they take with them their technology and ideas, but also plants, animals or specific land uses, which merge with local environments and practices to create the so-called transported landscapes. This process can result in significant landscape changes - e.g. deforestation, introduction of exotic plants, erosion - that can be tracked using palaeoenvironmental techniques. However, the use of palaeoenvironmental analysis to reconstruct transported landscapes in the Mediterranean remains hampered by the difficulty of finding undisturbed organic-rich palaeoenvironmental records in highly anthropized and developed littoral areas, as well as by poor chronological control, and/or insufficient high temporal resolution of palaeoenvironmental analyses. This presentation will draw on research conducted in different Mediterranean study areas over the last decade to assess the role of human mobility and cultural exchange in the late Holocene shaping of Mediterranean landscapes in Southern Europe and overseas.

Methods. Integrated research approach joining high-temporal resolution multi-proxy palaeoenvironmental analyses (eg. pollen, non-pollen palynomorphs, charcoal particles, diatoms, sedimentology, geomorphology) from natural and archaeological records, and the study of archaeo-historical sources has been conducted in selected coastal areas of eastern Spain and southern California. These areas have been selected for accounting for a long and intense history of colonial, migratory and socio-economic exchanges, and for having ancient colonial bonds.

Results. The Empordà plain, north-eastern Iberian Peninsula, bears witness to a confluence of indigenous populations and colonial processes during the Iron Age and Antiquity. In the early 6th century BC, Phocian communities established the colony of *Emporion* as part of their expansion into the Western Mediterranean. It is noteworthy that the establishment of the Greek colony and its subsequent growth as a prominent trade hub did not result in an intensified exploitation of the land for agriculture or the clearance of coastal woodlands. Instead, there was a moderate recovery of woodlands and a reduction in the extent of agricultural activities (Ejarque et al., 2022). The exploitation of the rural landscape continued to rely on cereal cultivation and grazing, as was the case previously, indicating the persistence of indigenous landscapes and practices in the colonial hinterland. In contrast, the shaping of transported landscapes is well-attested in both the archaeological and paleoenvironmental records during the Roman colonization of the area. Intensified rural settlement, and the development of field systems and drainages in the plain resulted in the expansion of irrigated meadows, intensified agropastoral exploitation and removal of littoral woodlands, as well as the introduction of new crops and land-uses. During the Early Medieval period, the pioneer colonization of Christian Carolingian communities further impacted the region's landscape, with the expansion of pasturelands, farming and the development of new crops resulting in an overall open coastal landscape (Ejarque et al., 2016).

Mediterranean agropastoral landscapes, which had evolved over millennia greatly as a result of cultural contact and human mobility in the Mediterranean basin, were ultimately used as a tool of cultural

engagement and landscape appropriation in modern colonisation processes overseas. Indeed, during the Spanish colonisation of California (USA), agropastoral activities as well as plants and crops from the Mediterranean Basin were introduced into Mediterranean areas of the New World previously occupied by foraging indigenous communities. This led to significant landscape changes, including erosion processes, eutrophication and contamination of wetlands with faecal-borne parasites, and the introduction of alien plants and crops, which provoked a loss of native habitats and biodiversity (Ejarque et al., 2015). However, by bridging ecosystems and cultures that had diverged for millennia, a shared landscape heritage integrating multiple cultural traditions was configured between the two world regions.

Conclusions. The research presented here highlights the significant role of mobility and cultural exchange in the long-term shaping of Mediterranean coastal landscapes. Integrated palaeoenvironmental and archaeological analyses can significantly contribute to a better understanding of how the mixing of autochthonous and foreign cultural traditions interacted with dynamic coastal environments and contributed to cultural landscape change over time. The study of palaeoenvironmental proxies at high temporal resolution is essential to unravel landscape changes associated with migratory and colonial processes. In fact, this is the only way to detect short-lived palaeoenvironmental events of a few centuries and to link palaeoenvironmental and archaeological data effectively. Finally, the results underline the importance of multi-site palaeoenvironmental studies, combining sites close to the colonial site and further inland, in order to reconstruct accurate local-to-regional landscape changes.

References. Ejarque, A., Anderson, R.S., Simms, A.R., Gentry, B.J. (2015) Prehistoric fires and the shaping of colonial transported landscapes in southern California: a palaeoenvironmental study at Dune Pond, Santa Barbara County. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 112: 181-196.

Ejarque, A., Julià, R., Reed, J.M., Mesquita-Joanes, F., Marco-Barba, J., Riera, S. (2016) Coastal evolution in a Mediterranean microtidal zone: Mid to late Holocene natural dynamics and human management of the Castelló Lagoon, NE Spain. *PLoS One*, 11(5): e0155446.

Ejarque, A., Julià, R., Castanyer, P., Orengo, H.A., Palet, J.M., Riera, S. (2022) Landscape footprints of peopling and colonisation from the Late Bronze Age to Antiquity in the coastal hinterland of Emporion-Emporiae, NE Iberia. *The Holocene*, 32(4): 280-296.

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[Plenary conference Aeropalynology]

Applications of Aeropalynology

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Aeropalynology focuses on the study of pollen grains and spores present in the air, and their relationship with meteorological factors, in order to understand the phenomena of production, release, dispersion and transport of them in the environment, as well as its impact on human health and environment. Therefore, we can point out that Aeropalynology is related to other scientific disciplines such as aerobiology, phenology, agriculture and immunocytochemistry.

Aerobiology study biological components suspended in the atmosphere, including not only pollen and spores, but also microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi. Both disciplines, Aeropalynology and Aerobiology, are related in their interest in understanding the dispersion of biological particles in the air and their impact on human health and the environment. Different aerobiological studies have been known for years and were aimed at knowing the content of pollen and spores in the air in different locations, and determining which pollen types were most abundant. Currently we know its incidence well, and it is represented in pollen calendars, many of which point to a tendency to increase pollen concentration.

Another line closely related to Aeropalynology is Phenology, here the greatest efforts are focused on species of agronomic interest, analysing the sequence of phenophases, phenoclimatic models aimed at estimating the pollen production of a given species.

Aeropalynology study the pollen grains present in the atmosphere, which is crucial in Agriculture to know the dispersion of pollen from allergenic plants and to understand the pollination of crops. This information, together with phenology, would be a useful tool in predicting crop production. Additionally, Aeropalynology can help identify dispersal patterns of fungal spores that cause plant diseases, allowing for better pest and disease management. Finally, in relation to predictive models of Climate Change, Aeropalynology can contribute to the monitoring of climate variability through the study of the presence of pollen in the air, which can be indicative of changes in flowering and pollination patterns due to climate change.

Finally, Aeropalynology in addition to pollen also studies other airborne biological materials, including aeroallergens that can trigger allergic reactions in sensitive people. The relationship between Aeropalynology and Immunocytochemistry lies in the identification and quantification of aeroallergens, which allows studying their impact on human health. In addition, this technique can also be used to analyze the presence of atmospheric pollutants that could interact with aeroallergens and enhance their effects. Together, Aeropalynology and Immunocytochemistry contribute to the study of air quality and its implications for the respiratory health of the population.

[Plenary conference Melissopalynology]

Melissopalynology review: a proposal to improve pollen criteria in the identification of monofloral honeys

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Despite the use of recent and innovative techniques in the study of honey, classical melissopalynology continues to play an essential role in establishing its botanical and geographical origin. In this methodology, the classification of honeys as monofloral is based on the percentage value of pollen from the target species, normally a value of 45%, after removing the pollens from anemophilous species and other that are not very nectar-bearing. Exceptions are considered for species considered to be under-represented or over-represented, in terms of the pollen/nectar ratio, whose criterion value is lower and higher, respectively. This criterion, being a relative value, is dependent on the polliniferous contribution of other species that make up the pollen profile of the honeys under evaluation, causing distortion in the interpretation of the results.

With this work, we seek to review the history of melissopalynology, documenting its path both from a methodological perspective and in terms of its application and constraints. The aim is also to systematize the various factors that affect the profile and quantity of pollen present in honey, the techniques used to isolate and identify pollen, the factors that influence the count and the different perspectives used to interpret the result. We also seek to explore the approach proposed by Zofia and Antoni Demianowiczowie in 1957, the use of “pollen indices”, as an alternative to the percentage value for the classification of monofloral honeys. For this purpose, qualitative and quantitative melissopalynology data were compare with physicochemical parameters of Portuguese lavender (*Lavandula pedunculata* and *L. stoechas*) honey samples.

The results show that there are honeys that are classified as multifloral considering the percentage of *Lavandula* pollen as a criterion, but which have a higher concentration of *Lavandula* pollen than those classified as monofloral by this criterion. Therefore, it should be questioned the possibility of classifying monofloral honey following the pollen concentration instead of the percentage value of a given species.

Reference. Demianowicz, Z., & Demianowicz, A. (1957). Nowe podstawy analizy pyłkowej miodów. *Pszczelnicze Zeszyty Naukowe*, 1(2): 69-78.

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[Plenary conference Paleopalynology]

Central and eastern Mediterranean long pollen records

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Studying long terrestrial pollen records in the Mediterranean area is pivotal for understanding past climate variations and their impacts on vegetation dynamics. These records, spanning multiple glacial and interglacial cycles, offer detailed reconstructions of historical climate conditions and ecological responses. The Mediterranean region, characterized by its diverse and sensitive ecosystems, serves as a key area for examining the interplay between climate change and vegetation. By analyzing pollen data, we have been able to identify patterns of species distribution, shifts in plant communities, and resilience mechanisms over time. This knowledge not only sheds light on historical biodiversity and environmental shifts but also provides essential insights for predicting future ecological changes in response to ongoing global climate change. Ultimately, long pollen records are instrumental in informing conservation strategies and enhancing our understanding of ecosystem adaptation and resilience.

Long Mediterranean terrestrial pollen records encompassing the Eemian interglacial period are few, and provide crucial insights into past climate and vegetation dynamics. The Eemian, occurring approximately 130,000 to 115,000 years ago, was characterized by warmer temperatures and higher sea levels compared to the present Holocene epoch.

After an overview on available long pollen records the presentation will focus on the pivotal study of Valle di Castiglione (Follieri et al. 1988) and Piana Del Fucino (Follieri et al. 1986) and, above all, on Lake Ohrid 1.35 million years pollen record (Sadori et al. 2016, Donders et al. 2021, Fig.1).

References. Donders T., Panagiotopoulos K., Koutsodendris A., Bertini A., Mercuri A.M., Masi A., Combourieu-Nebout N., Joannin S., Kouli K., Kousis I., Peyron O., Torri P., Florenzano A., Francke A., Wagner B., Sadori L. (2021) 1.36 million years of Mediterranean forest refugium dynamics in response to glacial-interglacial cycle strength. *PNAS* 118 No. 34 e2026111118, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2026111118>

Follieri M., Magri D., Sadori L. (1986). Late Pleistocene *Zelkova* extinction in Central Italy. *The New Phytologist*, 103: 269-273.

Follieri M., Magri D., Sadori L. (1988). 250,000-year pollen record from Valle di Castiglione (Roma). *Pollen et Spores*, 30: 329--356.

Sadori L., Koutsodendris A., Panagiotopoulos K., Masi A., Bertini A., Combourieu-Nebout N., Francke A., Kouli K., Joannin S., Mercuri A.M., Peyron O., Torri P., Wagner B., Zanchetta G., Sinopoli G., Donders T.H. (2016). Pollen-based paleoenvironmental and paleoclimatic change at Lake Ohrid (SE Europe) during the past 500 ka. *Biogeosciences*, 13: 1423–1437, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/bg-13-1423-2016>

Figure 1. Lake Ohrid synthetic pollen diagram against other proxies (Donders et al. 2021). (A) Pollen diagram of ecological groups (%) against chronology of Wagner et al. 2019: montane trees (*Abies*, *Betula*, *Cedrus*, *Fagus*, *Ilex*, *Picea*, *Taxus*, *Tsuga*); mesophyllous trees (*Acer*, *Buxus*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Carya*, *Castanea*, *Celtis*, *Corylus*, *Fraxinus excelsior/oxycarpa*, *Hedera*, *Ostrya/Carpinus orientalis*, *Pterocarya*, *Q. cerris*-type, *Q. robur*-type, *Tilia*, *Ulmus*, *Zelkova*); Sclerophyllous trees (*Arbutus*, *Cistus*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Olea*, *Phillyrea*, *Pistacia*, *Quercus ilex*-type, *Rhamnus*); wetland trees (*Alnus*, *Liquidambar*, *Platanus*, *Populus*, *Salix*, *Tamarix*, *Taxodium*-type); and semiarid shrubs (*Ephedra*, *Ericaceae*, *Hippophaë*, *Cupressaceae* [mostly *Juniperus*-type]). (B) TP: AP percentages excluding *Pinus*, *Betula*, and *Juniperus*-type. (C) Model timeseries of annual precipitation and (D) mean SAT for the LO grid cell. (E) MEDSTACK planktonic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data. (F) Stacked benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data for Ocean Drilling Program sites 967 and 968 from the eastern Mediterranean. (G) LR04 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ global benthic stack.

**AEROPALYNOLOGY:
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

Predictive models of the onset of *Platanus* pollen exposure: an operative and successful case of study in the Madrid metropolitan area.

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Background. Airborne *Platanus* pollen is one of the most abundant pollen types in the Western Mediterranean region in spite of being a non-native species because of its widespread use in monospecific plantations in urban green spaces and streets of the large metropolitan areas due to the shadow it provides. It constitutes an emergent public health issue in Madrid (central Spain) over the past few decades due to its pollen continuously increasing its incidence, which also has a notorious allergenic potential. In this context, a suitable public information system based on predictive alerts about the onset of the pollen incidence is crucial to ensure exposure avoidance among the sensitized population.

Methods. The Madrid Region Palynological Network continuously monitors the biological air quality of the Madrid Autonomous Region since 1994. The onset of *Platanus* pollen season in Madrid was predicted using a prediction model generated by researchers of the Spanish Meteorological Agency (https://www.aemet.es/es/conocermas/recursos_en_linea/publicaciones_y_estudios/publicaciones/detalles/Pred_polin_platano). This model was based on thermal accumulation whose forecast is given by the European Centre for medium-range weather forecasts (ECMWF) ensemble forecast model “European centre” that is updated daily and the onset of the *Platanus* pollen season was related to reaching a given threshold of temperature. The onset of pollen season was established the first day when 30 pollen grains/m³ were counted. The Aerobiology Research Group of the Complutense University of Madrid also maintains a phenological record of the flowering development of plane trees in the city of Madrid since 2008 to complete the information given by the model.

Results. In the Madrid region, *Platanus* pollen season occurs explosively during the months of March and April, with a great incidence (large annual pollen integrals ranging between 3,339 and 34,658 pollen * day/m³ during the period 1994-2023 as the average of the Madrid Region Palynological Network) over a brief period of time (pollen seasons ranging between 19-46 days). The onset of *Platanus* pollen season was predicted with an error of 5.3 days (Mean Absolute Error) during the period 1994-2023. The model was particularly accurate in 2024, when the date 17th March exactly matched the forecast results, the phenological observations and the onset of the pollen season. The sensitized population conveniently received the results provided by the Directorate-General for Public Health of the Madrid Autonomous Region massively disseminated through the social networks, and personal messages (<https://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/salud/polen>). An opportune warning was published one week in advance noticing about the close increase of *Platanus* pollen levels.

Conclusions. This work presents a successful experience of a public health service as a result of the fruitful cooperation between different public institutions. Public dissemination of results of this operative predictive model allows the sensitized citizens to face accurately informed high pollen exposure events in Madrid Region.

Pollen biodiversity in the city of Rome: three monitoring stations compared (2021-2023)

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Background. In aerobiological monitoring the presence of several sampling sites in the same city is an unusual scenario. The city of Rome is a rare example of an urban centre with no less than three stations, belonging to the Rome 'Tor Vergata' Aerobiological Monitoring Centre, located at different points of the city: Cipro (31 m a.s.l., 41°54'26.6" N, 12°26'57.0" E) near the Vatican City, intensely urbanised, with street trees and poorly preserved urban greenery; Tor Vergata (80 m a.s.l., 41°51'13.5" N, 12°36'14.2" E) a rural area with a high presence of wild species; San Pietro (86 m a.s.l., 41°57'48.6" N, 12°27'03.2" E) near the San Pietro Fatebenefratelli Hospital, influenced by the Insugherata Park. This multicentre survey aims to investigate daily inhaled bioaerosols and to reveal the actual representativeness of the data, which is necessary for a vast and heterogeneous territory such as Rome. This is reflected in a wide floristic-vegetational biodiversity and, at the same time, in a considerable variability of the pollen spectrum in the air, confirming the role of pollen as an environmental indicator for the connotation of the flora in situ. The relationship between phenological (start, end and duration dates of the pollen season) and productive (Annual Pollen Integral -API_n) indicators was studied, i.e. the daily peak period of seven taxa considered interesting for their allergenicity and copiousness: two herbaceous Poaceae and Urticaceae and five arboreal Cupressaceae-Taxaceae, Betulaceae, *Quercus* spp., *Olea europaea* L. and Platanaceae (*Platanus hispanica* Mill. ex Münchh) for the three-year period 2021-2023.

Methods. For the calculation of the pollen season of the different taxa, the method of Jäger was used. A Hirst-type volumetric pollen sampler, model VPPS[®] Lanzoni, according to UNI EN 16868:2019, was used as the survey instrument.

Results. The data show differences both between the three stations and over the three years investigated. It emerged that the period for the start of pollen emission is earlier in the centre than in the rural areas by around 14 days, while for the end of flowering in the urban sites there is a delay of up to four weeks with a limit of 51 days for Betulaceae in the year 2023. The situation is also similar for the peak day and for API_n, with fluctuations of up to several weeks due to the variability of the beginning and especially the end of the flowering.

Conclusions. The earlier flowering demonstrates the microclimatic phenomenon, known as the heat island, caused by intense urbanisation, which leads to an increase in temperatures of up to 4-5°C in both winter and summer in urban areas compared to suburban areas.

References. UNI EN 16868:2019 (2019). Ambient air – Sampling and analysis of airborne pollen grains and fungal spores for allergy networks. Volumetric Hirst method.

Intradiurnal variations of airborne pollen in Sierra de las Nieves (southern Spain)

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Background. Intradaily airborne pollen concentrations oscillate depending on the pollen release dynamics of the plants that produce it, their distribution, and the meteorological conditions. Understanding the intradiurnal pattern of the different pollen types is fundamental for elucidating their reproductive strategies and determining the intradiurnal risk for allergy sufferers. Around 100.000 people visit the Sierra de las Nieves National Park every year and part of them may suffer allergy symptoms due to the presence of allergenic pollen types in the atmosphere. The aim of this study was to analyse the intradiurnal behavior of the main pollen types detected in the air of Sierra de las Nieves, to link the patterns obtained with the distribution and abundance of the pollen emission sources present in the area as well as to determine the most appropriate period of the day for allergic people to visit the Park.

Methods. Pollen was sampled by means of a Hirst-type volumetric pollen trap installed in “Las Conejeras” recreational area. In this study, data from 2018 to 2023, both inclusive, were considered. The most relevant pollen types according to their frequent presence in the atmosphere and allergy interest were studied, i.e., *Amaranthaceae*, *Castanea*, *Cupressaceae*, *Olea*, *Pinus*, *Plantago*, *Poaceae*, *Quercus* and *Urticaceae*. Countings were made hourly, considering only days without rainfall with a daily mean pollen concentration equal to or greater than the mean of the main pollen season (MPS) (Galán et al., 1991). Then, accumulated values for every two hours were calculated, and the pollen detected was expressed as percentages over the daily total.

Results. Three different intradiurnal patterns were observed. *Amaranthaceae* and *Urticaceae* presented a similar pattern, with their highest presence during the last hours of the day; *Castanea*, *Cupressaceae*, *Olea* and *Pinus* showed a peak after midday; and *Plantago*, *Poaceae* and *Quercus* pollen concentrations were evenly spread throughout the day. Pollen types integrated by numerous species (e.g., *Poaceae* or *Plantago*) tended to present lower peaks during the day while pollen types integrated by few species, such as *Castanea*, *Cupressaceae* or *Pinus* had more pronounced peaks. The period of the day with the highest pollen detection in the air was between 12 and 21 hours, with the greatest incidence between 12 and 13 hours.

Conclusions. The different pollen types studied have presented different intra-daily behaviours, with the highest concentrations detected starting at midday and peaks of different intensity that, with some exceptions, normally take place between 12:00 and 14:00.

Reference. Galán, C., Tormo, R., Cuevas, J., Infante, F., & Domínguez, E. (1991). Theoretical daily variation patterns of airborne pollen in the southwest of Spain. *Grana*, 30(1): 201-209.

Airborne Poaceae pollen and their main allergens Phl p 1 and Phl p 5 in relation to the allergy risk period

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Background. Poaceae is a cosmopolitan family of plants, with more than 12.000 species around the world and more than 350 in the study area. Poaceae pollen is one of the most widespread airborne allergenic pollen types in the world, inducing 30% of allergies in cold and temperate climates. In the Mediterranean region, this pollen is present nearly all year round, although its maximum concentrations are registered between March and June. Phl p 1 and Phl p 5 are among the main allergens in the Poaceae family and are considered the major allergens of this family.

This study aims to compare the airborne concentrations and dynamics of the Poaceae pollen and the allergens Phl p 1 and Phl p 5 to discuss the period of risk allergy to Poaceae in Catalonia (NE Spain).

Methods. Daily airborne pollen was measured using a Hirst trap according to the recommendations of the Spanish Aerobiology Network (REA) and the international standards. Airborne allergens were collected using a high-volume sampler (MCV CAV-A/mb, ©MCV). It is a volumetric sampler that works at a flow intake rate of 400 L/min. and impelling the air against a fiberglass filter. The detection and quantification of allergens was done using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) technique (InBio manufacturers). Both samplers were located on the roof of the C building at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, (Bellaterra, Spain) at 23 m.a.g.l. from 2018 to 2021. The statistical analysis was performed by the Spearman rank correlation test.

Results. The daily concentrations of Poaceae pollen in the four years analysed showed a presence in the atmosphere from February to November. These results were according with the results found for Phl p 1 in the same period. However, Phl p 5 showed a different behavior with a shorter presence, since February until June.

Poaceae pollen and Phl p 1 allergen coincided in the air, on average, during 237 days per year (min. 222; max. 266), showing a significant positive Spearman rank correlation ($p < 0.01$) for the whole year. In the case of Phl p 5, it was registered in the air for an average of 177 days per year (min. 122; max. 185) and always when Poaceae pollen was present too. In this case, the statistical analysis showed also a positive significant Spearman test ($p < 0.01$) but only for the period of 177 days.

Conclusions. The risk period of allergy for patients affected by Poaceae pollen varies according to the allergen. While Phl p 5 presence is limited to spring, Phl p 1 is spread from spring to autumn. This shows how important it is to know the allergen sensitizing each patient in order to establish the best medication and to prepare the best avoidance strategies.

Categorization of pollen stations in aerobiological monitoring networks

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Background. An aerobiological monitoring network provides to control and study the biological component of the airborne particulate matter and its data are valuable for integrating air quality monitoring, estimating the biodiversity of green areas, detecting phenomena related to the global warming, as well as in the human health field (creating data in diagnostics, clinical, within the therapy, investigate and avoidance of unfavorably susceptible respiratory illnesses) (Di Menno di Bucchianico et al., 2023). To achieve these goals, however, all sampling points should be placed on the basis of criteria of greatest spatial representativeness to give data that accurately depict the contribution of the main Taxa around the stations (Brighetti et al., 2022). Unfortunately, the European Standard for pollen networks, doesn't provide anything but instructions on the micro-localization of the samplers and nothing is indicated on the characterization of the sites based on the dominant sources.

Methods. Siting characteristics of the Italian aerobiological monitoring network stations were studied and compared to achieve a general classification of the sampling sites, comparable to that used at European level for Air Quality networks. To categorize the pollen monitoring sampling points a classification approach based on land use classes from the CLC, Corine Land Cover inventory (EEA, 2019) was considered.

Results. Based on our data we can draw up a hypothetical classification of Italian pollen monitoring stations, out of 64 total stations we have: Mostly built area: 1 station (2%); Built area: 5 stations (8%); Built-vegetated area: 23 stations (36%) and Natural - semi natural area: 35 stations (55%)

Conclusions. This study clearly shows how the failure to apply of homogeneous criteria for the placement of aerobiological sampling sites can lead to an imbalanced distribution of the stations with respect to the characteristics of the territory.

References. Brighetti, M. A., De Franco, D., Di Cosmo, C., Di Menno di Bucchianico, A., Froio, F., Miraglia, A.; Moselli, D., Travaglini, A. (2022). Aerobiological Biodiversity in the Metropolitan City of Rome. *Int J Environ Sci Nat Res.* 30, 556283.

Di Menno di Bucchianico, A., Gaddi, R., Brighetti, M.A., De Franco, D., Miraglia, A., Travaglini A. (2023). *Sustainability* 15, 6150, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15076150>.

EEA - European Environment Agency. 2019. Updated CLC illustrated nomenclature guidelines, Service Contract No 3436/R0-Copernicus/EEA.57441, Environment Agency Austria EEA.

An automatic system for recording and processing atmosphere particle data

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Background. Airborne pollen and fungal spores are a major concern due to their impact on public health, agriculture or urban planning. Current analysis methods normally involve manual microscopic identification by specialists, making the process slow and labor-intensive. This research aims to address this by developing a speech recognition software to automate particle identification and analysis.

Methods. The system integrates a web interface, database, and speech recognition module. This module leverages Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) with AI and machine learning to convert spoken scientific names of pollen and fungal spore types into text (Povey, 2011). Since existing ASR systems lack biology-specific vocabulary, a custom database was built. Volunteers recorded audio files (48 each) containing scientific names and system commands (e.g., "minus" for subtracting counts, "read" for displaying current counts). Scripts and pronunciation guides ensured accurate name pronunciation. With 36 speakers recording 1657 files, the dataset provides an average of 36 repetitions per word. This allows training the model with 70% of the data for accurate recognition and using the remaining 30% for testing.

Results. The web system offers two main functionalities: data entry and analysis. Users can either manually fill in a spreadsheet with observed pollen data or utilize the speech recognition area to speak the pollen name, quantity, and commands. This spoken data can then be filtered and analyzed in various ways. The system can generate graphs to visualize both daily and monthly pollen concentration trends throughout the study period.

Conclusions. A collaboration between CEFET-MG and the University of Salamanca is developing a system to automatically store pollen and fungal spore data from speech recognition in a web-based database. This will allow researchers to access seasonal analyses, generate data visualizations (graphs), and share findings. Initial tests confirm the potential of the system for building speech-to-text models. However, the sensitivity of the model to database size highlights the need for more audio samples per word, prompting efforts to expand the audio database.

Reference. Povey, D. et al. The Kaldi Speech Recognition Toolkit. In: Workshop on Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding, 2011, Hawaii. Proceedings. IEEE, 2011.

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Automatic Pollen Monitoring in Mediterranean Climates: Results from the SYLVA Project Training Campaign in Córdoba (Spain)

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Background. The Mediterranean region faces unique challenges in aerobiology due to its diverse climates and pollen types. Until now, fully automatic pollen monitoring has proven ineffective in Mediterranean environments. The SYLVA project aims to standardize and automate pollen monitoring across Europe. The project is dedicated to constructing a robust infrastructure designed to enhance bioaerosol monitoring. It aims to demonstrate the capability of automated monitoring under diverse and extreme conditions. The project strategically targets locations within the Arctic Circle in Finland, Alpine conditions on Germany/Switzerland, and the dusty and warm environments of southern Spain. The primary objective of this presentation is to showcase the results and progress of the SYLVA project, with a special focus on its implementation in Córdoba (Spain). The current state of technology deployment will be shown, outlining the difficulties encountered in adapting these technologies to the Mediterranean environment and sharing the results of training the automatic devices and developed infrastructure. Validation results of the current versions of the classification algorithms will be shown.

Methods. The methodology employed to produce reference datasets for the automatic pollen monitoring devices—Swisens Poleno Jupiter, BAA500, and Pollen Sense (APS-300)—varies according to the capabilities of each system. For validation, we compared the daily and three-hourly data of trained taxa with the concentration obtained from Hirst with three automatic devices in Córdoba. We calculated the ratio among each couple of devices and homogenization scaling factors were compared using Hirst as reference method.

Results. A total of 44 different reference datasets were created. Till the moment, high correlations are shown for every device with assimilated pollen categories: e.g. in case of *Cupressus* 0.94 (APS-300), 0.87 (BAA500) and 0.82 (Swisens Poleno Jupiter). The average rates of daily pollen concentrations between Hirst/automatic devices were below 1.2 in the case of APS and BAA500 and above 3 in the case of Swisens Poleno. We have observed a deviation in correlation coefficients depending on the instrument and the classification algorithm version. Different scaling factors are needed to homogenize time series on every device.

Conclusions. We developed reference datasets for all representative local biological taxa, but we compared the pre-load commercial algorithms. Potential improvements are expected for the three tested automatic systems after training for local biodiversity.

Studying allergenic pollen in moss: the case-study of Reggio Emilia (Northern Italy)

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Background. Mosses are natural gravimetric pollen traps and can be studied to obtain the mean pollen rain from around 5 years before the moss is collected. In addition, they can be used as modern analogues for palaeo/archeopalynological studies. Moss samples are often taken from natural areas to check the present pollen rain while palynological studies on moss from urban areas are not so common. The study of moss in our city centers can help us understand the mean pollen rain to which citizens are exposed and also give information on changes in pollen rain inside cities due to the different plants in different areas. In order to better understand how exposure to allergic plants can be recorded in moss, showing changes within urban environment with the presence of different parks and green area, we chose the city of Reggio Emilia as a case study. This was due to the stable presence of an ARPAE station that could give us detailed information on the airborne pollen rain in the city and the high presence of parks and urban green areas.

Methods. To obtain the data, various samplings were performed during spring and autumn 2022. Using a 1 km² grid for the city outskirts and 500 m² in the city centre, one or more moss samples were collected for each mesh, for a total of 50 moss samples from different parks of Reggio Emilia (Emilia Romagna region, N Italy). After pollen extraction and acetolysis, at least 500 pollen grains were counted for each sample at 400x.

Results and discussion. Pollen was found in all samples, with a mean concentration of 709,428 pollen/g (min: 14,776 pollen/g, max: 5,623,614 pollen/g). A total of 118 taxa were found (51 arboreal pollen, 67 non arboreal pollen). The percentage of arboreal pollen was higher than non-arboreal pollen (70% AP, 30% NAP on mean) with prevalent *Quercus*, *Fraxinus*, *Platanus*, *Cupressus/Taxus*, *Carpinus* and *Pinus*. The main non arboreal pollen taxa are Poaceae wild grass group, Cyperaceae and *Aster* type. Considering taxa with known allergenic role, *Fraxinus*, *Quercus*, Poaceae wild grass group and Cupressaceae/Taxaceae are the most important in moss spectra (9.1%, 13.0%, 12.9% and 7.4%, respectively). The data obtained varies greatly based on the plants surrounding each moss sample, as well as the percentages of the allergenic taxa compared to the total (mean: 79.4%, min: 29.3%, max: 94.7%). Comparing it to the data from the ARPAE station most of the taxa found by the station were also found in the moss, with a few exceptions (e.g., Myrtaceae).

Conclusions. The study made it possible not only to understand how pollen spectra changed in mosses from different parks in the city, but also as a base to compare percentages of allergenic pollen in moss from different parts of Reggio Emilia, and to compare data of allergenic pollen in mosses and in the ARPAE station in Reggio Emilia. The pollen rain is similar in moss and in the air, but there are important local differences depending on what park or urban green area is considered both in composition and in overall percentages of allergenic taxa.

Evaluating the effectiveness of photocatalytic paints in reducing indoor airborne pollen concentrations in schools: LIME4HEALTH project

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Background. In Europe, children spend approximately six to nine hours per day in primary school buildings, making it the most important microenvironment after their home. Since airborne particles and pollutants can be very harmful for their health, Lime4health project is being carried out with the main objective of testing whether the use of photocatalytic paint together with the modification of the user's habits in the classrooms of four schools in Madrid (Spain) can reduce them.

Methods. The project is currently under development and the data analyzed so far are the pre-painting ones. Later, the analysis will be extended with post-painting data. The variables used are indoor-outdoor pollen; school; campaign (to date February, April, May, October, and December 2023); week (week one and two); shift (8:30h and 14:00h), and classroom (two for school except for Montserrat, where three were sampled). Sampling was carried out using a Burkard Personal Volumetric Air Sampler and then the concentrations were calculated multiplying by the correction factor 11.11.

Results. Outdoor concentrations are significantly higher than indoors, showing a very similar behavior throughout the campaigns; likewise, pollen level at 14:00h is significantly higher than at 8:30h, obtaining an alike behavior during the campaigns studied (February, April, May, and October), except for December where the pollen quantity obtained in both shifts are very close. However, there are no significant differences between the classrooms sampled nor the monitored week, although we can see how the behavior of the weeks studied differs in April, with higher level registered during the second week of the study compared to that of week one. Regarding to the campaign, we have been able to observe that April has a significantly higher pollen concentration, with more variability and with a different behavior respect to the other months; on the contrary, October, although it has a behavior equal to the rest of the campaigns (except for April), is the month where a lower concentration is registered. The school placed in the north of Madrid showed a concentration significantly higher than in the one placed at the south nor east has been obtained. When we analyzed the possible interactions between the different schools and the campaigns, we observed that the school placed in a suburban new neighborhood had a different behavior from the rest due to the increase in concentrations in April because of *Quercus* and *Olea* pollen observed, while the schools placed closed to the city center had a very similar behavior throughout the campaigns. On the other hand, the campaigns and the indoor/outdoor ratio have a high effect on pollen concentrations, while the shift and the school-campaign interaction have a moderate effect, and the school has a small effect.

Conclusions. We have been able to confirm that there are no significant differences between the classrooms studied, thus ensuring the validity of the results that we will obtain when analyzing the data after painting in one of the rooms tested for each school and being able to check if the interactions between the different variables have changed.

The air we breathe: Characterising Malta's summer pollen season

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Background: One of the various applications of aerobiology is related to health, because biological material in the air can be potentially hazardous to plants, animals, and human systems. In this regard, allergies caused by pollen are prominent, which cause respiratory diseases and allergies. The objectives of this study included identifying and quantifying airborne pollen on the island of Malta during the 2023 summer season, creating a pollen calendar for this period characterising the pollen season, and comparing the temperature increase with the results. It should be noted that Malta currently has no ongoing aerobiological studies for the region, therefore research focused on this subject, even if only conducted for one summer season, is still relevant.

Methods. The methodology of this study followed the recommendations of the European Aerobiology Society and the guidelines of European Standard EN 1668:2019, which is based on Hirst's methodology. The pollen trap worked continuously for three months. Every seven days, the drum was replaced and the samples prepared, and then analysed under a microscope to identify and quantify the pollen grains. Microsoft Excel was used to carry out the analyses and build the pollen calendar.

Results. A total of 7229 pollen grains were counted, with 47 taxa identified during the months of June, July, and August, while 11.7 percent of the pollen observed were not identifiable. The highest pollen concentrations were observed in June, with 4660 pollen grains counted (65 percent of the total) and the pollen types Urticaceae, *Olea* sp., *Pinus* and *Euphorbia* sp. are mainly present in this month. The second highest pollen concentration were in July (22 percent of the total), while in August only 13 percent of the total pollen were present. Fabaceae recorded a pollen season only in July, however Poaceae, Amaranthaceae, Apiaceae and Lamiaceae are mainly present between June and July. Only the Asteraceae pollen type has its peak concentration in August, although Apiaceae also displayed a peak towards the end of this last month. The pollen calendar highlights that Urticaceae has one of the highest concentrations, mainly in June and July. The average air temperature during the summer maintains an increasing linear trend over the months. The pollen concentration displays the opposite behaviour. This is to be expected given the progression through the summer months, with temperature and other climatic conditions influencing the transport and production of pollen by plants. This is due to the fact that the season studied is not characterised by a period of intense flowering, therefore the overall airborne pollen amounts gradually decrease following the peak spring months.

Conclusions. With this study, it was possible to construct the pollen calendar for Malta's 2023 summer, identifying the main pollen types present in the area. The pollen type Urticaceae recorded the highest concentration, mainly in June and July; due to the known allergenic characteristics of this pollen this warrants particular attention. Among the main pollen types observed, the only one that has its pollen peak only in August is from the Asteraceae family. In terms of qualitative level classification, the Urticaceae was the only pollen type that registered a high level of concentration in atmosphere in June. The rest of the months, the pollen levels were registered as low.

Behaviour of *Platanus* pollen curve through functional data analysis

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Background. *Platanus* pollen is an important cause of allergy in many cities of Western Europe, where this pollen comes from plane tree, *Platanus orientalis* L. var. *acerifolia* Dyand in Aiton, widely used as an ornamental species in parks, gardens and other urban green areas. *Platanus* pollen type presents an intense and explosive flowering that causes the emission of high concentrations of pollen into the atmosphere in a short period of time. This behaviour allows to identify the periods related to the emission and dispersion of pollen. The nature of data associated with this pollen type, generally curves, is suitable for applying functional data analysis, allowing the complete behaviour of a function to be analysed without losing essential information such as the continuity or smoothness of the curves. Therefore, the main objective of this work is to analyse the behaviour of the pollen curve by applying functional data analysis and explain the influence that meteorological variables might have on these behaviours.

Methods. Pollen sampling was carried out using a Hirst volumetric trap located in the city of Toledo. Fourteen years has been analysed for both *Platanus* pollen and meteorological variables, selecting for each year the period from the beginning of the pollen season until the following forty days, thus concentrating more than 90% of the Annual Pollen Integral (API_n). The beginning of the pollen season has been calculated as the first day with at least 1 pollen grain/m³ of *Platanus* pollen followed by five days with an equal or higher concentration. The methodology consisted of carrying out a reconstruction of the functional form by means of basis expansion of sample curves and applying a principal component analysis to all the functional variables to explain the behaviours presented during the study period. The influence of the most important principal components of the meteorological variables on the principal components of the pollen variable has been analysed using Spearman's non-parametric correlation test.

Results. In the city of Toledo, *Platanus* pollen curve presents different behaviours relative, firstly, to the pollen concentration during the pre-peak period or during the post-peak period; secondly, to the amplitude of the pollen curve and, finally, to the date on which the main concentrations occur. Regarding the influence of meteorological variables, the results obtained allow us to identify the average temperature and precipitation as the meteorological variables that affect the pollen concentration during the pre-peak period or during the post-peak period. Concerning the amplitude of the pollen curve, the results indicate that it is mainly related to the average temperature and hours of sunshine. Finally, the date on which the peak of maximum pollen concentration occurs is negatively related to the precipitation recorded during the beginning of the pollen season.

Conclusions. Functional data analysis has allowed to identify different behaviours in the pollen curve, providing information on the influence of the behaviour of meteorological variables on the pollen curve. This work provides relevant information for the understanding of aerobiological dynamics, as well as a new methodology that can be implemented to analyse pollen data series.

Variations in the fungal spore detection within urban environments

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Background. The analysis of fungal spores in the atmosphere is crucial for understanding the dynamics of terrestrial ecosystems and their interaction with urban environments. Fungal spore concentrations influence not only agricultural production but also human health due to the respiratory diseases they cause, including allergies, which results in high economic losses (Simović et al., 2023). However, the spore airborne concentrations may vary depending on land use and local environmental conditions, which underlines the importance of investigating their presence in different locations within urban areas (Singh & Kumar, 2022). The aim of this study was to analyze the variation in fungal spore diversity and concentrations in seven sampling sites in the city of Malaga (southern Spain).

Methods. The monitoring was carried out using a Hirst-type volumetric pollen trap situated at seven sampling locations within Malaga city. Malaga is a coastal Mediterranean urban area, densely populated, with an uneven distribution of the green areas and diverse land use. Both coastal and inland locations were sampled in densely and more sparsely populated neighborhoods with different abundance of green areas. The pollen trap was placed in each location for two hours. Fungal spores were identified and counted, and their relative abundance was calculated. For each sampling location, the Shannon H index was calculated to determine the spore diversity.

Results. The results revealed an overall higher relative abundance of the spore types *Cladosporium cladosporioides* (Fresen.) G.A. de Vries, *Cladosporium herbarum* (Pers.) Link, *Coprinus* Pers., 1797, Aspergillaceae, *Alternaria* Nees, *Dreschlera* S.Ito, 1930 and *Myxomycetes*. A greater diversity was observed in the locations that combined extensive green areas and densely populated neighborhoods. One of the sampling points (i.e., Camino de San Rafael) presented a slightly higher spore diversity due to the greater heterogeneity of its surroundings, combining the presence of green areas, densely populated areas, industrial estates and wastelands. Minority spore types were identified in some locations, which have not been found in the rest of the locations, such as *Arthrinium* Kunze, 1817, *Botrytis* P.Micheli, 1729, *Curvularia* Boedijn, *Erysiphe* R.Hedw. ex DC., 1805 and *Spondycladiella*.

Conclusions. The variation in the abundance of fungal spores in the atmosphere of Malaga may be a function of land use, which highlights the relevance of urban planning in the prevention of respiratory allergies and, thus, in promoting healthier and more sustainable urban environments. In addition, these results bring to the fore the importance of monitoring airborne spores in different parts of the cities. Future research is required to assess the impacts of microclimatic conditions on fungal spore dynamics.

References. Simović, I., Matavulj, P., & Šikoparija, B. (2023). Manual and automatic quantification of airborne fungal spores during wheat harvest period. *Aerobiologia*, 39(2): 227-239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10453-023-09788-5>.

Singh, A. B., & Kumar, P. (2022). Climate change and allergic diseases: An overview. *Frontiers in Allergy*, 3: 964987. <https://doi.org/10.3389/falgy.2022.964987>.

Spore levels of Albuginaceae species in the atmosphere of central Iberian Peninsula

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Background. Albuginaceae is a family of plant pathogenic oomycetes that cause diseases known as "white rust" on a wide range of angiosperms species, some of which are of agronomic interest. The most characteristic symptom of these diseases is the appearance of pustules, which upon rupture release spores that are dispersed by the wind. The study of airborne spores in agricultural areas provides information on their presence and risk of infection by phytopathogenic fungi in crops. The aim of this work was to analyse the dynamics of Albuginaceae airborne spore concentrations in central Iberian Peninsula, as well as their relationship with different meteorological variables.

Methods. The study was carried out in the year 2023 in an agricultural area with Mediterranean climate located in the west of the province of Cuenca (Castilla-La Mancha, central Iberian Peninsula). Aerobiological sampling was carried out using a volumetric Hirst spore trap (LANZONI VPPS-2000) which was placed in an area of vineyards and herbaceous crops. Samples were prepared and analysed following the methodology established by the Spanish Aerobiology Network. Meteorological data were obtained from the Spanish Meteorological Agency (AEMET). The relationship between spore concentrations and meteorological variables was analysed using Spearman's non-parametric correlation test and principal component analysis (PCA). An intradiurnal analysis of spore concentrations was also performed.

Results. In 2023, a total of 15,561 spores/m³ were registered. The spores are present in the atmosphere between June and October. During this period, two stages are distinguished. The first runs from mid-June to the end of August, with a maximum concentration peak of 493 spores/m³ on July 14th. The second stage runs from the end of August to the end of October, with a maximum spore concentration of 2165 spores/m³ on October 14th. In the first stage, wind speed have a positive influence on spore concentration. In the second stage, temperature and sunshine hours have a positive influence, while wind, relative humidity and precipitation have a negative influence on spore concentration. Analysis of intradiurnal variation showed that Albuginaceae spores appear throughout the day, although they reach their peak in the central hours of the day.

Conclusions. The period when Albuginaceae spores are in the atmosphere coincides with the growing season of sunflower, so it is necessary to follow the phenology and monitor the health status of the crop. The ability to sporulate under exposure to sunlight and the possibility of spore dispersal in periods of low humidity show that Albuginaceae spores are highly adapted to the environmental conditions of the central Iberian Peninsula.

Usefulness of questionnaires in the allergenic risk assessment

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Background. Allergic subjects should avoid the exposure to pollen allergens, but this recommendation is difficult to comply with (Suanno et al., 2021a). Although pollen forecasting and allergenicity indices can provide an evaluation of the allergenic risk for a certain area, this risk has never been compared to the severity of the allergic symptoms observed in such area. Hence, the relevance of these tools in pollen allergy management remains unclear. In the present study, we addressed this issue by comparing the allergic symptoms experienced by the visitors of the Botanical Garden of Bologna (Italy) with the allergenic airborne pollen concentrations, forecasted and observed, and the risk levels estimated by two allergenicity indices (Suanno et al., 2021b).

Methods. Allergic symptoms were evaluated by administering a custom questionnaire to the visitors of the Botanical Garden on a voluntary basis. The main aims of the questionnaire were to estimate the prevalence of the pollen sensitisation among the interviewed subjects, to analyse the intensity of their symptoms during the visit, and to identify possible biases influencing their symptoms. During the questionnaire distribution, a portable Hirst-type sampler was operated at 1.6 m above ground level to evaluate the actual pollen exposure of the respondents. The results were then compared to the allergenicity indices previously calculated for the Garden, and to the pollen bulletins and calendars provided by the Regional Environmental Protection Agency (ARPAE).

Results. The self-reported prevalence of pollen sensitisation was overall in line with the epidemiological data from Europe and Italy (33.7%), with 61% of the allergic subjects sensitised against Poaceae. Interestingly, the self-diagnosis of pollen allergy resulted more common for the respondents who spent most of their lives in rural areas (39.5%) compared to those who lived mainly in urban areas (31.8%). The average intensity of the allergic symptoms experienced by the surveyed subjects was low (1.71 over 5), in line with low allergenicity risk estimated by the Urban Green Zones Allergenicity Index (I_{UGZA}) for the Garden. Remarkably, no correlation was found between airborne pollen concentrations at ground level and symptoms intensity. Moreover, the average intensity of allergic symptoms correlated neither with the surface cover of the allergenic families, nor with the allergenicity indices calculated for each allergenic plant family. Furthermore, while a correlation was found between ground-level pollen concentrations and ARPAE pollen bulletins for some plant families, the pollen calendar failed to predict both the ground-level and the rooftop-level pollen loads.

Conclusions. This study demonstrated that the correlation between allergenic potential of the vegetation, pollen loads, pollen forecasting, and allergic symptoms cannot be assumed *a priori*, underlining the importance of keeping allergic symptoms into account when evaluating the allergenic risk.

References. Suanno, C., Aloisi, I., Fernández-González, D., & Del Duca, S. (2021a). Pollen forecasting and its relevance in pollen allergen avoidance. *Environmental Research*, 200: 111150.

Suanno, C., Aloisi, I., Parrotta, L., Fernández-González, D., & Del Duca, S (2021b). Allergenic risk assessment of urban parks: Towards a standard index. *Environmental Research*, 200: 111436.

Comparison of pollen records from two different counties in Santiago de Chile

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Background. Since 1990 systematic counts of airborne pollen are performed in Santiago de Chile in the pollen monitoring station located in the Providencia County. Santiago, the capital of Chile, is located in a valley flanked by mountains, and present a Mediterranean climate with temperatures that oscillate from 2°C to 35°C. Providencia county has an average altitude of 604 m and it is characterized by a significant presence of buildings, with business and residential areas. Until 2021, there was only one pollen monitoring station in Santiago and since September 2021 a new station was added in Las Condes County, which is closer to the Andes, with an average altitude of 709 m, being mainly a residential area. The purpose of this study was to compare the pollen spectra from two different stations in the same city, to figure out if there are significant differences between them which could justify the need to incorporate more pollen monitoring stations in Santiago.

Methods. A Burkard volumetric sampler was used to collect the airborne pollen in Providencia and Las Condes. The airborne pollen concentration and composition were analyzed from January 2022 and December 2023. To compare the two different pollen records T student was used.

Results. When comparing the total pollen record from the two stations there were no significant differences between them, but when comparing the records from individual species we saw some significant differences. Pollen from *Acer* and *Rumex*, were higher in Providencia on 2022, but not on 2023 while pollen from *Populus* and *Ulmus* were higher in Las Condes on 2022, but not on 2023. Pollen from Cupressaceae, *Fraxinus*, *Ginkgo* and *Liquidambar* were higher in Las Condes on both years.

Conclusions. Surprisingly there were no significant differences on global pollen records from 2022 and 2023, despite 2023 was much rainy than 2022. Also, there were no significant differences on global pollen records between centers, despite Las Condes is closer to the mountains rich in native trees and grasses. Interestingly in Las Condes we observed higher pollen concentration from ornamental trees, that could be related with the residential character of the county, while in Providencia we observed a higher pollen concentration from *Acer*, that could be related to a county tendency on landscaping and also higher pollen concentrations from *Rumex* that could be explain because of the presence of a big hill in the middle of the county which is full of it. Even the differences are small, the information collected from the new pollen station is important and could be very useful for clinicians when choosing an immunotherapy for patients who live in Las Condes, especially in relation to Cupressaceae pollen which is a very allergenic pollen. Clearly adding more pollen monitoring stations in Santiago is a contribution and would be interesting to incorporate more stations along de city in the future.

Cipro, an aerobiological monitoring station representative of Rome's urban centre: five years in comparison (2019-2023)

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Background. Aerobiological monitoring is a multi-purpose tool: it can be used for allergy prevention through the publication of weekly bulletins, it can be a tool for monitoring changes in the composition of flora and vegetation over time, and it can be an element of climate change assessment. The presence of numerous monitoring centres in a nation is certainly an asset, in Italy as in other European and non-European countries. This can lead to stations representing one type of environment and not others. In order to propose a classification of monitoring centres along the lines of what has already been done for air quality measurement stations, in 2017 the Rome 'Tor Vergata' Aerobiological Monitoring Centre installed a sampler at the Vatican Museums (31 m a.s.l., 41°54'26.6" N, 12°26'57.0" E). The neighbourhoods that fall within the sampling radius of the VPSS[®] 2000 sampler present a predominantly built-up and busy area, with roads with and without street trees, green areas that fall within the nearby Vatican City State or Monte Mario Park.

Methods. A Hirst type volumetric pollen sampler VPSS[®] 2000 Lanzoni was used for aerobiological monitoring with a sampling radius of 12-15 km as required at national and international level by the UNI EN 16868:2019 standard in force. The years from 2019 to 2023 were considered for a total of 1820 sampling slides analysed, qualitatively and quantitatively, using the standard routine method, continuous swipe reading. The pollen data used refer to the daily concentration, expressed as pollen grains/m³ air. Statistical processing made it possible to calculate the phenological (beginning, end, duration of the pollen season) and production indicators (API_n - Annual Pollen Integral, peak day and maximum concentration) of the main families or genera of allergenic interest most representative of the area investigated: four arboreal Cupressaceae-Taxaceae, *Quercus* spp., *Olea europaea* L. and Platanaceae (*Platanus hispanica* Mill. ex Münchh) and two herbaceous Poaceae and Urticaceae.

Results. The evidence shows that the herbaceous taxa considered show greater variability for production indicators, phenological indicators and peak day over the five-year period investigated. Comparing the duration of the pollen seasons, it can be seen that of the herbaceous species (Poaceae) is longer (spring-summer) than that of the tree species, with a delay of up to 120 days at the end of flowering, probably because their anthesis is influenced more by meteorological variables such as precipitation. The API_n and peak day show fluctuations of up to 4 weeks.

Conclusions. This study highlights how the 'urban heat island' phenomenon, specific to urban centres, accelerates the onset of flowering and other physiological rhythms of certain plant processes.

Reference. UNI EN 16868:2019 (2019). Ambient air – Sampling and analysis of airborne pollen grains and fungal spores for allergy networks. Volumetric Hirst method.

**AEROPALYNOLOGY:
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS**

Preliminary aerobiological study of a semi-urban area in the central west of the Iberian Peninsula

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Background. Most aerobiological studies have been carried out in densely populated urban areas. The objective of the study is to characterize the most abundant pollen types in the atmosphere of a semi-urban location and establish whether there are differences with nearby urban centers.

Methods. The study was carried out in Peñaranda de Bracamonte (Salamanca) between January 2021 and December 2023. The samples were taken using a Hirst “Lanzoni VPPS 2000” volumetric trap. The preparation and reading were carried out following the standards established by the Spanish Aerobiological Network (Galán *et al.*, 2003). Data processing was made using “AeRobiology” package in “R” (Rojo *et al.*, 2019). The atmospheric pollen season (APS), its maximum concentration value, the prepeak period and the annual and main season pollen integrals (API_n, SPI_n) were established and compared with a study carried out in nearby areas (Rodríguez de la Cruz *et al.*, 2010). Meteorological data were provided by the Spanish Meteorological Agency (AEMET in Spanish). To evaluate the influence of the most relevant meteorological parameters on atmospheric pollen concentrations, the Spearman’s nonparametric test was used with SPSS software v.23.

Results. The most abundant types of pollen found were *Quercus*, Poaceae, Cupressaceae and *Olea*. The same order of types appears in the study carried out in Salamanca (40 km west of the sampling point), although the relative abundance of *Quercus* was higher in the semi-urban area (42% of total pollen recorded vs. 26%). Positive and significant correlations were obtained among temperature, insolation hours, average wind speed and pollen levels of *Quercus*, Poaceae and *Olea*. These types of pollen showed negative correlations with relative humidity and precipitations. In the case of Cupressaceae, similar correlations were obtained considering only the winter months.

Conclusions: The main atmospheric pollen types in the semi-urban area studied were the same as in nearby urban localities, although further analysis of their daily and hourly behavior is needed to establish differences between urban and semi-urban areas.

References. Galán, C., Cariñanos P., Alcázar, P., Domínguez, E. (2007). *Spanish aerobiology network (REA): Management and quality manual*. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Córdoba.

Rojo, J., Picornell, A., Oteros, J. (2019). AeRobiology: the computational tool for biological data in the air. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13203>.

Rodríguez-de la Cruz, D., Sánchez-Reyes, E., Dávila-González, I., Lorente-Toledano, F., & Sánchez-Sánchez, J. (2010). Airborne pollen calendar of Salamanca, Spain, 2000–2007. *Allergologia et immunopathologia*, 38(6): 307-312. 10.1016/j.aller.2010.04.001

Have the trends and intra-diurnal dynamics of *Olea europaea* and *Platanus* pollen changed during three decades of aerobiological studies?

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Background. Important environmental changes linked to changes in the phenological cycle of plants, together with increasing trends in the prevalence of pollen allergy have been observed in recent years. In this context, it is important to know the diurnal and seasonal patterns of pollen concentrations. This will help to improve allergy prevention in urban areas. *Olea europaea* is the taxon most used in agriculture in the Mediterranean region, being the most widespread crop in Andalusia. It is also used as an ornamental tree in parks and streets in the region, along with *Platanus* L. This study aims to establish if the annual trend and the hourly dynamic of *Olea europaea* and *Platanus* pollen types have changed over the last 30 years.

Methods. The temporal dynamics study was carried out in the city of Granada (south-east Spain, 37°11' N, 03°35' W, 685 m.a.s.l. and 23 m.a.g.l.) using a Hirst-type volumetric trap. The samples were analysed according to the standards of the Spanish Aerobiological Network and the annual trend was studied for the period 1992-2022. In this period, the average pollen season was calculated at 90% for the *Olea europaea* and *Platanus* pollen types to carry out the hourly count. With all, we compare the hourly dynamics of the pollen of these taxa between the years 1993-1994, at the beginning of the series, and compare it with the hourly dynamics of the years 2021-2022 at the end of the series.

Results. The Annual Pollen Integral (API_n) of *Olea europaea* pollen over the three decades of data show a significant increasing trend (Spearman test $p < 0.001$), which can be interpreted as an annual increase of more than 300 pollen grains/year (Theil Shen estimator). *Platanus* pollen also shows a significant increasing trend (Spearman test $p < 0.001$) with an annual increase of 59 pollen grains/year (Theil Shen estimator). The comparative study between the intradiurnal dynamic pollen of 1993-1994 and 2021-2022 showed a change in the hourly distribution of *Platanus* pollen. In the period 93-94, the maximum pollen concentration was registered between 13.00 and 18.00, peaking at 15.00, whereas in the period 21-22, this maximum was concentrated between 13.00 and 22.00, peaking at 18.00. In the case of *Olea* pollen, no diurnal dynamic changes were observed in the aerobiological data.

Conclusions. The increase in API_n throughout the 30 years studied and the increase in the number of hours of pollen permanence in the case of *Platanus* pollen may be causing a change in allergic symptoms, increasing and extending the hours of the day in which the symptoms are more severe. The ornamental use of these taxa in the city should be reconsidered as it may further worsen the health of patients with pollinosis.

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***Plasmopara viticola* infection risk management using aerobiological, phenological data and Goidanich index in a vineyard (north-west Spain)**

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Background. Phytopathogenic fungi are one of the main causes of production losses in the vineyards of northwest Spain. One of the most important diseases is downy mildew, caused by *Plasmopara viticola* (Berk. & Curtis) Berl. & de Toni pseudofungi. The climate in this area, with high temperatures and relative humidity during the grapevine vegetative cycle, can especially favour the development of fungal diseases in vineyards. The aim of the present study is to propose a system containing phenological data, biological sensors of pathogen indicator (aerobiological data) and the agrometeorological Goidanich Index in order to optimize the application of downy mildew fungicide treatments, and thus reduce crop losses.

Methods. A phenological and aerobiological study of the Treixadura grape variety was carried out in a vineyard belonging to the Ribeiro Designation of Origin (Ourense-Spain) from 2014 to 2023. Aerobiological study was conducted with a Lanzoni VPPS-2000 pollen and spore trap placed inside the vineyard. Phenological data were performed on 20 selected vines, following the Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt and chemical industry (BBCH) standardized scale. In order to ascertain the possible periods of disease attack, infection risk cycles were calculated following the methodology proposed by Goidanich et al. (1957).

Results. During the study period, the highest total *P. viticola* sporangia amount was recorded in 2018 with 3606 sporangia, and the lowest take place in 2015 with 277 sporangia. Analyzing the sporangia concentration by phenological stage, we observe that the highest sporangia concentration took place in stage 7 (Development of fruits) with 2468 sporangia in 2018 year, and the lowest concentration took place in stage 8 (Ripening of berries) 9 sporangia in 2022 year. The highest number of infection cycles was recorded during the 2018 harvest, with a total of 15 cycles. Years with fewer infection cycles were 2015 and 2022 (9 cycles). Primary infections were produced during the second half of April and a high amount of secondary infection cycles were detected by Goidanich algorithm during the fruit development and berry ripening stages. Finally, we carried out a PCA analysis, this analysis showed that the variables most related to *P. viticola* concentrations were relative humidity and temperatures.

Conclusions. The combination of aerobiological sensors, phenology variables and Goidanich index provide a valuable tool to establish an accurate, modern, integrated downy mildew pest-management strategy.

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Prediction of grape production in Treixadura cultivar using aerobiological, phenological and meteorological variables (northwest Spain)

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Background: Nowadays and under the current context of climate change, it is increasingly important for the viticulture sector to know the potential grape production in advance of the harvest. This will help us in harvest and post-harvest planning tasks, allowing wineries to estimate the needs in terms of agricultural insurance and harvesting labor, optimize post-harvest processes and detect frauds as a consequence of grape introduction from outside into the denomination areas.

Methods: A phenological and aerobiological study of the Treixadura grape variety was carried out in a vineyard belonging to the Ribeiro Designation of Origin (Ourense-Spain) from 2006 to 2022. Aerobiological study was conducted with a Lanzoni VPPS-2000 pollen and spore trap placed inside the vineyard. Phenological data were performed on 20 selected vines, following the Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt and chemical industry (BBCH) standardized scale. Pollen production per Bunch, per anther and per grapevine was studied during the flowering stage (stage 6). This information was used to develop a prediction model for local grape production.

Results: During the study period, the highest total fungal spore amount was recorded in 2008 for *Botrytis cinerea* Pers. (De Bary) with 41492 spores, in 2016 for *Erysiphe necator* Schwein with 17111 spores and in 2018 for *Plasmopara viticola* (Berk. & Curtis) Berl. & de Toni with 3670 sporangia. The highest number of flowers per plant (6565) and airborne pollen (359) was recorded in 2013, and the lowest number of flowers per plant (1594) and airborne pollen (90) took place in 2008. The year with a highest final grape production was 2010 with 12734 Kg, on the contrary the lowest production took place in 2018 with 2102 Kg. This information and the meteorological data were used to develop a model for predicting Treixadura yield, this model accounted for 69.2% of harvest variability.

Conclusions: The use of disciplines such as Aerobiology, Phenology and the Phytopathogenic fungi concentration can be very useful as tools to lose the *Vitis vinifera* final harvest.

Comparison of *Alternaria* spore levels between two cities (Bragança and Salamanca)

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3

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Background. Our study aimed to provide information on the atmospheric concentration levels of *Alternaria* fungal spores in two cities, Bragança, in Portugal, and Salamanca, in Spain, also exploring their geographic dependence, since different climatic regions present different patterns. This is of great relevance, as there are many fungal spores related to allergic processes, with *Alternaria*, from the taxonomic class of ascomycetes, being one of the most studied. The allergenic relevance is due to the large quantity of this spore type in the air and the fact that more and more people are sensitized to it.

Methods. Hirst type 7-day volumetric spore samplers (Lanzoni VPPS 2000 in Bragança and Burkard in Salamanca) were used, in Salamanca the trap is located on the roof of a historic building in the city center (14 m high), in Bragança installed on the roof of the Hospital Unit (25 m high). The sampling flow rate was 10 liters of air per minute, equivalent to the air flow inhaled by the human lung. The samples were continuously collected during 2021. The methodology used to obtain and process the samples followed the EN 16868:2019-09. Counts were carried out in two or four equidistant longitudinal scans at a magnification of 40x under an optical microscope. The data obtained were expressed in spores/m³.

Results. Comparing concentrations between the cities, we see that there is a similar behavior between them, where values increase with the arrival of the hottest months of the year and decrease again in winter (December-February). In August, in Salamanca and Bragança there was a sharp drop in concentration. The highest concentrations found in the two cities were observed in September, which also coincides with similar research results in other areas of the Mediterranean. The hydrographic situation of Bragança and Salamanca influences the quantity of spores collected, since they are located in a continental climate, which could explain the similar behavior in spore concentrations compared to other continental cities.

Conclusions. Therefore, it can be concluded that the warmer months with not so low rainfall, which is the case of September, regardless of the city, are the most problematic for allergenic individuals sensitized to *Alternaria*, as this is where there are greater concentrations of spores of the fungus.

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Estimation of potential pollen production of different *Plantago* spp. species in Central Iberian Peninsula

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Background: The pollen production of plant species is conditioned by genetic and physiological factors, as well as by meteorological factors, which influence both the duration of flowering and the rate of pollen production (Galán et al., 2008). Species of the genus *Plantago*, presenting anemophilous pollination, release large amounts of pollen into the atmosphere due to the imprecision of using wind as a vector for pollination, and this pollen is highly allergenic (Galán Labaca et al., 2010).

Methods: The aim of this study is to investigate the pollen production of three species of *Plantago* (*P. lanceolata* L., *P. coronopus* L., and *P. sempervirens* Crantz) located in the central Iberian Peninsula, where pollen production per anther, flower, inflorescence, and plant will be calculated. To achieve this, the protocol used by González-Parrado et al. (2015) will be followed. Thus, three individuals of each *Plantago* species will be collected from each of which two inflorescences will be analyzed. From these inflorescences, three flowers will be chosen, and from each flower, two anthers will be analyzed. Additionally, the number of inflorescences per specimen, the length of the inflorescence, and the number of flowers per analyzed inflorescence will be considered.

Results: Among the three selected species, *Plantago lanceolata* showed the highest pollen production, followed by *P. sempervirens* and *P. coronopus*, which showed very similar values. The pollen production values per plant were 58.353.186, 15.763.223 and 13.570.049 grains respectively.

Conclusions: *P. lanceolata* has been shown to be a species with high pollen production, as in other studies. Its high allergenic capacity and representativeness reveal its importance from a health perspective in the Iberian Peninsula. Future studies will allow for understanding pollen production in other species and its impact on sensitized populations.

References. Galán, C., García-Mozo, H., Vázquez, L., Ruiz Valenzuela, L., Díaz de la Guardia, C., Domínguez Vilches, E. (2008). Modeling Olive Crop Yield in Andalucía, Spain. *Agronomy Journal*, 100 (1): 98-104.

Galán Labaca I, Prieto A, Rubio M, Herrero T, Cervigón P, Cantero JL, Gurbindo MD, Martínez MI, Tobías A. (2010). Association between airborne pollen and epidemic asthma in Madrid, Spain: A case-control study. *Thorax*, 65: 398-402.

González-Parrado, Z., Fernández-González, D., Vega-Maray, A.M., Valencia-Barrera, R.M. (2015). Relationship between flowering phenology, pollen production and atmospheric pollen concentration of *Plantago lanceolata* (L.). *Aerobiología*, 31: 481–498.

**ARCHEOPALYNOLOGY:
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

More objective inference of regional vegetation subtypes using pollen assemblages from the East African Rift (Ethiopia)

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Background. The eastern branch of the East African Rift System is characterised by arid or semi-arid environments. In this environment, surface waters such as rivers, lakes, and areas of groundwater flow (springs) favour the development of wet local vegetation. With their dense tree cover and high plant diversity, these environments are particularly attractive to wildlife and have played, in the past, an important role in the human evolution. They are still important today for local populations, biodiversity conservation, and ecotourism, but they are threatened by climate change and human activity. The identification and monitoring of this vegetation in the past and present are therefore an important issue in order to respond to past, present and future ecological problems. A very good proxy for this task is the pollen tool, but this requires working below the regional vegetation scale, which is very difficult in East Africa with current palynological approaches.

Methods. Here, a new approach for calculating vegetation scores using statistical analysis and machine learning (k-nearest neighbor classifier) is developed and tested on 262 modern pollen samples of soils and muds collected in Ethiopia, Tanzania and in the Arabian Peninsula.

Results. Applying our new approach has made it possible to clearly distinguish 24 vegetations, 22 of which were subtypes of regional vegetation. Of these 22 regional vegetation sub-types, 10 are wet azonal vegetations. Our approach also makes it possible to associate the pollen signal with the morphology of the river (sinuous or rectilinear) and the type of vegetation strip along the banks (in particular the width of the vegetation strip). These two results show that it is possible to work much more effectively on the reconstitution and monitoring of vegetation below the scale of regional vegetation. This represents a major advance for palynology in East Africa.

Conclusions. The effectiveness of this new approach is linked to 3 fundamental differences from previous approaches: (1) no preconditions or opinions on the pollen types to be considered or the importance to be attributed to the various taxa, (2) the use of a threshold of 0.2% instead of the classic threshold of 0.5%, (3) the conversion of pollen data into relative abundances to the relative abundance scale for non-dynamic deposition environments and presence/absence for dynamic deposition environments.

BRAIN archaeobotanical database: pollen datasets for the diachronic study of Italian biodiversity

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Background. The study of botanical remains from human-modified sites (on-sites) and Holocene natural sequences (off-sites) is essential for understanding past and present plant biodiversity and the extent of human impact on a long-time scale. BRAIN-Botanical Records of Archaeobotany Italian Network is the first database collecting data from hundreds of archaeological sites in Italy and the Mediterranean with botanical research (<https://brainplants.successoterra.net/index.html>; Mercuri et al., 2015, accepted). BRAIN includes a collection of 800 sites with IDs, with metadata and references of sites that have provided data on microscopic (pollen, NPPs, phytoliths, microcharcoal particles) and macroscopic (seeds, fruits, wood/charcoal, artifacts) plant remains. The first pollen datasets were updated in 2024.

Methods. Sites analysed by the Laboratory of Palynology and Palaeobotany of Modena (LPP) were selected and tables of raw counts were prepared. The nomenclature and taxonomy of pollen types were checked, and a Doi was assigned to each dataset.

Results. Currently 42 LPP sites have been prepared for inclusion in BRAIN, for which 70 pollen series have been studied. 15 are off-sites and 55 are on-sites. An average of 122 pollen taxa are present per site, with herbaceous species being almost twice as diverse as woody species. The number of pollen samples per series ranges from 3 to 90. The number of taxa identified also varies widely, from 11 to 245 taxa per series. However, pollen biodiversity in the series almost always consists of more than 50 taxa, and pollen lists are often longer than 80 taxa per series, confirming that these data are very useful for biodiversity research. There is no strong correlation between the length of the floristic lists and the off-site records: on-sites also show extraordinary pollen diversity.

Conclusions. By processing BRAIN datasets, it is possible to study flora composition and change at regional and local scales, under climate and human impacts. BRAIN contributes to the knowledge of plant-human interactions in prehistoric and historic periods and increases the strategic role of Archaeobotany on current research priorities, such as biodiversity loss and nature conservation threatened by global change.

References. Mercuri, A.M. *et al.* (2015). Pollen and macroremains from Holocene archaeological sites: A dataset for the understanding of the biocultural diversity of the Italian landscape. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.*, 218: 250–266, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revpalbo.2014.05.010>

Mercuri, A.M. *et al.* (Accepted). BRAIN - Holocene archaeo-data for assessing plant-cultural diversity in Italy and other Mediterranean regions. *Sci. Data*

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Relevance of the pollen grain size criteria in palynology to identify cereals from wild grasses

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Background. Pollen analyses are commonly used to reconstruct the evolution of vegetation dynamics, environmental and climate changes as well as the impacts of human activities on watersheds and land uses. One of the most important challenges to discuss the evolution of the human-environment relationships over time in natural or archaeological contexts is to distinguish cereals from wild grasses within the Poaceae family. Although morphological criteria of the pollen grains are very discriminant to properly identifying most issuer plant genera and species, the Poaceae family needs a distinct approach. The main criterion is a morphometric one (*i.e.* grain and annulus diameters) but no consensus is emerging on threshold values. Thresholds commonly used do not appear to be fully satisfactory as revealed by irreconcilable time shifts regarding the appearance of agriculture between palynological and archaeological studies. Indeed, numerous occurrences of pollen grains identified as ‘Cerealia type’ have been found in many sedimentological records dated from the early Neolithic or Mesolithic periods over Europe. As the palynological distinction between cereals and wild grasses is crucial for identifying the earliest steps of agriculture, we'll take a closer look at the results of a study which proposes an unprecedented large-scale biostatistical study on pollen grains of current Poaceae species.

Methods. 117 species and 10 subspecies of both wild and cultivated Poaceae have been collected from different environmental contexts in the Brittany region (NW France). Diameter of the grain (or longest axis in few cases) and annulus diameter were measured on 100 pollen grains per species; statistical analyses (Fisher discriminant analysis) were carried out to discuss the thresholds used in the literature and try to establish a reliable one.

Results. The results of this study lead to a reappraisal of the commonly used thresholds to distinguish the first steps of agricultural practices in palynology because many wild species have pollen grains with morphometric characteristics similar to those of cereals. Biometric analysis shows the difficulty of defining whether a pollen grain belongs to wild grasses or cereals.

Conclusions. The conclusions of this study lead us to use biometric indices with great caution, and support the need to use also other indices to discuss the appearance and evolution of agriculture thanks to pollen studies.

Holocene paleoenvironmental reconstructions in western Brittany (Bay of Brest) with a focus on the Neolithic-Bronze transition

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Background. The Bay of Brest (BB, NW France) is a semi-enclosed basin of 180 km² subject to macro-tidal dynamics and to the fluvial influences of the rivers Aulne and Elorn, which combined drain watersheds of 2,600 km². This coastal environment is subject to natural climate oscillations overlaid on the long-term landscape transformations inherited from the post-glacial sea level rise and increasing anthropogenic forcing since the Neolithic (6.9 ka BP), and especially from the Bronze Age (4.2 ka BP) onwards. The BB therefore appears suitable for reconstruction of the interactions between climate, environment and human dynamics across the Holocene.

Methods. In this study, a palynological (pollen and dinoflagellate cysts) stack (X samples) was created based on eight cores: 5 cores previously analysed (core SRQ3-KS22: Lambert, 2017; cores 'A' and SRQ3-KS24: Lambert et al., 2019; cores 'G' and KS02: Lambert et al., 2020), and 3 new cores (cores PALM-KS05, PALM-KS06, and 'F'), allowing us to discuss the BB paleolandscape evolution over the last 7 kyrs.

Results. Since the Neolithic period, the forest cover has decreased in favour of open and agro-pastoral landscapes. This trend is not uniform, however: forest cover first declined slowly around 4 ka BP, then strongly decreased at the end of the Iron Age, before experiencing a revival of about 5 centuries at the end of the Roman period (1.7–1.2 ka BP). Finally, a drastic fall of tree pollen taxa is recorded at the start of the Middle Ages.

Conclusions. This study is the first on long-term Holocene trends in the BB that allows discussion of both climatic and anthropogenic forcing at an unprecedented study resolution of 35 years. We also place this local evolution in a wider regional context to detail interactions between natural and anthropic forcings over the last 7 kyrs BP.

References. Lambert C (2017). *Signature paléoenvironnementale des séquences holocènes en Rade de Brest : forçages climatiques et anthropiques*. PhD Thesis, Université de Bretagne occidentale, Brest, France.

Lambert C, Vidal M, Penaud A, et al. (2019). Palaeoenvironmental reconstructions during the Mesolithic to Neolithic transition (9.2–5.3 cal. ka BP) in Northwestern France: Palynological evidences. *The Holocene*, 29(3): 380–402.

Lambert C, Penaud A, Vidal M, et al. (2020). Striking forest revival at the end of the Roman Period in north-western Europe. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1): 21984.

Archaeopalynology at Palù di Livenza (PN, Northern Italy): adaptation and strategies of a prehistoric community in a changing environment

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Background. Palù di Livenza is a pile-dwelling Neolithic site located in Friuli Venezia Giulia, in Northern Italy. It belongs to the UNESCO world heritage list in the transnational series “Prehistoric pile-dwelling sites in the Alps” and it is one of the oldest Italian sites. Excavations carried out thanks to Soprintendenza ABAP-FVG, allowed to uncover several overlapping Neolithic features on stilts that followed each other between about 4400 and 3600 BC. Thanks to the peaty nature of the sediments, organic remains are well preserved, allowing the study of agricultural practices and plant exploitation (Zappa et al., 2023). The aim of the palynological analyses performed at Palù (both on-site and off-site) is to study the environmental transformations along time. In fact, these changes are often strongly influenced not only by climate but also by human presence, giving a unique insight into the human-environment relationship and into the adaptation strategies pursued by the local community in this peculiar environment.

Methods. Two on-site sequences and one off-site core were analysed for this study. The two on-site sequences were taken from the western side (PaluON1) and eastern side (PaluON2) of the southern section of the excavation trench. They consist of 20 samples each. The off-site record was cored 300 m away from the Neolithic settlement, in an area lacking archaeological material. The core is almost 6 m long with 21 samples. Samples were treated with a method including nylon sieving and heavy liquid floatation. Statistical elaborations were performed using Tilia software.

Results. Pollen spectra from all records show excellent pollen preservation and high plant biodiversity richness (> 100 taxa). Considering PaluON1 and PaluON2, some major changes are detectable. The cluster analysis highlights four Pollen Zones in PaluON1 (PDLW) and five Pollen Zones in PaluON2 (PDLE). The pre-settlement phases (PDLW1 and PDLE1) show 45% of Arboreal Pollen, with mixed oakwood (23%) and hygrophilous trees (10%) as the dominant taxa. During the most ancient Neolithic phases (PDLE2/PDLE3), cereals and Anthropogenic Pollen Indicators (API) gradually increase up to an average of 9% and 12%, respectively. In the most recent Neolithic phases (PDLW2/PDLW3 and PDLE4), cereals and API increase up to 13% and 15% on average, indicating proximal presence and extension of fields. Cereal values also suggest some plant processing in the site. During PDLW4 and PDLE5, forest cover reaches 60% on average, largely due to hygrophilous trees (36%), indicating a shift in vegetation towards wetter conditions.

Conclusions. The Palù basin provided optimal conditions for a pile-dwelling settlement due to its surrounding forest, wetlands, and land available for agriculture. Neolithic people exploited forest resources, planted fields, and shaped pastures. As the swamp expanded, likely due to changing climatic conditions, the site became unsuitable for habitation, leading to abandonment by the local Neolithic community and a return to natural plant assemblages and a hygrophilous wood.

References. Zappa, J., Degasperi, N., Bassetti, M., Florenzano, A., Torri, P., Servera-Vives, G., Mercuri, A.M., Micheli, R. (2023). Plants, Fire and Landscape at the Prehistoric Pile-Dwelling Village of Palù di Livenza (PaluON1), UNESCO Site in the Italian Alps. *Quaternary*, 6(2): 34.

**ARCHEOPALYNOLOGY:
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS**

Archaeopalynological evidence from the Holy Sepulcher area: preliminary results

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Background. The Basilica of the Holy Sepulcher, in the Christian quarter of the Old City of Jerusalem (Israel), represents an extraordinary site in terms of historical and cultural importance. An archaeological excavation connected with the restoration of the floor of the Basilica is being carried out by Sapienza University of Rome in accordance with the Communities who have custody of the Holy Sepulcher and licensed by the Israel Antiquities Authority. The archaeological study involves the comprehensive collection of all plant materials recovered during the excavation, including pollen. It is a rare opportunity to provide a paleoenvironmental reconstruction, the first palynological evidence from the Basilica of the Holy Sepulcher. In fact, of the archeopalynological research conducted in the Israeli region, only two studies have been conducted in the city of Jerusalem (Langgut et al., 2013; Kisilevitz et al., 2017). The purpose of this study is to enrich the information given by the study of macroremains in order to understand and reconstruct the past environment and the human impact from the pre-Basilica time to the Crusader.

Methods. Soil samples were directly collected adopting blanket sampling and sterile vials. A known quantity of *Lycopodium* spores was added to each weighted sample to estimate the concentration of pollen and non-pollen palynomorphs (NPPs). To obtain clearer slides, sample residues were sieved using a 10 µm nylon sieve and immersed in an ultrasonic bath. A transmitted light optical microscope with variable magnifications (400x and 630x) was used for the identification of pollen grains.

Results. This preliminary palynological analysis unexpectedly shows a good concentration for archaeological contexts, despite the poor preservation state. Anyway, an interesting insight of the Jerusalem vegetation is recorded with high values of non-arboreal pollen. Tens of different taxa have been identified, among them, in order of abundance, are Cichorieae followed by Asteroideae and Amaranthaceae. The arboreal flora list is quite rich, although in lower percentages: *Quercus ilex* type, *Olea*, *Quercus cerris* type, and traces of *Fraxinus* and *Pinus* were found.

Conclusions. The samples chronologically belonging to the quarry previous the Roman phase and the Basilica construction. The high amount of Cichorieae in all samples is the result of selective corrosion and overestimated the herbs. Nonetheless, the herbs assemblage describes an open environment with human disturbance as attested by *Urtica* and *Plantago* growing in pasturelands and disturbed areas. The trees list enriches the picture given by the charcoals giving an insight of the surrounding area.

References. Langgut, D. et al. (2013). Fossil pollen reveals the secrets of the Royal Persian Garden at Ramat Rahel, Jerusalem. *Palynology*, 37(1): 115-129.

Kisilevitz, S. et al. (2017). New Insights into Middle Bronze Age Burial Customs in Light of Recent Excavations at the Manaḥat Spur (Jerusalem) in *New Studies in the Archaeology of Jerusalem and Its Region*. Collected Papers XI. Jerusalem, 38.

Neolithic life in arid lands: pollen profiles and climate insights from the PPNB site of Nahal Efe (Northern Negev, Israel)

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Background. In this paper, the detailed pollen analysis and vegetation interpretation from the Neolithic site of Nahal Efe (Israel) is presented. The site is located in the north-eastern Negev at approximately 320 masl. Seven field seasons have been undertaken since 2015, revealing the largest and best preserved Pre-Pottery Neolithic B (PPNB) settlement in the Negev and Sinai, constituting a privileged data source for the study of hunter-gatherer communities that inhabited the Negev 10,000 years ago (e.g., Borrell *et al.*, 2015; Borrell and Vardi, 2022; Alcàntara *et al.*, 2023). The main occupation of the site corresponds to the Middle PPNB, dating to ca. 8000-7700 cal. BCE, with an estimated size of 2000 m². The extensive excavation of approximately 315 m² has revealed eight sub-circular semi-subterranean buildings, which seem to be part of a large residential area structured on different levels of the slope of the hill.

Methods. In this study, we reveal the results of pollen analysis of archaeological sediments from the Neolithic site of Nahal Efe, and the results of the anthracological analysis of charcoals from the collapse levels of one of the buildings excavated (Unit 8).

Results. The analysis suggests that the site surroundings were primarily dominated by desert vegetation, particularly herbs from the Saharo-Arabian desert biome such as Amaranthaceae or the *Anabasis*-type. The high prevalence of Asteraceae and low presence of Poaceae and the presence of drought-tolerant shrub communities including *Ephedra*, *Euphorbia* and *Artemisia* further underline the aridity of the conditions during the period of occupation. The sparse presence of arboreal pollen (AP), including taxa like *Pinus*, *Quercus* spp., *Pistacia* and *Tamarix*, suggests that while trees were not prevalent in a closed forest context, they did appear in more moisture-privileged or specific ecological niches, such as littoral zones or ephemeral riverbeds. This scattered distribution of trees likely reflects adaptations to the harsh, dry environment and, accordingly, its potential availability at a regional scale, a fact that in the case of the *Quercus ithaburensis* can be confirmed by the abundance of charcoals of this species in the collapse levels of one of the buildings excavated (Unit 8) and that has been interpreted as a result of the use of oak wood as building material.

Conclusions. This study contributes to the broader paleoenvironmental research in the Negev desert by providing specific data from 10,000 years ago that is relevant to reconstruct past climates and understanding early human adaptations to arid conditions. It also highlights the remarkable existence of relict Mediterranean vegetation areas near this northern Negev site exploited by Neolithic communities. Furthermore, this work emphasizes the importance of integrating botanical, archaeological and environmental data to gain comprehensive insights into past landscapes and climates, providing crucial insights into the climate and landscape dynamics of the region during this time.

References. Alcàntara, R., Sierra, A., Gourichon, L., Saña, M., Alejandre, J., Teira, L., Vardi, J., Borrell, F. (2023). Hunting at the fringe of the desert: Animal exploitation at Nahal Efe (northern Negev, Israel) during the Pre-Pottery Neolithic B. *Paléorient* 49(1): 163-189.

Borrell, F., Vardi, J. (2022). Chipped Stone Tool Production Strategies at Nahal Efe (northern Negev) during the Middle Pre-Pottery Neolithic B. In: Y. Nishiaki, O. Maeda, M. Arimura (eds.): *Tracking the Neolithic in the Near East. Lithic Perspectives on Its Origins, Development and Dispersals*: 311-326. Leiden: Sidestone Press.

Borrell, F., Boaretto, E., Caracuta, V., Cohen-Sasson, E., Lavi, R., Lupu, R., Teira, L. & Vardi, J. (2015). Nahal Efe: A Middle Pre-Pottery Neolithic B site in the north-eastern Negev. Preliminary results of the 2015 pilot season. *Neo-lithics* 2/15: 33-41.

Landscape dynamics in the NE Catalan coast from the Neolithic to the Late Roman times: Sant Antoni de Calonge coastal marsh

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Background. Coastal marshes are excellent archives for reconstructing landscape changes of coastal areas, due to the fact that these areas integrate high environmental variability and ancient human occupation. In the NE Iberian Peninsula, archaeological sites near the coastline have been documented and studied, such as the Roman villae of Sant Antoni de Calonge located in the Palamós littoral plain. However, no palaeoecological and palaeolandscape studies have been carried out to analyze landscape dynamics and human impacts. We present the first palynological study of a coastal marsh in the Sant Antoni de Calonge plain, that allows us to understand the evolution of the plant landscape and the human influence from the Neolithic period (c.a. 4,500 cal yr BC) to the Late Roman times (4th century AD).

Methods. A sedimentary record was retrieved from the marsh, from 6.90 to 11.60 m depth. An age-depth chronological model was established using eight ¹⁴C AMS dates calibrated using the open-source environment RStudio for R, the Clam package, and smoothing spline interpolation. A total of 29 samples were treated for palynological analyses following standard chemical procedures. A tablet of *Lycopodium* spores was added to estimate the pollen concentration. The counting and identification were carried out under an optical microscope using visual atlases and morphological identification keys.

Results. Results revealed a mixed woodland dominated by deciduous *Quercus* and *Q. suber* (>50% combined) at the beginning of the sequence (c.a. 4,500 cal yr BC). Forest values decreased progressively until 100 cal yr BC (20-30%), contrary to the percentages of holm oaks, which increased from <5% to 20% during the same period. This is in line with the increasingly drier climatic characteristics of the Iberian Mediterranean coastline throughout the mid Holocene. Regarding other taxa of interest, *Pinus* exhibits modest values, not reaching 25% during this period, while a non-continuous presence of *Abies* is detected through the sequence. The highest *Fagus* values are reported between 1,700 and 300 cal yr BC, but without reaching 5%. From 100 cal yr BC onwards, a landscape clearance occurred, as is shown by the expansion of Ericaceae (35-50%), *Cistus* (5%), and *Pinus* (15-37%). During this period, several samples reported the presence of coprophilous fungi, such as *Podospora*, *Sporormiella*, and *Cercophora*. The values of crops, such as *Olea* and *Vitis*, were very modest, with pollen being detected only in some samples and not reaching 2%. These evidences suggest a restricted farming activity. Finally, the pollen sequence also reflects changes in the marsh, mainly due to variability in salinity, as indicated by Cyperaceae, *Typha/Sparganium*, and Amaranthaceae, the latter probably being *Salicornia*.

Conclusions. This research fills a gap in the study of the evolution of the landscape on the north-east Catalan coast. In this way, it complements the information provided by the archaeological sites of the area.

**MELISSOPALYNOLOGY:
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

The automated microscopy empowered with Artificial intelligence that automatically analyzes honey quality: Honey.AI.

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Background. Pollen analysis stands as a longstanding and reliable technique for determining the botanical source of honey. Moreover, it serves as a valuable tool in evaluating purity, market worth, and geographical provenance. Unfortunately, pollen analysis remains intricate, demanding in labor, and heavily reliant on the expertise and experience of technicians. Considering these factors, we have devised an alternative solution aimed at enhancing usability. Honey.AI emerges as a digital asset tailored for beekeeping and honey industries, enabling the analysis of pollen, starch, yeast, color, conductivity (via an integrated probe), starch detection, crystallization measurement, and automated spore counting of *Nosema* spp. The primary aim of the Honey.AI device is to streamline and standardize the pollen identification process by integrating a low-cost optical microscope with Artificial Intelligence and image processing capabilities.

Material and methods. Honey.AI has been trained to accurately identify honeys from the Iberian Peninsula and is in the process of being extended to other parts of Europe. Currently, pollen percentage is tailored to monofloral honeys, identifying a single pollen type, but has been recently extended to a multi-spectrum analysis including predominant, secondary and minority pollen types, together with pollen richness and starch content. The new functionality is currently being tested by Apisol (ES) and Apisrom (RO), and following confirmation of accuracy measurements, will be released before summer 2024.

Results. As a result, apart from pollen analysis, pollen richness and starch content, the device performs other parameter measurements, enabling multiple results to be obtained with a single equipment. For instance, we have developed a method for measuring PFund color with the microscope, reproducing Hanna photometer values with an average error of less than 5 points. We also incorporated a conductivity probe to measure mineral concentration and help differentiate nectar honey from honeydew. Furthermore, a sensitive method has been developed to quantify the crystallization percentage of the sample, estimating its evolution in relation to glucose content, humidity and storage temperature.

Conclusions. Finally, as a novelty, the system has been adapted to provide support for the potential diagnosis of nosema disease in *Apis mellifera* with automated optical microscopy. This was developed on the basis of samples supplied by the Central Veterinary Laboratory in Algete (Spain), and with image processing and AI models, so that to validate good accuracies, a cross-validation between microscopy and PCR will be performed by summer of this year.

Palynological profile and physicochemical properties of *Tamarix* honey from Algeria

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Background. In Algeria, 80% of the country is covered by the Sahara Desert, because of this, just 3.5% of Algeria's total land area are utilized for agriculture (Bona et al. 2021). Despite the severe environmental conditions and poor plant cover, beekeeping is being developed and promoted in many domains including Saharan regions. In these areas, different types of honey are produced but few of them are studied. *Tamarix* honey is one of the important honey productions in arid and semi-arid regions, it is used, by local people, for its nutritional and therapeutic effect, but no study has been carried out on its characterization. *Tamarix* known as tamarisk, taray or salt cedar is a halophyte plant native from deserts and coastal areas that grows in hot and dry environments; however, it can be found also in temperate climates. In sandy and arid habitats *Tamarix* plants contribute to fix the sandy dunes (Bahramsoltani et al. 2020). This research aimed to provide knowledge about the physicochemical characteristics of tamarisk honey produced in these regions of Algeria.

Material and Methods. Seven samples of tamarisk honey are collected from arid and semi-arid regions of Algeria. The melissopalynological study was used to obtain the pollen spectra of samples and physicochemical parameters such as HMF, color, electrical conductivity, water content, pH, diastase content and anthocyanin content were measured to characterize the honey type. Furthermore, the phenolic profile was identified using a Triple Quad 3500 LC-MS/MS System.

Results. The obtained results showed that all the samples met the appropriate standards for good quality having low content of HMF (mean value of 3.9 mg/kg). Samples presented light amber color (65 mm Pfund mean), low electrical conductivity (0.274 mS/cm mean), water content mean of 17.0%, pH mean of 4.1 and diastase content mean value of 25.8°. *Tamarix* pollen was presented in a range between 45% to 96%, being the mean value 66.0%. The pollen type *Peganum harmala* was identified in all the samples and *Eruca sativa* was in 70% of them. Both pollen types were secondary or important pollen. Other representative pollen types were Asteraceae (*Chrysanthemum* type, *Centaurea* type and *Atractylis serratuloides*). The phenolic profile of the studied honey shows the presence of several flavonoid and phenolic acids, among them highlighted, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, p-coumaric acid, luteolin, isorhamnetin and galagin.

Conclusions. The results obtained provided information on the pollen spectra and the most important physicochemical characteristics of tamarisk honey and its phenolic compounds (phenolic acids and flavonoids), however, it is necessary to study more samples to reinforce these results.

References. Bahramsoltani, R., Mahdieh, K., Syed M. A. Z., Mohammad, H. F., Roja, R. (2020). The Genus *Tamarix*: Traditional Uses, Phytochemistry, and Pharmacology. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 246: 112245.

Bona, E., Nadia, M., Omrane, T., Giorgia, N., Patrizia, C., Valeria, T., Lara, B., et al. (2021). Climatic Zone and Soil Properties Determine the Biodiversity of the Soil Bacterial Communities Associated to Native Plants from Desert Areas of North-Central Algeria. *Microorganisms* 2021, 9 (7): 1359.

Contribution to the knowledge of pollen diversity in honeys from Campoo-Los Valles (N Spain)

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Background. The region of Campoo-Los Valles (1012 km²) temporarily had a Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) for honeys (Resolution of September 12, 2014) with two types: heather, made from different species of *Erica* L. and *Calluna vulgaris* (L.) Hull., and honeydew, made from oak honeydew. However, this category has been annulled due to administrative discrepancies relating to regional boundaries. In any case, greater knowledge of the pollen content of honeys produced in this region is needed to promote the development and implementation of protection regulations.

Methods. Melissopalynological analysis was carried out on 10 honey samples provided by different beekeepers following the proposal of the APLE Honey Working Group. These samples were obtained by centrifugation from apiaries with a fixed location in the summer of 2021 (González-Porto et al., 2018). These samples were analysed and processed according to the recommendations of the APLE Honey Working Group (González-Porto et al., 2018). Two of the samples were taken outside the transitional boundary that included the POD, although one was located a few kilometers away but in another administrative region (Cillamayor, Castilla y León region). The pollen spectrum of the different honey samples was evaluated according to Loveaux et al. (1978).

Results. In the ten samples analysed, an average number of 16 pollen types and 10 botanical families were identified, as well as an average number of 104606 botanical elements per sample. The pollen types with the highest average representation were *Erica* spp., *Cytisus scoparius*, *Castanea sativa* and *Quercus pyrenaica*. In honey samples obtained outside the geographical delimitation of the former POD, several types of pollen not present in honeys included in that area were identified, such as *Anthemis arvensis*, *Bellis annua*, *Calendula arvensis* and *Eucalyptus* spp.

Conclusions. The pollen spectrum of the honeys collected in the studied region corresponds to a large extent with the types of honeys marked in the cancelled POD. More studies, including more apiaries, years, both in the area and in neighboring areas, are recommended for the elaboration of future regulations.

References. González-Porto, A. V., Sánchez Reyes, E., De Linares Fernández, C., Rodríguez de la Cruz, D., Sánchez Sánchez, J., Belmonte Soler, J., Seijo Coello, M. C., Valencia Barrera, R. M., García Rogado, M. R., Matías Martínez, Y. (2018). El Grupo de Trabajo de la Miel y la normalización de protocolos de análisis melisopalinológicos". *IX Congreso Nacional de Apicultura*, Tenerife, España.

Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A. Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of Melissopalynology. *Bee World*, 59: 139-154.

Resolution of September 12, 2014, of the Department of Livestock, Fisheries and Rural Development, granting transitional national protection to the Protected Designation of Origin "Miel de Campoo-Los Valles".

Nutritive value of areas according to the botanical origin of the pollen loads

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Background. At this time there is a push to establish legislation (ISO Standards) at an international level, in order to define the criteria and requirements for quality and safety of bee pollen. This aims to improve consumer confidence and reduce the risk of fraud. The recognition of the qualities, description and classification of the productions of each country is necessary and will provide added value and a competitive advantage in the market. Spain presents a great variety of productions, according to the diversity in floristic and climatic composition. The collaboration between CIAPA and UAH allows us to obtain data that serve as a starting source in the description of the botanical origin of the foraged species and their nutritional composition with traceability of the hives used. This work presents the data regarding the nutritional value obtained in specific apiaries in Castilla-La Mancha.

Methods. The sugar, fat and protein contents of the taxa mostly collected in one hundred and ten bee pollen samples were analyzed in two apiaries located in different environments: one wild and the other cultivated. The methods used for this analysis are those used daily in food analysis laboratories. For sugars, a Y15 Analyzer from Biosystems was used, for the assessment of total protein the Kjeldahl method and for total fats the Soxhlet method. Only those homogeneous bee pollen loads were analyzed. We consider homogeneous samples to be those pollen loads of a given color, whose botanical origin of the pollen represents between 80% and 100% of the taxa identified in the sample.

Results. The chemical composition and nutritional value of the following identified taxa were analyzed: *Carduus* t., *Cistus*, *Rosa* t., *Brassica* t., *Quercus ilex* t., *Retama* t., *Genista* t., *Rubus*, *Papaver*, *Reseda*, *Olea*. The highest nutritional value (in kcal) corresponded to *Genista* t. (302), while the one inferior to *Quercus ilex* t. (198). Taxa of *Carduus* t., *Cistus* and *Olea*, have high sugar and fat contents (44-42 and 3.5-3.8%, respectively) and lower protein contents (16.6-20.2%), while taxa of *Rosa* t. and *Brassica* t. have high fat content (4.7-3.6%) and low sugar content (29-27%).

Conclusions. The study carried out and its conclusions are an important advance for a particular region to establish areas with different interest for bee nutrition. However, new studies applied to broader areas will help open the range of interesting areas in Spain.

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Preliminary melissopalynological analysis of honeys produced in the Sierra del Rincón Biosphere Reserve, Spain

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Background. The Biosphere Reserve "Sierra del Rincón" (Central Spain) with more than 15000 hectares and about 65 kilometers from the city of Madrid is an area of environmental relevance and beekeeping tradition. In the context of the project "Nectar: connecting territories through resilient beekeeping", the aim is to contribute to the botanical characterisation of the honeys produced in the area.

Methods. Twelve samples of honey harvested in the years 2021 and 2022 within the Biosphere Reserve were studied, as well as three other samples from nearby sites not included in the reserve. These samples were analysed and processed according to the recommendations of the APLE Honey Working Group (González-Porto et al., 2018). The pollen spectrum of the different honey samples was evaluated according to Loveaux et al. (1978). The electrical conductivity of the samples was calculated to determine whether they were nectar or honeydew honeys in each case, according to Spanish regulations (RD 1049/2003).

Results. The honey samples analysed showed an average content of botanical elements (116984, Class III Maurizio) as well as an average electrical conductivity of 0.85 mS/cm, with similar values for samples outside the study area. In terms of diversity, the samples from the natural area had an average of 25 pollen types belonging to 16 botanical families, a pollen variety similar to that of the external samples. The most represented pollen types were *Cytisus scoparius*, *Echium* spp. and *Cistus ladanifer* (22%, 14% and 10% average representation, respectively) for the honeys of the study area, while in the external honeys they were *Echium* spp., *Cytisus scoparius* and *Castanea sativa* (37%, 35% and 5%). Nine of the 12 samples were typified as honeydew honeys (as were all the external samples), one as multifloral, one as heather (*Erica* spp.) and one as Viper's bugloss (*Echium* spp.) honey, about the particular results of each sample.

Conclusions. The honeys produced in this area of high environmental interest reflect the variety of trophic resources available to the honey bee and allow beekeepers to obtain a quality product for consumers from a botanical point of view, although further studies are needed to confirm these preliminary findings.

References. González-Porto, A. V., Sánchez Reyes, E., De Linares Fernández, C., Rodríguez de la Cruz, D., Sánchez Sánchez, J., Belmonte Soler, J., Seijo Coello, M. C., Valencia Barrera, R. M., García Rogado, M. R., Matías Martínez, Y. (2018). El Grupo de Trabajo de la Miel y la normalización de protocolos de análisis melisopalinológicos. *IX Congreso Nacional de Apicultura*, Tenerife, España.

Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A. Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of Melissopalynology. *Bee World*, 59: 139-154.

Real Decreto 1049/2003, de 1 de agosto, por el que se aprueba la Norma de calidad relativa a la miel. «BOE» núm. 186, de 5 de agosto de 2003, páginas 30181 a 30183.

Pollen profile of honeydew honey from Montesinho Natural Park oak forest

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Background. Honeydew honey has a non-flowering origin. In the northwest of the Iberian Peninsula, it is produced mainly through the secretion of a sugary liquid from the acorns of *Quercus pyrenaica* and hybrids (Rodríguez-Flores et al. 2015). This honey shares its geographical area of production with chestnut honey, and thus it is not uncommon to find *Castanea* pollen in its pollen spectrum. In addition to *Castanea*, the presence of other pollen types is also common, including those of *Rubus* and *Cytisus* type, due to the overlapping of the flowering season. The pollen spectrum enables the characteristics of this honey to be differentiated from those of other honeydew honey originating from other geographical regions. In addition, the classification of honeydew honey is currently of commercial value. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify the diversity of pollen types of interest to beekeepers for the production of honeydew honeys in the northwest of the Iberian Peninsula.

Methods. A total of 80 samples of honeydew honey were analyzed from four apiaries situated within the Montesinho Natural Park oak forest. Samples were collected from honeydew inflow until the final harvest was made, from June to September. The pollen identification and quantification were conducted using melissopalynological analysis (Rodríguez-Flores et al. 2015).

Results. A total of 53 pollen types belonging to 33 families were identified in the 80 honey samples. During the collection period up to the end of the harvest, *Castanea* and *Rubus* pollen grains were present in 100% of the honeydew samples. Furthermore, the presence of *Cytisus* type, *Echium*, and *Cistus* pollen grains was common in the samples. Other pollen types that were also notable during the foraging period were Poaceae, *Plantago*, *Taraxacum officinale* type, and *Foeniculum* type. This honeydew honey type is characterised by a medium pollen content belonging to Maurizio's classes II and III and by a low quantity of honeydew element.

Conclusions. Honeydew honey is produced during the summer months, mainly between mid-July and August. This coincides with the time when oak trees begin to produce acorns. This is the time when the hive accumulates pollen and nectar from plants such as chestnut, blackberry, heather and broom, which are also present in other honeys produced in the inland areas of the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula. These plants are of great interest to beekeepers and may be the most likely source of the pollen profile of honeydew honey.

Reference. Rodríguez-Flores, M. S., Escuredo, O., Seijo, M. C. (2015). Assessment of physicochemical and antioxidant characteristics of *Quercus pyrenaica* honeydew honeys. *Food chemistry*, 166: 101-106.

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Bee pollen produced in Algeria: botanical origin and protein content

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Background. Algeria is the largest country in Africa, more than 80% of the country is a desert area, the Sahara region, and only 4% of the country corresponds to the Mediterranean region. Beekeeping plays an important role in the agricultural life of Algerians, it is practiced all over the country, however, this practice is more intense in the Mediterranean area due to the climatic conditions and the richness of biodiversity with near to than 4000 species and 178 recognized endemism (Bona et al. 2021). Bee pollen is one of the products of hive used by Algerian people for nutrition and in traditional medicine, due to its wealth of carbohydrates, proteins, lipids and on several nutritional and therapeutic properties. Nevertheless, few studies have been carried out on the identification and characterization of bee pollen from Algeria. For this reason, this study aimed to characterize some bee pollen samples and study the relationship between botanical origin and protein content of these samples.

Methods. Twenty-eight bee pollen samples were collected in the Mediterranean region of Algeria. The botanical origin of the samples was determined using a palynological analysis before the separation of the different pollen loads of 2 g of pollen by color. LC–MS/MS method was applied for the determination of free amino acids in bee pollen without derivatization steps.

Results. The palynological analysis of the samples enables to identify some pollen types belonging to the families of Cistaceae (*Cistus*), Myrtaceae (*Myrtus communis*), Brassicaceae (*Brassica napus* type), Tamaricaceae (*Tamarix*), Apiaceae (*Daucus carota* type, *Coriandrum*, *Ferula communis*), Anacardiaceae (*Pistacia*) and Fabaceae (*Hedysarum*, *Onobrychis*, *Acacia*) representing more than 30% of the bee pollen samples. The best-represented pollen types were studied regarding the protein content and amino acid profile. The results showed important differences in protein content, ranging from 28.9 g/100g to 10.2 g/100g. Moreover. The amino acid profile varied also with the botanical origin, but proline, glycine, alanine, serine, leucine, glutamic acid, aspartic acid and lysine were the most abundant.

Conclusions. The results obtained showed the richness of bee pollen on protein content and remarks the influence of botanical origin on the amino acid composition.

Reference. Bona, E., Massa, N., Toumatia, O., Novello, G., Cesaro, P., Todeschini, V., Boatti, L., Mignone, F., Titouah, H., Zitouni, A., Lingua, G., Vuolo, F., Gamalero, E. (2021). Climatic Zone and Soil Properties Determine the Biodiversity of the Soil Bacterial Communities Associated to Native Plants from Desert Areas of North-Central Algeria. *Microorganisms*, 9(7), 1359. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9071359>.

Spanish honey: botanical origin and physicochemical properties

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Background. Spain with about 3 million hives is one of the main honey producers of the EU. The rich biodiversity and the particularities of Spanish beekeeping allow to obtain many honey types with different properties and market value. Consequently, fluctuations in market demands and prices create opportunities for fraudulent activities. The absence of adequate legislation, including specifications for different honey types, compromises food safety and the assurance of honey authenticity. Increasing knowledge of relationships between botanical origin and physicochemical and healthy properties is essential to establish effective controls and to defend consumers' rights. VASBEEP project aims to improve knowledge of honey and bee pollen produced in Spain providing specific biomarkers for guaranteeing authenticity and detecting frauds. This work presents the first results obtained.

Material and Methods. One hundred and sixty-five honey samples were collected in different geographical areas of Spain. The honeys were studied regarding the palynological profile and physicochemical parameters. The pollen spectrum of each sample was obtained using melissopalynology (Louveaux et al., 1978). Physicochemical parameters (water content, pH, electrical conductivity, diastase content and color) were measured according to the methods proposed by International Honey Commission (Bogdanov et al., 2002).

Results. The most relevant honey types studied were chestnut, sunflower, heather, honeydew, blackberry, rape, rosemary, lavender, avocado, and multifloral honey. The pollen spectra presented a great pollen diversity, including more than 120 types. The best represented were Brassicaceae (mainly *Brassica napus* type), Fagaceae (*Castanea sativa* and *Quercus*), Fabaceae (*Genista* type, *Onobrychis*, *Trifolium*, *Vicia*, among others), Labiatae (*Lavandula latifolia*, *L. stoechas*, *Rosmarinus*, *Lamium*, *Thymus*), Rosaceae (*Rubus*, *Prunus* type), Ericaceae (*Erica umbellata*, *E. arborea*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Arbutus unedo*), Asteraceae (*Helianthus annuus*, *Centaurea*) and Myrtaceae (*Eucalyptus*). Pollen types from non-nectariferous species such as Papaveraceae, Poaceae, *Olea europaea* or *Quercus* were common in many of the samples. Regarding physicochemical parameters, electrical conductivity had a high variation related to botanical origin from near to 0,1 mS/cm to 1,5 mS/cm in straight relationships with color pattern (light honey to dark honey). Other physicochemical parameters such as water content, diastase content, pH, or free activity were related to botanical and geographical origin. Multivariate analysis allows the classification of samples regarding the botanical origin.

Conclusions. These are the first results of this research project. In the next years, a greater number of samples from different seasons will be studied to implement knowledge about the production of Spanish honey.

References. Bogdanov, S., Martin, P., Lullmann, C. (2002). Harmonised methods of the international honey commission. *Swiss Bee Research Centre*, Liebefeld, 5(1).
Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A., Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of melissopalynology. *Bee World*, 59(4): 139-157.

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**MELISSOPALYNOLOGY:
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS**

Pollen composition of stingless native bee honey (Meliponini) from Northeast Argentina, South America

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Background. Stingless native bees originate from tropical and subtropical forests worldwide. In Argentina, Meliponini are mainly distributed in the provinces of Salta, Jujuy, Formosa, Chaco, and Misiones. These bees do not sting, many of them are harmless, but they need to defend themselves against potential predators. To do so, they locate their nests in cavities which they enclose and seal with a hard material called "batumen". To protect their nests from intruders, the entrances of some Meliponini species are narrow and long. Honey was recently incorporated into the Argentine Food Code and is considered a genuine natural resource for communities in the northern region of the country. The aim of this study is to understand the floral resources used by stingless native bees to produce honey in the Northeast Argentine Region (NEA).

Methods. A total of 14 samples of honeys were collected from the provinces of Formosa (12) and Misiones (2) in Argentina during the periods 2020-2021 and 2022-2023. These samples were produced by 3 species of stingless native bees: *Scaptotrigona jujuyensis*, *Tetragonisca fiebrigi*, and *Plebeia* sp. The honey samples were processed using conventional techniques, mounted on permanent slides, and embedded in glycerinated gelatin (Louveaux et al., 1978).

Results. A total of 90 pollen types from 41 families of Angiosperms were identified. There were 7 monofloral honeys from native species: *Schinopsis balansae*, *Neltuma alba*, *Copernicia alba*, *Stemodia* sp., and 7 multifloral honeys. The honeys of *Scaptotrigona jujuyensis* contained pollen from *Schinopsis lorentzii*, *Tessaria integrifolia*, *Neltuma alba*, *Stemodia* sp., among others. In the honeys of *Tetragonisca fiebrigi*, the predominant pollen was from *Schinopsis balansae*, *Copernicia alba*, Type *Baccharis-Eupatorium*, *Neltuma alba*, *Psidium* sp., *Melilotus albus*, *Morus alba*, and *Pisonia zapallo*. Lastly, in the honeys of *Plebeia* sp., pollen from *Schinopsis lorentzii*, *Cynophalla flexuosa*, *Titbonia tubiformis*, and *Sideroxylon obtusifolium* stood out.

Conclusions. The honeys from the NEA Region collected from three species of stingless native bees exhibit a diversity of woody and herbaceous species, highlighting the value and richness of the native forest.

Reference. Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A., Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of melissopalynology. *Bee world*, 59(4): 139-157.

Study on the melissopalynological monoflorality for three Portuguese honeys

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Background. Portugal has a rich and diverse honey flora, predominantly wild species. This diversity allows the production of distinct monofloral honeys, such as lavender (*Lavandula pedunculata*), heather (*Erica* spp.) or chestnut honey (*Castanea sativa*), each with unique characteristics determined by specific geographical and botanical conditions. The main aim of this study is to deepen our knowledge of the botanical profile of Portuguese monofloral honeys with higher impact in the market, such as those mentioned above.

Methods. Honey pollen analysis, known as melissopalynology, plays a crucial role in identifying the botanical and geographical origin of honeys, as well as guaranteeing their authenticity. Using this procedure as the core methodology, the research involves quantifying the pollen density of the target species in the nectar, either within the gut of bees captured over the flowers, bees collected at the entrance of the colony, as well as in the fresh nectar deposited in the combs during peak flowering. Specific apiaries located in areas with a high concentration of the target plants were selected. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of the honey aims to determine the pollen coefficients, through the absolute number of pollens of the target species per 10 g of honey.

Results. As expected, the data revealed very different pollen densities between the plants under analysis, but also some variability was found considering the source where the nectar was collected.

Conclusions. This data can provide a better scientific basis for the certification of monofloral honeys but will also allow beekeepers to associate a distinctive quality label with their products, adding commercial value and promoting the authenticity of Portuguese honeys in increasingly demanding national and international markets.

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Melissopalynological characterization of honey samples: a preliminary study from Parco delle Serre, Calabria (Italy)

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Background. As a product that still interests a niche audience, honey doesn't enjoy as broad a market as other food products. This, combined with the increasing importation of non-European honeys that often do not meet regulations, has made it urgent to implement valorisation strategies to protect local productions. The use of geographical indications can be an excellent tool in this regard. This study aims to characterize and enhance honeys produced within the Calabrian territory which has well preserved environments in Southern Italy. The ultimate goal is laying the groundwork for establishing potential territorial quality labels such as PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) or PGI (Protected Geographical Indication).

Methods. The defining characteristics of typical honey products must be identified through a study primarily based on melissopalynological analysis and the identification of unique marker pollen in spectra, faithfully reflecting the floristic composition of the original territory. In total, 4 parks within the Calabria region, were selected for sampling: Parco Nazionale del Pollino, Parco Regionale delle Serre, Parco dell'Aspromonte, and Parco Nazionale della Sila. Bee-handling data by the producers were obtained for each sample. Melissopalynological analysis follows the method outlined by Louveaux et al. 1978, observing pollen forms in their fresh state and after acetolysis.

Results. Melissopalynological analysis are in progress, and the first honey results from Parco delle Serre are presented reporting the pollen spectra. The characteristic feature of these honeys is the almost constant presence of *Castanea* and *Hedysarum*. Recurrent are the pollen grains of early flowering species, such as Fabaceae (especially *Robinia* and *Genista*) and, to a lesser extent, Rosaceae (particularly *Malus/Pyrus* and *Prunus*), *Echium*, and Asteraceae. Also contributing to the pollen spectrum of these honeys are some ubiquitous and therefore less distinctive forms, such as Brassicaceae, and *Trifolium repens*. Among the non-nectariferous forms, the pollen of *Quercus robur* and *Papaver* are frequent.

Conclusions. Pollen spectra can serve as a valuable tool to gather data useful for distinguishing honey produced in Calabria from similar products of different geographic origin. These data could lay the groundwork for the application of optimal valorisation strategies in one or more of the studied areas.

Reference. Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A., Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of melissopalynology. *Bee world*, 59(4): 139-157.

***Erica* pollen type identification: improving the accuracy of the geographical origin of honeys**

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Background. The genus *Erica*, widely distributed in Europe, is of great interest in beekeeping, with heather honeys being among the most valued. The aim of this study is to identify the various pollen types of *Erica* in honeys with high heather content, in order to determine a more accurate botanical and geographical origin, and to contribute to assessing potential differences in their organoleptic characteristics.

Methods. The study areas are located in the provinces of León and Burgos (Spain), where 7 and 9 species of *Erica* are present, respectively. The 50 selected honeys come from stationary apiaries in areas where several species of this genus converge, according to the Anthos and GBIF databases, and which exhibit *Erica* pollen values higher than 15%. The differentiation of pollen types was based on reference samples from the Botany Department of the University of León and the pollen key to Ericaceae by Ramil et al. (1992), with the modification of *E. vagans*, which, due to its smaller size, is distinguished from the pollen type *E. cinerea*. Thus, the differentiated pollen types are: *E. arborea* (*E. arborea* and *E. lusitanica*), *E. australis*, *E. cinerea* (*E. ciliaris*, *E. cinerea* and *E. tetralix*), *E. scoparia*, *E. umbellata* and *E. vagans*. The method used for sample preparation follows Louveaux *et al.* (1978) without acetolysis, counting and identifying a minimum of 600 pollen grains by optical microscope at 400x (1000x when required).

Results. Half of all the samples analyzed were characterized as heather unifloral. Unifloral honeys from Burgos apiaries were all from *E. vagans*, with *E. cinerea* as important minor or only present pollen. Conversely, in those of León, there is greater diversity, yielding unifloral honeys of *E. vagans*, one of *E. arborea*, and various combinations of other pollen types, with *E. umbellata* and the *E. cinerea* type appearing as accompanying and important minor pollen, while *E. australis* only appears as present pollen.

Conclusions. Identifying the different pollen types of *Erica* in honeys, particularly *E. arborea* and *E. vagans*, from which unifloral honeys are obtained, enables us to determine a more precise botanical and geographical origin, and to find potential differences in organoleptic characteristics, thereby enhancing the value of the product.

References. Louveaux, J., Maurizio, A., Vorwohl, G. (1978). Methods of melissopalynology. *Bee world*, 59(4): 139-157.

Ramil Rego, P., Aira Rodríguez, M. J. Saá Otero, P. (1992). Clave polínica de las Ericaceae gallegas. *Lazarroa*, 13: 33-40

Botanical origin and mineral composition of Galician honey

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Background. The botanical origin of honey determines its composition and properties, being the most relevant factor influencing mineral content. The main mineral element in honey is potassium, but magnesium, calcium, phosphorus and sodium among others are well represented. The content of these elements is strictly related to honey color and other physicochemical parameters such as electrical conductivity. This study aims to investigate the relationships between mineral content and botanical origin of monofloral honey and honeydew honey produced in Galicia (NW Spain).

Material and Methods. Ninety-eight honey samples from heather (19 samples), chestnut (19 samples), eucalyptus (19 samples), blackberry (18 samples) and honeydew (23 samples), were studied regarding the botanical origin, physicochemical parameters and mineral content. The botanical origin of each sample was tested by melissopalynology, physicochemical parameters and sensorial profile. Quality parameters were measured following the methodology proposed by Bogdanov et al., (2002) and sensorial data was obtained with a trained panel. Regarding mineral content, the extraction was carried out using microwave digestion according to the methodology proposed by (Caroli et al., 1999). The mineral elements magnesium, copper, calcium, iron, phosphorus and zinc were quantified by atomic absorption, while sodium and potassium were quantified by atomic emission.

Results. *Rubus*, *Castanea*, *Erica*, *Eucalyptus* and *Cytisus* t. were found in more than 80% of the samples. *Eucalyptus* had a maximum value of 94.8%, while *Rubus* reached 91.3%, *Castanea* 90.0%, *Erica* 68.6% and *Cytisus* t. 48.6%. The mean values for the main pollen types according to honey type were as follows: heather samples (*Erica*, 40.2%), chestnut samples (*Castanea*, 78.1%), eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus*, 78.1%), blackberry (*Rubus*, 49.6%). Honeydew samples had as main pollen *Castanea* (44.3%) and *Rubus* (33.8%, but *Cytisus* t. occasionally was the dominant pollen. It was found significant statistical differences among honey types related to physicochemical profile and metal content. Potassium content varied greatly (377.0 mg/100g to 32.7 mg/100g), being the richest samples honeydew and chestnut. Calcium content varied from 48.1 mg/100g to 4.7 mg/100g, being chestnut honey the richest. In the case of magnesium content (40.2 - 1.5 mg/100g) and phosphorus content (31.5 - 1.6 mg/100g), the greatest mean value was for honeydew honey. Otherwise, heather and eucalyptus honey had the biggest sodium content (29.7 - 0.9 mg/100g). Finally, copper, iron and zinc had low values in all the samples. Multivariate analysis explained differences between groups of samples and enabled grouping them according to botanical origin.

Conclusions. The content of major mineral elements in honey varies significantly with the botanical origin.

References. Bogdanov, S., Martin, P., Lullmann, C. (2002). Harmonised methods of the international honey commission. *Swiss Bee Research Centre*, Liebefeld, 5(1).

Caroli, S., Forte, G., Iamiceli, A. L., Galoppi, B. (1999). Determination of essential and potentially toxic trace elements in honey by inductively coupled plasma-based techniques. *Talanta*, 50(2): 327-336.

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Analysis and composition of corbicular pollen collected in experimental hives at N'dali (North Benin)

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Background. The aim of this study was to collect and analyze corbicular pollen grains from hives installed in the commune of N'dali in the Sudanian zone of Benin. These corbicular pollens are only collected by female bees, which have specialized body parts (hind legs lined with small hairs called scopae or flattened plates lined with curved hairs (called corbicula) that function like brushes and baskets that can hold pollen grains in place. These enable them to collect and transport pollen grains to their hives.

Methods. The pollen was collected using pollen traps from January to April 2022, at a rate of one sample per month. A total of 4 samples (M1, M2, M3 and M4) of corbicular pollen pellets were collected and analysed microscopically. For all the samples, all the pollen loads were separated according to their colours using the Pantone table classification in order to identify the botanical origin of each type of pollen. A maximum of 10 slides of each colour of pollen load per sample were prepared and observed under the microscope.

Results. The dominant taxa in the four samples were : *Anacardium occidentale*, Combretaceae, Meliaceae/Sapotaceae, *Elaeis guineensis*, Fabaceae, *Isobertinia doka*, *Lannea* type, Onagraceae, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Senna* type, *Terminalia* type and *Trichilia* type. The accompanying pollen grains are : Amaranthaceae, Anacardiaceae, Asteraceae, Cyperaceae, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, Euphorbiaceae, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Khaya senegalensis*, Poaceae and Phyllanthaceae. Species such as *Parkia biglobosa* and *Elaeis guineensis* and Meliaceae/Sapotaceae are common to both groups.

Conclusions. It has been found that shades of colour can be associated with different types of pollen in the characterisation of particular species. This is the case for *Elaeis guineensis*, whose colour corresponds approximately to P466U of the same colour shade as several other species.

References. Carpentier, C. (2019). Collection en ligne de lames de pollen de l'ISEM. GDR 3644 Bioarcheodat. Consulté le 28 mars 2024. <https://doi.org/10.58079/>

Kénali I., Zanou A.R.S., Mama A., Amakpé F., Tossou M., Mensah G., Akoègninou A.. (2021). Contenu pollinique des miels récoltés dans un champ de *Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp (Fabaceae) dans la commune de Djidja (Bénin). *Ann. Sci. Limousin*, (30). <https://doi.org/10.25965/asl.115>

Pearce, Y. R. (2019). *Corbicular pollen studies from urban beekeeping*. Master's Degree in Biological Diversity and Environment. Specialty: Biodiversity and Management of the Continental Environment. University of Malaga. 55p.

**PALEOPALYNOLOGY:
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

Responses of cedar forests to Late Holocene disturbances in the Rif mountains (Morocco)

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Background. Mediterranean mountain conifers have progressively changed their distribution range since the Last glacial period. Probably, they reached their widest extension in lower altitude areas during cold periods, with a great connectivity between populations. As climatic conditions became warmer with the onset of the Holocene, they have steadily migrated upwards to find more suitable habitats. As a result, their populations fragmented, got isolated and even locally extinct in low-altitude mountains. *Cedrus atlantica* (Atlas cedar) is an endangered conifer species, whose populations in the North of Africa are severely threatened by extinction. The understanding of the processes involved in such altitudinal movements, as well as the identification of suitable refugia will help the design of the most appropriate protection measures, in order to ensure their future survival. This work falls within the scope of Conservation Paleobiology, which applies paleo-archives to address current problems in the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services. Specifically, our study is included in the project TED2021-132631B-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI /10.13039/ 501100011033 and Next Generation EU/PTR. These studies provide valuable information on millennial-scale responses to long-term drivers of ecosystem change.

Methods. We have analysed six pollen records, mainly covering the Late Holocene (ca. 4000 cal yr BP), in the Western and Central Rif mountains (Morocco), focusing on the patterns of change of cedar forests. The cores have been chosen according to the altitude in three different ranges, with also distinct current situations, such as an isolated population, extinction, and persistence of a wide population, respectively.

Results. After the greatest expansion of *Cedrus* in the Rif mountains during the first millennium of the Middle Holocene, ca. 7000-6000 cal yr BP, these forests have undergone an overall decline until today. Our detailed analysis of the changes undergone throughout the late Holocene, i.e. the last 4000 years, shows relevant shifts linked to the response of these populations to different ecological drivers. From West to East, in Jbel Bou Hachem climate could be the main factor driving vegetation until ca. 3200 cal yr BP, triggering the upward migration of cedar forests and the expansion of oak forests in mid altitudes. From this date onwards, human impact increases, lessening climate influence which allows successive recoveries of cedar forests, until their last decline. In Jbel Khesana, two upward migration events can be identified during the late Holocene, the main one from ca. 2300 to 1500 cal yr BP. The final demise of cedar forests can be attributed to human activities. Jbel Tidighine shows the persistence of cedar forests at higher altitudes (ca. 1700-1800 m) during the whole Late Holocene, with minor retreats likely related to human-induced disturbances.

Conclusions. While climate has been the primary driver of the shifts undergone by cedar forests in the Rif mountains until ca. 3200 cal yr BP, later, the increasing human impact has led cedar populations to an overall decline. This overall pattern is clearly reported in the westernmost area, allowing later distinct upward migrations eastwards, and even the persistence of the easternmost cedar populations, located at higher altitudes, showing the essential role of altitude as a determining factor of resilience for these forests, as well as the implications for their management.

A simplified key for Cyperaceae pollen: preliminary results from a sedge peatland in a Holocene paleochannel of Tagliamento River (NE Italy)

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Background. The current global change is marked by an unprecedented loss of biodiversity, which is a major threat to ecosystems and human life. Investigating plant biodiversity changes over long time periods (centennial-millennial scale) is necessary to understand present ecosystems and develop sustainable conservation strategies. Palynology is an invaluable tool in studying the past plant biodiversity and provides insight on biodiversity shifts over time, thereby acting as a bridge between present and past. This work focuses on the palynology of wetlands, which are renowned biodiversity hotspots. We investigated a peatland formed in a residual paleochannel of the Tagliamento River in Friuli Venezia Giulia (NE Italy), a region that hosts the priority habitat type “Calcareous fens with *Cladium mariscus* and species of the *Caricion davallianae*”. Studying the long-term evolution of Cyperaceae peatlands could enhance our understanding of these vulnerable habitats, possibly highlighting their vegetation dynamics and suggesting ways to manage and protect them. The aforementioned species, together with almost all of the other species forming the *Caricion davallianae* alliance, belong to the Cyperaceae family, whose pollen grains are particularly hard to determine due to their high inter-genus morphological similarity and the lack of monographies, keys, and adequate coverage in pollen atlases. This work is a first attempt at discerning the pollen of Cyperaceae and elaborating a key to ease determination of their pollen grains, with particular regard to the relevant species.

Methods. Pollen samples from a 6.5 m-long sediment core covering the last 5000 years from the paleochannel were analysed. Pollen grains belonging to the Cyperaceae family were morphologically described and determined using morphological criteria established by Beug (2004).

Results. Out of 123 pollen taxa determined throughout the series, Cyperaceae pollen is ubiquitous and the most abundant in samples, marking the site as an important area concerning this family. A simplified key for pollen analysis of the Cyperaceae family was developed. The considered morphological parameters are dimensions and shape of the grains, thickness of the exine and sculpture elements; apertures were not included, as they are often hardly distinguishable. Using these criteria, pollen of some genera or species, such as *Cladium mariscus*, *Cyperus* spp., *Rhynchospora* spp. and some in the *Scirpus* s.l. group (*sensu* Beug, 2004), could be reliably determined.

Conclusions. Pollen analyses returned valuable information on the biodiversity and vegetation dynamics of Cyperaceae peatlands over long time periods. The proposed key allows for a reliable determination of some Cyperaceae pollen grains, but the lack of monographies, other keys and comprehensive picture references in atlases hinders determination of other Cyperaceae grains. Further morphological research and studies are needed to allow more specific and consistent determination, thus providing a better understanding of dynamics in habitat involving this family, and in turn ease their management and protection.

References. Beug H. J. (2004). *Leitfaden der Pollenbestimmung für Mitteleuropa und angrenzende Gebiete*, Verlag Dr. Friedrich Pfeil, München, Germany. ISBN: 3-89937-043-0.

Vegetation and climate change during MIS 35-19 (~1.2 - 0.75 Ma) in Western Mediterranean (Alboran Sea): new insights to understand the late hominin occupation in Western Europe?

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Background. The Early-Middle Pleistocene Transition (EMPT, 1.4 - 0.4 Ma) exhibits the transition from obliquity-driven 41ka to eccentricity-driven 100ka climate cycles. This transition coincides with the first evidences of hominin occupation in Western Europe, dated between 1.4 and 1.2 Ma for the site of the Sima del Elefante, Fuente Nueva 3 (Spain) and Pirro Nord (Italy). Nevertheless, hominin settlements occur later than those observed in the Caucasus and Asia. The reconstruction of vegetation and climate for this period is therefore crucial for the understanding of these late occupations.

Methods. The marine sequence from Leg 161 ODP Site 976, located south of the Iberian Peninsula in the Alboran Sea, provides a regional and continuous record of vegetation over this major climatic change. This record is one of the few continuous sequences available for this period in the Mediterranean, along with continental records of Tenaghi Philippon (Greece) and Lake Ohrid (Balkans).

Results. Here we provide new palynological analyses to document MIS 35-31 (1.141 – 1.062 Ma) and MIS 22-21 (0.9 - 0.814 Ma), which complete previous studies on MIS 20-19 (0.814 – 0.761 Ma) and MIS 30-23 (1.141-0.9 Ma). Our new pollen diagram highlights vegetation changes associated with eight glacial and nine interglacial periods with a resolution never reached before. Specifically, we focus on transitional phases from glacial to interglacial conditions, showing fast and characteristic vegetation dynamics. Then, these data are compared with key sequences from the Eastern Mediterranean.

Conclusions. This work will provide new environmental and climatic references for the human occupations in the Western Mediterranean.

Vegetation and climate changes during Heinrich Stadial 4 (~39.5 ka BP) in western Mediterranean: new results from high-resolution palynological analyses and quantitative climate reconstructions

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Background. During the last glacial period (MIS 4-2), the Northern hemisphere experienced submillennial climate oscillations as evidenced for the first time through the study of Atlantic sedimentary cores and the Greenland ice record. Heinrich Stadials were described as phases of extreme and abrupt shift toward cold and dry conditions on the continent, linked with an event of major iceberg discharge in the North Atlantic. Previous palynological studies of marine cores from the Iberian margins already evidenced vegetation changes associated with the submillennial climate variability and Heinrich events. In the past years, the transition from the Middle to the Upper Palaeolithic in Europe has often been debated in the light of these fast climate changes characteristic of the last glacial.

Methods. Leg 161 ODP 976 core is located in the Alboran Sea, ca. 50 km south of Malaga, and has continuously recorded climate and vegetation changes across the last glacial period. We carried out very high-resolution palynological analyses and pollen-based paleoclimatic reconstructions on ODP 976 core, including 75 samples between 41-35 ka BP, the chronological window associated to Heinrich Stadial 4 and Dansgaard-Oeschger interstadial 8. An updated age model was built using radiocarbon ages and calibration with the Greenland isotopic chronology. Pollen counting and identification followed the traditional protocol, and we applied multiple methods of pollen-based climate reconstructions: Modern Analogue Technique (MAT), Weighted Averaging Partial Least Squares regression (WA-PLS), and recent machine learning methods as Random Forest (RF) and Boosted Regression Trees (BRT).

Results. The results of palynological analyses evidence the fast spread at centennial-scale of semi-arid vegetation with the main taxa *Artemisia*, *Amaranthaceae* and *Ephedra* reaching more than 60% of the total pollen sum during the HS4. The high-resolution approach allows us to detect a three-phased pattern during the HE4 as already evidenced in other Greenland and Mediterranean records. Then, the recovery of temperate and Mediterranean vegetation during the DO8 is progressive. All the four methods of climate reconstructions show a climate deterioration and a trend toward enhanced aridity during HE4, but with different amplitudes depending on the method employed. Comparison of these results with other palynological and paleoclimatic records from the western Mediterranean (MD95-2042, MD95-2043, Padul) brings light on the spatial expression of the arid event from both sides of the Gibraltar Strait, evidencing a westward trend in aridification in the Mediterranean region.

Conclusions. The Alboran Sea is confirmed to be a critical area where the Atlantic and Mediterranean influences meet and determine the expression of fast climate oscillations. The results of this study are of particular relevance in the debate on the impact of fast climate variability on the dynamics of Human populations during MIS3.

Vegetation response in NW Mediterranean borderlands to the millennial-scale climate variability during the Last Glacial period

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Background. Deep-sea pollen records from the Western European margin indicate that regional vegetation oscillated between open forest and steppe during the Last Glacial period (*ca.* 115 – 11.7 kiloyears [kyrs]) in response to the millennial scale climate variability, specifically the Dansgaard-Oeschger, (D-O) cycles and Heinrich events (HE). The magnitude of the forest expansions during D-O warming events was modulated by orbital parameters. However, the vegetation response in the northwestern Mediterranean region during this period remains poorly understood due to the fragmentary nature of the available sequences.

Methods. In this study, we present a new well-chronologically constrained high-resolution marine pollen record from the Gulf of Lion (MD99-2343, 40°29'N, 4°01'E), documenting the NW Mediterranean borderlands' vegetation response during Marine Isotope Stages (MIS) 4 to 2 (~73 - 14kyrs).

Results. Initial findings highlight that the extent of the temperate forest expansions in NW Mediterranean borderlands, *i.e.*, the forest colonizing the Rhône and Ebro valleys, in response to D-Os warming events is modulated by precession; as previously indicated by Western European margin pollen records located in the Mediterranean region below 40°N. In Western Europe, the HEs are all characterized by steppe expansions, but the new pollen analysis documents another scenario with an increase in forest cover during HE 6 and 2.

Conclusions. We hypothesize that local atmospheric and marine processes in the Gulf of Lion allowed the development of the temperate forest in the NW Mediterranean borderlands during HE 6 and 2, while the expansion of open and steppic environments occurred in other Western European regions.

Fire variability in the southeastern France over the past 8200 years.

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Background. The French Mediterranean region faces increased fire risks due to anticipated climate change impacts. However, current fire projection models overlook the intricate interactions among climate, vegetation, and fire dynamics. Paleofire records from marine sediments offer insights into past biomass burning trends and their relationship with climate change. This study presents the first marine paleofire record from southeastern France during the Northgrippian and the Meghalayan stages.

Methods. Microcharcoal and its morphometry was analysed in marine sediments from the Gulf of Lion, to reconstruct biomass burning, fire frequency, fire episodes and fire size.

Results. Twenty fire episodes were identified, with five during the Northgrippian and ten in the Meghalayan.

Conclusions. Fire regime changes are discussed with vegetation, climate, and human presence, suggesting climate and vegetation shifts as key fire regime drivers.

The marine core MD02-2503. 4000 years of landscape shaping in Santa Barbara Basin, California

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Background. The landscape of Southern California (SoCal) has been shaped by climate and anthropogenic dynamics for thousands of years. The ENSO precipitation patterns and several climatic episodes, such as the Little Ice Age have played a major role in the landscape transformation. Human mobility, cultural interactions and colonization processes, as well as the different management strategies and land uses implemented during the Late Holocene, also have had a remarkable impact on the vegetation composition, structure and distribution. This is particularly evident during the last ~250 years, following the introduction of agropastoral practices, fire suppression policies and urban development in coastal areas. However, the spatial extent of human-induced Late Holocene landscape change in SoCal remains poorly characterized, as does the impact of Holocene climate changes at high temporal resolution.

Methods. High temporal resolution pollen, non-pollen palynomorph, and microcharcoal analyses of over 115 samples were conducted in the marine core MD02-2503 from the Santa Barbara Basin, California, to reconstruct regional vegetation change and fire dynamics. The regional data obtained in this study were compared with local palaeoecological reconstructions obtained from small wetlands on the continental coast and the Channel Islands, as well as with archaeo-historical datasets.

Results. The results obtained have highlighted the resilience of the vegetation of the Santa Barbara Basin and its response to the different climatic changes during the Late Holocene. The 4.2 ka BP event and the Medieval Climate Anomaly resulted in changes in the composition and structure of the landscape, and it was possible to depict different vegetation responses to the climatic events between the coast and the mountain. At the same time, this regional reconstruction allowed calibration of the spatial extent of anthropogenic impacts and the management strategies implemented over time. Around the Santa Barbara Basin, indigenous hunter-gatherer communities actively used fire as a tool to maintain a mosaic Mediterranean landscape rich in plant resources and attractive for hunting. On the other hand, the colonial processes were characterized by the alteration of fire patterns and the introduction of new species and agropastoral practices that transformed the landscape.

Conclusions. In conclusion, this study provides a regional framework for measuring the spatial extent of long-term climatic and anthropogenic impacts on landscape change in the Santa Barbara coastal region, and offers new insights for the future management and conservation of this threatened Mediterranean biodiversity hotspot in Southern California. Understanding the mechanisms of change and how species have adapted in the past may be essential for addressing the future scenarios under the accelerated current climate change.

Vegetation and human dynamics revealed the history of the last 2 millennia in Southern Macedonia. The case study of Lake Volvi (Greece)

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Background: Lake Volvi, the second largest natural lake in Greece, occupies a notable position in Central Macedonia, approximately 35 km east of Thessaloniki, in northern Greece. The area is characterized as a significant biodiversity hotspot, it is recognized for its significance as a wetland habitat, protected under the Ramsar Convention and designated as Special Areas of Conservation (Gantidis et al., 2007). The natural ecosystems have been shaped by a blend of factors, including climate, tectonic movements, and erosive forces. Moreover, since the Neolithic the Volvi area has been influenced by human activities (Kotsos and Urem-Kotsou, 2016). During the Roman and Byzantine times, it held strategic significance as it was positioned within a communication corridor, the Via Egnatia, linking the eastern and western Balkans. This study aims to reconstruct a high-resolution record of the last 2000 years combining geological and palynological analyses with historical sources, aiming to implement the concept of consilience to acquire a complete understanding of the region's environmental dynamics.

Methods: The study integrates palaeoecological, geochronological, geochemical and historical approaches to unravel the intricate environmental changes of the Lake Volvi region. Through high-resolution pollen analysis and geochemical data (XRF, TC, TS, TN) the study traces the evolution of past environmental changes. While archaeological data from the 1st millennium CE provides insights into the area's early history, more detailed historical records emerge from the 13th century CE onward, primarily through detailed Byzantine and Ottoman documents. The consilience concept is employed, interpreting palaeoecological information alongside available archaeological and historical sources.

Results: Pollen analysis with a mean temporal resolution of 49 years, provides detailed insight into environmental changes since the Roman occupation of the area. Pollen data records a vegetation dominated by mixed deciduous oak and mesothermic forests, wetland habitat as well as cereal cultivation, grazing, and arboriculture. The expansion of crop and cereals fields with a diversification in the agricultural crops characterized also the first stage of the Byzantine empire. Medieval times were afflicted by political instability that resulted in an abrupt decline in cereal and anthropogenic taxa but at the same time vegetation was stressed by climatic factors underlined by geochemical and pollen data. The combined analysis of historical and palaeoecological data highlights the 16th century as a period marked by significant population pressure on the environment of the Volvi region. Expansion of the anthropogenic pollen indicators related to pastoralism reveal the importance of animal

husbandry practices in the economy that overall may have contributed to the reduction of the evergreen oaks.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of integrating palaeoecological and historical data for reconstructing past environments and understanding human-environment interactions. The combination of pollen data with historical events reveals paradoxes such as the contrasting impact of plague outbreaks in the 6th and 14th centuries CE and emphasizes the complexity of human-environment interactions in the Volvi region. Moreover, the combined approach shows the importance of integrating multiple data sources for a comprehensive understanding of the environmental history.

References. Gantidis, N., Pervolarakis, M., Fytianos, K. (2007). Assessment of the Quality Characteristics of Two Lakes (Koronia and Volvi) of Northern Greece. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 125: 175–181.

Kotsos, S., Urem-Kotsou, D. (2016). *Langadas Basin and the Settlement of Mikri Volvi*. In *Southeast Europe and Anatolia in Prehistory: Essays in Honour of Vassil Nikolov on his 65th Anniversary*, edited by Bacvarov K., Gleser R., Universitätsforschungen zur Prähistorischen Archäologie. Rudolf Habelt, Bonn.

Pollen Analysis Reveals Anatolian Environmental Change from antiquity to Middle Age: Insights from Lake Yeniçağa (Türkiye)

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Background. A palynological sequence has been obtained from a shallow water body surrounded by marshy areas in Northern Anatolia (Türkiye), Lake Yeniçağa. The core records the palaeoenvironmental history for a region rich of historical events from ca. 400 BCE to 800 CE. Although some parts of Türkiye have been investigated in detail from the point of view of paleo-science, for the Yeniçağa area, strictly connected with the ancient city of Constantinople (the modern Istanbul), this is one of only a few sites reporting the history of the recent past.

Methods. Pollen analysis has been carried out on 38 sediment samples taken from 200 cm long core. The pollen has been chemically extracted from sediment using HCl, HF and NaOH. The identification has been provided under transmitted microscope and with the support of atlases and reference collection. Pollen, NPPS and charcoal have been counted. The age-depth model is based on 9 AMS radiocarbon dates performed on bulk sediment and pollen.

Results. The main arboreal vegetation is represented by conifer forest with cold resistant deciduous and mountain elements. The presence of Mediterranean taxa evidences the complexity and the fragmentary nature of the vegetation of the Northern Anatolia. Human presence is well attested for the entire sequence. Among trees, *Castanea*, *Corylus*, *Sorbus* gr. *Juglans*, *Olea* and *Vitis* are linked with the land use as well as herbs, mainly represented by Cereals, pastoral and ruderal plants. The continuous human occupation shows an important break at the end of the 5th cent. CE followed by another important change in the land use at ca. mid 8th cent. CE

Conclusions. The palaeoenvironmental reconstruction shows a complex and rich environment and the strong imprint of economic and cultural activities on the landscape. For this reason, the pollen data is one of the essential elements necessary for the deep understanding of the history of this record. The study of archaeological and historical sources will be integrated to the vegetation data for a detailed reconstruction of the history of the Northern Anatolia during a key historical transition period between antiquity and early Mediaeval times.

Holocene *Pinus* pollen evidence in Ría de Vigo (NW Iberia): can be ancient pinewoods discriminated from modern repopulations?

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Background. A sediment core in Ría de Vigo (NW Iberia) includes unexpected *Pinus* pollen peaks during the early and mid-Holocene. Radiocarbon dates enable building a coherent regional model able to explain the reworking of coastal and upland sediments during the marine transgression and their redeposition in the deepest part of the basin.

Methods. We studied sixty-six fossil subsamples for concentration (grain/cm³) and accumulation rate estimates and compared them with modern pollen evidence taken in different sedimentary contexts of the ria. Besides, we performed a biometric study of the *Pinus* pollen evidence (between 37 and 75 specimens taken in more than three samples from each Local Pollen Assemblage Zone, LPAZ) to discriminate the modern repopulations (*Pinus pinaster* Aiton) from the previous *Pinus* pollen evidence and pairwise tests applied to identify significant size differences between LPAZs.

Results and Discussion. The total *Pinus* pollen grain concentrations and average total sizes notably oscillate across the record, with the lowest means (<62 µm) found in LPAZ 1 and LPAZ-8 and the highest (>68.5 µm) in LPAZ-9, LPAZ-7, and LPAZ-4. Normality tests indicate that pine pollen's total grain sizes differ from normal distribution in LPAZ-1, LPAZ-2, LPAZ-5, LPAZ-7, and LPAZ-8. Besides, the hierarchical cluster analysis agrees in separate LPAZ-9, LPAZ-7, and LPAZ-4 from the others, dividing the last into two clades: LPAZ-1, LPAZ-3, LPAZ-6, and LPAZ-8 in the first cluster; and LPAZ-2 and LPAZ-5 in the second. *Pinus* concentrations in LPAZ-1 are much higher than equivalent pollen concentrations in sediment samples from a modern lagoon (10 samples) and in modern seabed sediment (26 samples); but they fit in the range of the samples (20 samples) from nearby upland lacustrine systems. It suggests that pinewoods formed part of the upland ecosystems in the ria at the beginning of the Holocene. Subsequently, concentrations of *Pinus* notably decline, and only in the LPAZ-9 (modern repopulations) and the LPAZ-4 (Thermal Optimum) increase up to values comparable to those in the modern seabed sediment. The total grain sizes in LPAZ-1 to LPAZ-3 are significantly different (smaller) than those corresponding to the modern repopulations with *Pinus pinaster* Aiton (LPAZ-9). However, the average size of the *Pinus* pollen in the LPAZ-8 is remarkably like that of the LPAZ-1 to LPAZ-3, and significantly different to the most modern *Pinus* pollen evidence (LPAZ-9). The *Pinus* pollen sizes registered during the Thermal Optimum (LPAZ-4) are also like modern pine pollen sizes (LPAZ-9). The average grain size of *Pinus* pollen also decreases in LPAZ-5 and LPAZ-6, which suggests that certain contributions of reworked ancient *Pinus* to the seabed occurred when upwelling intensifies.

Conclusions. *Pinus* pollen sizes and *Pinus* pollen abundances significantly change across the postglacial sediments of the ria. Further studies will be necessary to confirm if these trends may be related to the warmer/wetter conditions during the Thermal Optimum or if a regional replacement of pine species occurred between the lateglacial and the mid-Holocene.

Environmental changes in the Fleuve Manche paleoriver drainage system directly linked to the North Atlantic sub-millennial climate variability across HS1 from a northern Bay of Biscay pollen record

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Background and methods. Marine microfossils (dinoflagellate cysts and polar planktonic foraminifera *Neogloboquadrina pachyderma*) and geochemical (XRF-Ti/Ca)-based climatic records from a core located off the Fleuve Manche (FM) paleo-mouth (MD13-3438) have revealed that sustained warm summer sea surface temperatures (SSTs) during sub-millennial climate changes within Heinrich Stadial 1 (HS1) (~18–14.7 ka) may have played a key role in the FM regime related to the European Ice Sheet (EIS) melting rate. In this study, we have analyzed the MD13-3438 pollen content over the HS1 at a mean resolution of ~50 years to test whether vegetation-based air temperatures were coupled to SSTs face to this rapid climate variability amplifying their impact on EIS melting.

Results. First, our results highlight two major phases of pollen sources at site MD13-3438, preventing the pollen record to be interpreted as a continuous record of the evolution of vegetation and climate occupying a single watershed across HS1. The first phase, i.e. the HS1-a interval (~18–16.8 ka), is marked by strong occurrences of boreal pollen taxa (especially *Picea-Abies*). Considering their spatial distribution and the coalescence of the British and Scandinavian ice sheets into the North Sea during the Last Glacial Maximum, these taxa probably originated from the North European Plain, i.e., eastern FM tributaries (east of the Rhine River), where cool-humid conditions generally prevailed. Then, the second phase, i.e. the HS1-b interval (~16.8–14.7 ka BP), is characterized by a deceleration of the EIS retreat and the drop of boreal pollen values at site MD13-3438 further signing a less influence of the upstream FM drainage system and thus a better characterization of pollen sources related with western FM tributaries (west of the Rhine River).

Conclusions. Superimposed to the two HS1 main phases, pollen fluctuations are concomitant with sub-millennial variability in the EIS deglaciation intensity. During the early HS1 (HS1-a), two short-term increases in the ratio between deciduous trees (*Quercus-Corylus-Alnus*) vs. herbaceous plants (*Plantago-Amaranthaceae-Artemisia*) are interpreted as atmospheric warming events. These events were coeval with phases of increasing FM meltwater runoff and SST seasonality (i.e., dinocyst-based summer SST amplification) that were associated with lower contribution of the upstream FM catchment and regional sea-level positive oscillations, and possibly atmospheric warming. The HS1-b is composed of three main phases that appear more influenced by the downstream FM drainage system. HS1-b1 (16.8–16.3 ka BP) corresponds to the driest and coldest conditions, HS1-b2 (16.3–15.6 ka BP) to a phase of FM valley reworking coeval with large arrivals of iceberg from the Hudson strait in the Bay of Biscay and thus likely to a major sea-level positive oscillation, and HS1-b3 (15.6–14.7 ka BP) to persistent arid conditions preceding the subsequent humid conditions recorded from 14.7 ka BP at the start of the Bölling-Alleröd.

Holocene plant dynamics in Italian coastal wetlands: preliminary palynological analysis from Burano Lake (central Italy)

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Background. Burano Lake is nestled within a Natural Reserve and WWF Oasis in Tuscany (central Italy) and hosts high biodiversity. The area is included in the EU Natura 2000 Network and recognized as an International Value Wetland (Ramsar Conventions). The brackish lake testifies the ancient lagoons that characterized the Tuscan Maremma before the reclamations of the 20th century. Holocene evolution of coastal environments in central Italy was shaped by sea-level fluctuations, leading to the lagoon and marsh ecosystems formation. During the Bronze Age, important coastal settlements were developed by Etruscan and Latin civilizations that exploited these areas; anthropic activities increased during Roman times and persisted until the decline of the Roman Empire. The aim of our study is to reconstruct the middle-late Holocene plant dynamics in this wetland area, investigating both anthropic and natural factors responsible for main changes in the local plant biodiversity.

Methods. Two sediment cores (1.5 m apart) were taken from the center of the lake, stratigraphically described, and correlated to obtain a composite core of ~500 cm. It was subsampled at ~3 cm intervals for palynological analysis. Samples were treated with a method including nylon sieving and heavy liquid floatation. Pollen percentage diagrams were elaborated using Tilia software.

Results. The sequence covers a chronology spanning approximately the last 6000 years. All samples show excellent pollen preservation and high floristic richness (>100 pollen taxa), reflecting the high biodiversity of the area over time. The arboreal cover, characterized by a predominance of mixed oakwood and Mediterranean trees and shrubs, reaches maximum percentages in the oldest levels and assumes a general declining trend with variations along the sequence. Phases of arboreal cover reduction (mainly mixed oakwood) and herbaceous plants expansion (where Poaceae wild grass group are predominant) correspond to an increase in Anthropogenic Pollen Indicators (API) and cereals. The mixed oakwood expansion coincides with an increase in pollen percentages of hygrophilous trees and herbs, hydrophytes, signaling wet environments, and the anthropic signal reduction. In the most recent levels high pollen percentages of cultivated trees (OJC) and maximum reduction of mixed oak forest taxa are detected marked a significant land use change.

Conclusions. This study implements knowledge on mid-late Holocene plant biodiversity and landscape dynamics in an Italian coastal wetland and investigates the impact of human activities on these peculiar environments. Assessing the human-nature relationship can contribute to the future management, restoration and protection of such vulnerable areas.

Modern pollen-vegetation assemblages in the Cantabrian range, northern Iberian Peninsula: a vegetation cover-based approach and comparison with fossil pollen records

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Background. The analysis of pollen records has become one of the main techniques for studying the evolution of vegetation landscapes through time. However, interpreting these percentages can sometimes be complex because the amount of pollen that accumulates in sedimentary deposits, reflected in the pollen diagrams, depends on various factors. In order to better interpret the pollen record of the Cantabrian Range, a calibration of the modern pollen rain of certain vegetation types was carried out. Additionally, we investigated whether there were similar modern vegetation types to past ones interpreted from the pollen record of La Molina peatland, Cantabria.

Methods. 76 surface pollen samples (mosses) were collected on the Cantabrian Range, ranging from 3 to 1154 m a. s. l. Pollen was analysed following standard chemical procedures. Additionally, vegetation data were obtained from a vegetation map (Mapa forestal de España, 1:25,000) to estimate vegetation cover for comparison with pollen percentages from modern surface samples. Vegetation information within areas of 100 meters, 1 kilometer, and 5 kilometers radius around each sample was extracted. Principal component analysis was performed to compare the distribution of modern pollen records and fossil pollen records from the pollen record of La Molina peatland, Cantabria (n = 395; Sánchez-Morales et al., 2022).

Results. Results revealed that the laurel-evergreen oak community was predominantly marked by evergreen *Quercus* pollen (59-77%), while pollen from *Laurus nobilis* was underrepresented. The representation of *Fagus sylvatica* pollen varied depending on the presence of local species. In particular, two samples exhibited over 95% *Fagus* cover within a 100 m radius, yet their pollen content remained below 3%. Pine demonstrated high dispersal capability, with pollen levels exceeding 20% even in samples with little or no pine cover within 1 and 5 km. Poaceae had limited representation, maxing out at 60% even in samples lacking tree cover within a 5 km radius. Mixed deciduous woodlands were dominated by deciduous *Quercus* and *Corylus*, and their resemblance to formations during the mid-Holocene (from c. 9300 to 1900 cal yr BP) in the northern Iberian Peninsula was discussed. Although a principal component analysis linked modern plant formations to La Molina's most recent interval, no clear parallels emerged between present-day and ancient landscapes.

Conclusions: This investigation fills an information gap by characterising the modern pollen rain of various Cantabrian plant formations that have been insufficiently studied. The study of the pollen record of La Molina has not revealed any vegetation type analogous to present day ones in Cantabria, except in the most recent period (from c. 1900 cal yr BP to the present). However, a discernible relationship has been found between the pollen signal of the modern mixed deciduous woods and the vegetation of the mid-Holocene interval.

Reference: Sanchez-Morales, M., Pelachs, A., Garcia-Codron, J. C., Carracedo, V., Perez-Obiol, R. (2022). Landscape dynamics and fire regime since 17,550 cal yr BP in the Cantabrian region (La Molina peat bog, Puente Viesgo, Spain). *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 278: 107373.

Study of the recent Quaternary of the Southwest Coast Benin, from archaeological and palynological data

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Background. Climate reconstruction models show that there was an alternation between fairly long cooling phases (Glacials) and shorter warming phases (Interglacials), during the Quaternary. In West Africa, the phytogeographical interruption called the Dahomey-Gap is observed between Nigeria and Ghana as an area of savanna that extends to the Atlantic coast, separating the rainforest zones to the west and east in this region. The break in dense forest observed in southern Benin raises many questions about the relationship between vegetation and human activities over the late Holocene timescale. The origin of this drier savanna vegetation zone is debated both during the Quaternary and at present day.

Methods. The historical investigations were carried out through an oral inquiry and documentary research. Concerning the collection of archaeobotanical data, sediments were taken during the excavations and the flotation method was implemented for the identification of plant remains. Concerning the palynological studies, cores were taken at the edge of the ponds close to archaeological sites for identifications of pollen and spores. In addition, the floristic diversity of plant formations around the sites was evaluated and correlated with palynological data for a better interpretation of archaeological data.

Results. The study site is made up of a series of anthropogenic mounds on which there are high concentrations of ceramic material. Ceramics constitute the dominant furniture observed on the site. However, there are numerous other remains composed of both local and imported pipes and ash concretions. The vegetation of the study area is made up of a wide diversity of plant formations, ranging from mangroves, forest regrowth, fields and fallow lands. The diversity of plants reflects an average specific richness of the study sites. This specific potential varies in space and time. A total of 63 species were identified divided into 60 genera and 34 families. The pollen analysis of the four cores indicated an open vegetation shown on the pollen diagram.

Conclusions. The research work carried out in the part of South Benin and an archaeological survey was carried out in Djèkpomè where various archaeological remains which being dated. Palynological data were also collected and analyzed showing interesting results on the pollen diagram. Radiocarbon dating is in progress using charcoal collected during archaeological surveys.

References. Julier, A. C., Manzano, S., Razanatsoa, E., Razafimanantsoa, A. H., Githumbi, E., Hawthorne, D., Oden, G., Schüler, L., Tossou, M., Bunting, J. (2021). Modern pollen studies from tropical Africa and their use in palaeoecology. In J. Runge, W. D. Gosling, A. Lézine, & L. Scott (Eds.), *Quaternary Vegetation Dynamics – The African Pollen Database* (317-348). London: CRC Press.

Haour, A., Nixon, S., N'dah, D., Magnavita, D., Smith, A. (2016) The settlement mound of Birnin Lafiya: new evidence from the eastern arc of the Niger River. In *Antiquity*, 90 351, Antiquity publications Ltd., pp 695-710 doi: 10.15184/aqy.2016.7

Adiss Kamal Issifou Fatiou, Moussa Konaté, Luc Cossi Adissin Glodji, Soulémana Yessoufou, Monique Tossou, Matthias Heckmann, Hamidou Saley Garba. 2019. Preliminary Sporo-Pollenic Content Survey and Characterization of the Continental Terminal Formation Ironstones, Kandi Basin (North-East Benin). *European Scientific Journal*, 15:24

Vegetation dynamics in the Sila Mountains (southern Italy) during the last millennium

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Background. Mountain areas of southern Italy are a complex mosaic of natural and cultural landscapes, resulting from the combination of environmental heterogeneity and human exploitation. An in-depth understanding of their past vegetation along with their land-use history is essential for developing conservation strategies to face the modern climate change and biodiversity loss. In particular, the Sila plateau on the southernmost Apennine Mountains represents a unique Mediterranean mountain landscape, housing an almost pure forest of *Pinus nigra* J.F. Arnold subsp. *laricio* Palib. ex Maire (Corsican pine), which is native to this area. Our aim is to describe the last millennium of vegetation history of a vast and pure pine forest, evaluating its composition and structure in relation to economic activities and climatic oscillations.

Methods. We applied pollen and Non-Pollen Palynomorphs (NPPs) analyses to a 1,5 m core taken from a peat bog in the Sila National Park (39° 23' 05.7" N 16° 37' 52.5" E, 1290 m a.s.l.). A total of 20 organic-rich sediment samples were treated with a standard protocol for pollen extraction. Plant macro-remains were also recovered for AMS C14 analysis.

Results. A preliminary dating of the core reveals that the sequence covers the last 1000 ka. The first pollen data confirms a long-term persistence of the pinewood in the study area, with few other forest components like oaks, hornbeams and chestnut at lower altitudes. The attestation of *Olea europea* pollen may be related to the convective flows of warm air from coastal areas, where olive is widespread. Herbs from pasturelands revealing the degree of human impact on the landscape (*Poaceae*, *Rumex*, *Plantago* ssp.) are abundant.

Conclusions. The preliminary results need to be examined in relation to socio-economic factors and climatic changes of the last millennium that impacted on the Sila mountain ecosystem. Our results will contribute to shed light into the forest dynamics and the degree of naturalness and disturbance of vegetation in southern Italy, in order to develop a strategic baseline of biodiversity management activities. The work was implemented under the NRRP, Mission 4 Comp. 2 Inv. 1.4—Call for tender No. 3138 16 12 2021, rectified by Decree n.3175 of 18 12 2021 of Italian MUR funded by Next Generation EU. Project code CN_00000033, Concession Decree No. 1034 of 17 06 2022 adopted by MUR, Project title “National Biodiversity Future Center—NBFC”

Land-Sea dynamics in East Asia: Deciphering the impact of high-latitude versus tropical forcing during the last 70 kyrs

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Background. The East Asian Monsoon (EAM) is a complex climate system involving coupled ocean-atmosphere-land interactions that exerts a major impact on the daily-life of billions of inhabitants. Yet, future of monsoon rainfalls remains poorly constrained by climate models despite the growing need of truthful predictions at regional scale. In East Asia, uncertainties are accentuated by the northern distribution of the EAM, which is the unique monsoon system extending to the temperate region. This particular feature reinforces the EAM sensitivity to high latitude climate variability and considerably increases the challenge of identifying its low versus high latitude climatic control. To fill this gap, we present the preliminary results of the project CHUVA, recently funded by the FCT, the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.03976.CEECIND/CP1729/CT0001>).

Methods. The originality of the project relies on an innovative palynological approach of marine sediment from core ES14-GC01 located in the East Sea, combining a jointed-analysis of marine (i.e. dinocysts) and terrestrial (i.e. pollen grains) palynomorphs, which is the rare way to explore through the same analysis the interactions of the ocean-land-atmosphere systems without chronological ambiguities. Our palynological record covers the last 70 kyrs BP interval, including the present interglacial, the Holocene, and the last glacial period.

Results. The maximum expansion of boreal conifer forest with *Picea* and *Tsuga* is recorded from 48 to 14 ka, which together with the steppe, composed by *Artemisia* and Poaceae, reflect the coldest and driest conditions of the studied interval likely resulting in reinforced East Asian Winter Monsoon. A successive vegetation change from the boreal conifer forest to the temperate broadleaf forest, including *Pinus* subgenus *diploxylon*, passing through the temperate conifer forest dominated by *Quercus* subgenus *lepidobalanus*, is recorded during the last deglacial and the Holocene. The highest percentage of the temperate broadleaf forest is reported from 12 to 8 ka revealing the optimum of terrestrial warming and, thus an increased influence of the East Asian Summer Monsoon. In addition to vegetation record, dinocyst assemblage show a strong glacial/interglacial pattern. High percentage of the heterotrophic and temperate taxa, including *Spiniferites mirabilis* and *Spiniferites ramosus*, is recorded during the Holocene pointing out warm, saline and rich-nutrient conditions, probably in response to the Pacific tropical waters inflow. In opposite, *Operculodinium centrocarpum*, a cosmopolitan species extending in the Bering and Okhotsk Seas today, dominates the marine assemblages during the last glacial period revealing harsh but ice-free conditions.

Conclusions. Therefore, palynological record from the East Sea shows changes in terrestrial and oceanic conditions, which are closely linked to insolation and ice-sheet dynamic.

**PALEOPALYNOLOGY:
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS**

Millennial-Scale Upward Migration Patterns of Mediterranean Heat-sensitive Conifers: Implications on their Conservation

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Background. Biogeographical processes associated to climate shifts, such as expansion/contraction, connection/fragmentation, speciation/extinction, among others, are particularly relevant in Mediterranean mountains. Against the migration pattern described for thermophilous species, heat-sensitive Mediterranean ones show their widest expansion during cold periods as they occupy the lowest-altitude mountain areas, achieving a greater connectivity among their populations. By contrast, during warm periods, as the current Holocene, these species migrate in altitude to find their suitable habitat. As a result of these displacements, their distribution contracts, becomes fragmented and the populations get isolated, triggering their eventual extinction. Our study is included in the project TED2021-132631B-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI /10.13039/ 501100011033 and Next Generation EU/PTR.

Methods. We focus on Mediterranean mountain conifers such as *Cedrus atlantica* (Atlas cedar), which extends on the Rif, Middle and High Atlas in Morocco. We will turn to previously generated paleoenvironmental information from Moroccan mountains, both ours (10 sedimentary records) and 13 external ones (e.g. Neotoma database and literature already compiled by our research team).

Results. Our analyses from the 23 fossil pollen records show an upward migration between 16 ka (Rif Mountains) and 30 ka (Atlas Mountains) to present (0 ka). The results indicate that during Last Glacial cedar forests would have covered low-medium mountains in the Middle Atlas. The first cedar pollen records are detected in Early Holocene in medium-high mountain areas, maybe indicating that the leading edge of cedar forests were colonizing higher and suitable areas for their survival. Increasing temperatures and progressive drought during the Middle Holocene would have forced cedar forests to migrate upward, in search of greater available summer moisture at higher elevations. Cedar populations reached their maximum expansion in the beginning of the Late Holocene in mountain areas between 1600 and 2200 m above sea level. In addition, along the altitudinal gradient of the Rif Mountains, our paleoecological observations have been able to attest several local extinction events that have occurred in locations currently below the lower limit. Climate has been the primary driver of the shifts undergone by cedar forests. Later, the strengthening of human-induced disturbances has led cedar populations to local extinction.

Conclusions. A key way to conserve Mediterranean heat-sensitive coniferous will be the identification of suitable mountain refugia for them and the establishment of protection measures for these areas. Consequently, these refugia may represent the only alternative against extinction for these species under global warming.

Understanding the changing pollen accumulation rates in different environments of sedimentation from Ría de Vigo (NW Iberia)

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Background. The study of modern pollen sediment samples can decisively contribute to improve the interpretation of fossil evidence. Both marine and continental limnetic deposits are important pollen reservoirs, but their pollen records can vary due to the intrinsic characteristics of the different environment of sedimentation considered. *Lagoa dos Nenos* is a barrier-lagoon complex in the Cíes Islands, NW Iberia. It consists of a natural 1 km-long sand barrier that confines a shallow saline lagoon. Its western margin is permanently connected to the ocean and allows the water exchange during the tidal cycle. Another ephemeral connection exists with the Ría de Vigo in its eastern side, which is only opened in winter when storm waves coincide with spring tides causing the opening of an ephemeral inlet. Besides, there is a repopulation with pine trees on the southern margin of the lagoon. We analysed the pollen sedimentation in different zones of the lagoon and compared them with the modern sedimentation in the Ría de Vigo seabed and in nearby upland ponds.

Methods. Concentrations and pollen percentages were studied in 10 surface sediment samples from *Lagoa dos Nenos*, in other 26 samples from the modern seabed sediment of the Ría de Vigo, and another 25 samples from three continental upland ponds.

Results. Pollen sedimentation rates vary considerably across the main axis of the Ría, depending on its position and environments of sedimentation. Nevertheless, the average concentration (grains/cm³) of *Pinus* pollen in the lagoon samples is significantly lower than their equivalent concentrations in modern seabed samples and several orders of magnitude smaller than those found in upland ponds. The *Erica* pollen concentrations in the lagoon are also significantly lower than in the other locations studied, although currently this genus does not live on the islands.

Conclusions. The high pollen concentrations in the Ría sediment may be driven by the fluvial transport of pollen from the whole basin, as well as specific sedimentation processes across the Ría. The tides action promoting the outflow of saccate pollen grains with high buoyancy capacities is interpreted as the main factor explaining the notable differences in pollen concentration found in the lagoon sediment as compared to the seabed and the upland ponds samples. This same buoyancy phenomenon probably drags tetrahedral Ericaceae pollen into the lagoon, despite this pollen type do not exist on the Illas Cíes.

The marine transgression in NW Iberia: new pollen evidence from shallow submerged sediments in San Simón Bay (Ría de Vigo)

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Background. The Ría de Vigo (NW Iberia) is a funnel-shaped flooded valley in the Atlantic coast of Galicia, with the sea penetrating 30 km from its mouth to San Simón Bay. This shallow bay may be a key point to understand the last stages of the marine Holocene transgression, but seismic reflectors can only be studied in some marginal areas because the presence of shallow gas in the sediment. Thus, detailed interpretations require the comparison of multiple sediment cores. Core B1 (240 cm), at -3.5 m in the southernmost margin of San Simón Bay, may be directly correlated to nearby sites in Muñoz Sobrino et al. (2014).

Methods. The base of the core (205-240 cm depth, seismic sub-unit U_{7,2}) consists of coarse to very coarse grain bioclastic sand, but above 200 cm (sub-unit U_{7,3}) sediment alternates fine and medium silt beds. Five radiocarbon dates (shells and extracted pollen) enabled to establish a chronological framework covering the last 6000 years. 62 sediment samples, including percentages and concentrations (grains/cm³) of pollen, dinoflagellate cysts and non-pollen palynomorphs contents were analysed.

Results. Total pollen concentrations notably increase in muddy sediment above 196 cm depth (ca. 2800 cal a BP), while a significant increase in dinoflagellate cysts only occurred at ca. 600 years later. This change coincides with the total tree pollen decreasing by almost 20%. Subsequently, the Dinoflagellate cysts/Pollen ratio (D/P) persists high, except for four short stages: 1) at 130 cm depth (ca. 1600 cal a BP); 2) at 66 cm (ca. 700 cal a BP); 3) at 50 cm depth (ca 400 cal a BP); and 4) in the upper 20 cm (the last 90 years).

Conclusions. Seismic records and pollen stratigraphy reveal a hiatus at ca. 140 cm that can be dated back to 2000 – 1600 cal a BP. It suggests that an erosive event occurred in the area before the local development of a marsh/alder swamp (Muñoz Sobrino et al., 2014). New pollen analyses reveal sudden increases in *Castanea* and *Ulex*-type above 140 cm, which also agrees with evidence found in the subtidal CORE-8 recording the last 1200 cal a BP. The first three episodes of low D/P may be related to stages of upwelling intensification and interpreted as regionally cooler. The fourth may be affected by the modern repopulation (*Pinus*, *Eucalyptus*) of the basin.

Reference. Muñoz Sobrino C. *et al.* (2014). Climate and anthropogenic factors influencing an estuarine ecosystem from NW Iberia: new high resolution multiproxy analyses from San Simón Bay (Ría de Vigo). *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 93: 11-33.

The usefulness of modern sediment samples (Ría de Vigo, NW Iberia) to validate palaeoenvironmental inferences in estuarine sedimentary systems

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Background. Ría de Vigo, the southernmost Galician ria, is a funnel-shaped valley opening in a SW direction towards the Atlantic, with the sea penetrating about 30 km from the mouth of the ria, partially blocked by the Cíes Islands, to the Ensenada de San Simón in its innermost part. Thus, the estuary is a sedimentation trap, and notable differences exist in the grain size and sedimentation rates along its main axis. We compared 26 modern seabed pollen samples recovered along the Ria with the modern vegetation distribution and used our results to test some palaeo-inferences proposed in Muñoz-Sobrino et al. (2022).

Methods. We reanalysed a series of modern sediment samples (García-Moreiras et al., 2023) in search of certain key palynomorphs that had not been previously considered, studying the relationships between their absolute and relative abundances and different environmental variables, including the sediment grain size, the annual/seasonal precipitation, the size of the source areas, the distance to the most probable source areas, the total estimated subbasin flow and the flowering period.

Results. The percentages and concentrations of the total pollen counts and most of the palynomorph types found in the sediment of the ria follow linear growth. However, some notable exceptions exist in which exponential growth is shown, such as *Erica*, *Alnus*, *Quercus robur*-type, *Castanea*, and cf. *Juncus*.

Conclusions. Exponential increases of certain taxa in some types of sedimentary environments may be strongly mediated by their transport by river plumes and marine currents. This includes the carrying of pollen pellets in the form of staminate catkin remains (*Alnus*, *Quercus robur*-type, *Castanea*), the preferential transport of tetragonal tetrads by flows with good buoyancy capacities (*Erica*), but also the dragging of coastal wetlands pollen, many of them preferably deposited when the diameter (clay) and sinking rate of the mineral grains corresponded to those of the pollen grains. Besides, our results support the association of cf. *Juncus*-type with onshore coastal wetlands (high marshes, humid intradune slacks and coastal lagoons) and therefore its increasing abundance in coastal full-marine sediments may be a good indicator of increasing precipitation.

References. García-Moreiras, I., Vila C., S., García-Gil, S., Muñoz-Sobrino, C. (2023). Organic walled dinoflagellate cyst assemblages in surface sediments of the Ría de Vigo (Atlantic margin of NW Iberia) in relation to environmental gradients. *Marine Micropaleontology*. 180.

Muñoz-Sobrino, C., Cartelle, V., Martínez-Carreño, N., Ramil-Rego, P., García-Gil, S. (2022). The timing of postglacial marine transgression in the Ría de Ferrol (NW Iberia): a new multiproxy approach from its sedimentary infill. *Catena*. 209, 105847

Shaping Mediterranean cultural landscapes across the Ocean: the MeSCAL project

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Background. The California coast is a biodiversity hotspot with a long and rich history of prehistoric and colonial migration, contact and settlement. The MeSCAL project, funded by the French National Research Agency, investigates the role that past cultural interactions and human mobility have played in shaping the landscapes of southern California over the last 4000 years. The main objectives are to analyse the spatial distribution of land uses and plants following prehistoric migrations and colonial processes, and to assess their impact on native flora, wetlands and soilscares.

Methods. MeSCAL brings together an international team and combines 1) multi-proxy palaeoenvironmental analyses, i.e. pollen, non-pollen palynomorphs, fire history analysis, diatoms, sedimentology - in continental wetland and marine records providing local and regional information on vegetation and land-use change; 2) calibration of fossil palynological datasets with modern analogues of vegetation and land-use; 3) archaeobotanical analyses providing information on past plant consumption and use; and 4) comparison of palaeoenvironmental results with archaeological and ethnographic datasets. We combine the study of coastal areas in San Diego city and the Santa Barbara-Ventura region with nearby hinterland areas in Kern and Los Angeles counties. This transect of records will allow us to assess differences in landscape change between areas under direct colonial control and those with less colonial influence, which may have served as refuges for indigenous populations and landscapes.

Results. We present the first results obtained of this research including 1) charcoal, palynological and diatom analyses from continental wetlands showing the response of Mediterranean vegetation and wetlands to coupled climate change and human management during the last 4 ky; and 2) archaeopalynological analyses from archaeological cave sites showing the continued use of indigenous plant resources such as *Datura* and *chuchupate* (*Lomatium* ssp.) by Chumash indigenous communities in mountain areas between the 16th and 19th AD, before and after colonial contact.

Conclusions. MeSCAL will contribute to a better understanding of the long-term shaping of Southern California's Mediterranean landscape heritage, identities and cultures, and will provide Californian societies and land management agencies with important historical and cultural information about their landscapes and wetlands that can help promote culturally sensitive and sustainable landscape management tools and mitigate the current degradation and overexploitation of natural resources due to urban development and economic exploitation.

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Dynamics and temporal evolution of toxic harmful algal blooms from coastal Brittany sediments: First results from the Gulf of Morbihan

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Background. Harmful algal blooms occur when toxin-producing microalgae grow excessively in coastal waters. In France, surveys are done by Ifremer since 1987 through two networks, REPHY and REPHYTOX. Temporal series of toxic microalgae populations are necessary to better assess the dynamics of these recurring seasonal phenomena. Unfortunately, only about 40 years of data are available which is not enough for an accurate understanding and prediction of these dynamics. This study aims at increasing the temporal series length by studying sediments deposited over several decades, prior to 1987, with a focus on dinocyst assemblages through time and especially toxic cyst species, in different northern (e.g. Rance estuary, Gouessant estuary) and southern (e.g. Gulf of Morbihan, Penerf river, Bay of Vilaine) Brittany coasts which are currently experiencing toxic blooms.

Methods. Before studying sediment cores (i.e., temporal dynamics), distribution maps of dinocysts will be established in the studied bays and estuaries.

Results. Here, we show the first results acquired at the scale of the Gulf of Morbihan (33 surface samples). The Gulf is a macrotidal estuary subdivided by two bays: an occidental one characterised by coarser grains and a direct connection to the ocean, protected by the swell by a few islands with a North 90/North-West orientation; an oriental one dominated by finer grains, fluvial inputs and a weaker tidal effect (mesotidal).

Conclusions. These results give us a better understanding of cyst content and conservation in modern sediments from the Gulf. In addition, these new insights will be used to study the planned sediment cores over several decades.

Tracing fire regime changes in the western mediterranean region by using microcharcoal in marine sediments

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Background. The Western Mediterranean region is highly sensible to fires, and as warming trends persist, significant changes in the fire regime are anticipated. However, to interpret accurately changes in charcoal over time in relation to fire characteristics, climate conditions, and vegetation, a thorough understanding of the charcoal proxy is essential.

Methods. In this study, we examined the concentration of microcharcoal and its morphometric features, particularly the elongation ratio (length to width ratio), in 277 surface sediment samples collected from the Western Mediterranean region.

Results. The results reveal that increased concentration of microcharcoal is not associated with the high burnt area or number of fire but associated with the expansion of open vegetation and hotter and drier climates. Additionally, squared microcharcoal particles were linked to the burning of shrubs and trees, while elongated particles were associated with fires in open vegetation areas.

Conclusions. This study enables a deeper comprehension of the "microcharcoal" proxy, demonstrating that the distribution of microcharcoal is influenced not only by fire parameters such as the number of fires, burnt area, and fire intensity, but also by climate conditions and the type of vegetation burned.

Geochemical preservation of organic-walled dinoflagellate cysts and other resistant palynomorphs in Holocene marine settings: tracking changes of bio- to geomolecules via ATR micro-FTIR spectroscopy

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Background. Dinoflagellates, eukaryotic protists, are known to produce organic-walled resting cysts (dinocysts) which are very resistant to degradation. Chemical analysis based on attenuated total reflectance (ATR) microscope Fourier transform infrared (micro-FTIR) spectroscopy revealed that dinocyst walls are built from resistant macromolecules called ‘dinosporins’ (Meyvisch et al., 2022). Little is known about the molecular changes occurring when modern dinocysts (i.e. biomolecules) fossilize (i.e. geomolecules) and, similarly, when other resistant palynomorphs like spores and pollen (composed of sporopollenin) and phycoma of green algae (composed of algaenan) are buried. This study aims to investigate the early (i.e. Pleistocene-Holocene) molecular changes occurring in resistant organic compounds during their burial in shallow to deep-marine settings, via infrared spectroscopy.

Methods. This study relies on the spectrochemical (ATR micro-FTIR) comparison of palynomorphs using sediment cores spanning : i) the latest Pleistocene (18 to 14 ka BP) with a core from the northern Bay of Biscay (MD13-3438 : 2,180 m deep), and ii) the Middle and Late Holocene with cores collected at similar latitudes from offshore (MD95-2002 : 2,174 m deep, northern Bay of Biscay) to shallower environments (CBT-CS11, 73 m deep, mid-shelf south of Brittany).

Results. In dinocysts composed of ‘transparent dinosporin’ (*Lingulodinium machaerophorum*, *Operculodinium centrocarpum*, *Impagidinium*, *Spiniferites*), absorptions related to proteins and sugars remain unchanged with increasing age and between different depositional environments, indicating that these moieties within the compound are stable over a Holocene to late Pleistocene timespan. Sporopollenin and algaenan show a similarly stable signal across both MD cores. Nevertheless, in pollen from core MD95-2002, one absorption band related to aromatic compounds which increase with exposure to UV-B light (C=C–C aromatic ring stretch around 1520-1495 cm⁻¹; Jardine et al., 2017) shows a relative increase with age, suggesting higher-than-today UV-B fluxes during the early Holocene.

Conclusions. The findings indicate that common palynomorph compounds like transparent dinosporin, sporopollenin and algaenan remain virtually unchanged during burial over a late Quaternary timespan, suggesting that microbial degradation of these resistant compounds is minimal to non-existent and that diagenesis-related changes only start to occur during geologically longer (likely pre-Quaternary) burial periods. Compositional changes in pollen grains might reflect changes in terrestrial UV-B fluxes, with possibly higher fluxes in the early Holocene than today.

References. Jardine, P. E., Abernethy, F. A. J., Lomax, B. H., Gosling, W. D., Fraser, W. T. (2017). Shedding light on sporopollenin chemistry, with reference to UV reconstructions. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 238: 1–6.

Meyvisch, P., Gurdebeke, P. R., Vrielinck, H., Mertens, K. N., Versteegh, G., Louwye, S. (2022). Attenuated Total Reflection (ATR) Micro-Fourier Transform Infrared (Micro-FT-IR) Spectroscopy to Enhance Repeatability and Reproducibility of Spectra Derived from Single Specimen Organic-Walled Dinoflagellate Cysts. *Applied Spectroscopy*, 76(2): 235–254.

***Cedrus* dynamics from Lateglacial to present in the Middle Atlas (Morocco)**

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Background. Mediterranean Mountain conifers have undergone a gradual decline over the last decades throughout the Mediterranean Basin, one of the most relevant plant biodiversity hotspots in the world. Their survival is threatened both by climate change and human activities. *Cedrus atlantica* (Atlas cedar) is an endangered conifer species, whose populations in the North of Africa are severely threatened by extinction. Pollen records have shown the noteworthy variations undergone by Atlas cedar forests since Lateglacial period in the North of Africa, as well as the drivers and processes involved. The knowledge on the responses of these species to past climate and human-induced disturbances can help ensuring their persistence in this region. This study is included in the project TED2021-132631B-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI /10.13039/ 501100011033 and Next Generation EU/PTR.

Methods. Here, we present a new multi-proxy and high-resolution analysis of a core extracted from N'Harcha mire, located in the Middle Atlas and spanning the last 13000 years. The pollen record reveals both local and regional signals mainly related to vegetation dynamics, whereas sedimentology and geochemistry mostly report local hydrological variations. Traces of human activities like the introduction of crops or livestock have been also discussed. We have made a revision of previous works carried out in this region in order to establish the range dynamics of Atlas cedar forests in the Middle Atlas since Lateglacial to the present. Additionally, we aim to assess their resilience against climate and human-induced disturbances.

Results. The onset of the Holocene would have forced north African cedar populations to migrate, both in elevation and geographically from the regions where they lived, mainly low-mountain areas. *Cedrus* became extinct at low altitudes in the northeastern deposits of Algeria and Tunisia while its regional pollen signal enhanced slightly in the Middle Atlas. Overall, both increasing winter temperatures and progressive drought during the Middle Holocene would have forced cedar forests to continue their steady upward migration, in search of greater available summer moisture at higher elevations, especially since 6000 cal yr BP, setting different vegetation belts from an earlier mixed forest, with the development of cedar over oak forests. The trend towards increasing drought intensified with the onset of Late Holocene, strengthening this remarkable migration to higher elevations, with maxima ca. 4000 cal yr BP. The varying pace of the records analyzed underscores the primary importance of elevation in shaping the range of cedar populations. After this date, a steady decline also began as human activities spread and masked the influence of climatic variations. Nonetheless, cedar forests have shown high resilience to human disturbance until very recent times.

Conclusions. The postglacial dynamics of cedar forests shows their gradual spread in the Middle Atlas Mountains, after migrating upwards from low-altitude areas. After a slight advance in the Middle Holocene, they reached their maximum expansion in the beginning of the Late Holocene. Later, increasing aridity and the strengthening of human impact have led to their steady decline. However, cedar populations have demonstrated high resilience to both climatic, especially water stress, and human-induced disturbances and persist in current interglacial refugia.

Unraveling Flora Dynamics in Dry Ecosystems: A Palynological Approach

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Background: The uncertainty surrounding the expansion or contraction of tropical to subtropical deserts due to global warming remains significant. Regardless of the direction of change, the implications for food security and the livability of vast areas are profound. Paleobotanical records thus serve as fundamental archives for exploring the response of current dry-tolerant ecosystems to past greenhouse conditions and for understanding their historical and geological evolution. However, evaluating the past developments of these arid floras and associated landscapes poses challenges. This difficulty arises from the scarcity of continental sedimentary records containing abundant palynomorphs and the limited availability of well-documented palynological reference materials.

Methods: This work addresses the latter issue by presenting a detailed palynological characterization of over 170 tropical to subtropical dry-tolerant genera, thriving in Mediterranean-like climates along the Western South American Pacific coast. Our aim is to build a morphological guide that will serve as a primary reference for future (paleo)palynological studies. All samples were collected from geolocated Herbarium material and were prepared following the four-step protocol of Riding (2021), which uses an oxidative process with a 50% KOH solution. Botanical names were updated using the R-package *taxize* (Chamberlain and Boettiger, 2017; latest update on May 1st, 2024).

Results: To date, we have described and photographed 202 palynomorph types belonging to 200 spermatophyte species, 175 genera and 70 families. Typically, each genus corresponds to at least one palynomorph. Palynological descriptions include species name, unit, symmetry, polarity, shape and amb, palynomorph size, exine or sporoderm details, and aperture details, concluding with notable key morphological remarks. Multiple duplicates of the palynological slides are being shared and housed at different institutions, ensuring broader accessibility.

Conclusions: Georeferenced and voucher-related palynological reference materials, such as those presented herein, are essential for morphological comparisons, enabling the testing of diverse evolutionary, biogeographic, and ecological hypotheses. Therefore, this work potentially serves as a reference for upcoming palynological studies addressing the evolution of dry-tolerant floras, plant-animal interactions, landscape changes, as well as human-plant interactions from prehistoric to historic settlements.

References· Chamberlain, S.A. , Boettiger, C. (2017). R Python, and Ruby clients for GBIF species occurrence data. *PeerJ Preprints*, 5: e3304v1.

Riding, J.B. (2021). A guide to preparation protocols in palynology. *Palynology*. 45(1):1-110.

Low- and high-latitude forcings drive Indian monsoon and vegetation variability during glacial MIS 16

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Background. The Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) accounts for ~90% of Central India's annual precipitation yet understanding its natural variability during past glacial periods remains a challenge in paleoclimate research. Despite considerable documentation of ISM dynamics during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), debates persist regarding the role of the primary forcings, including boreal summer insolation, North Atlantic circulation, ice volume, atmospheric CO₂, and Southern Hemisphere heat export. Hence, pre-LGM paleorecords are crucially needed to evaluate impact of the ISM on fragile ecosystems, such as India's forests and savannas. Here, we focus on MIS 16 (676-621 ka), a severe Quaternary glacial period marked by the first instabilities of the Laurentide ice sheet leading to the development of Heinrich layers in the North Atlantic. Describe the purpose for your research. This may be a very brief introductory description of the science and/or the significance of the research area. Identify the problem you solved or the hypothesis you investigated.

Methods. We present the first MIS 16 vegetation reconstruction from India's Core Monsoon Zone based on pollen analysis from IODP Site U1446 strategically recovered at the exit of the Mahanadi River to capture a robust signal of the ISM rainfall.

Results. Our findings indicate the prevalence of grassland and low tropical forest abundance during MIS 16, indicating overall dry conditions and reduced ISM activity. Furthermore, a progressive expansion of semi-arid vegetation suggests long-term glacial aridification associated with ISM weakening. Intra-glacial variability exhibits alternating wetter/drier phases, linked to ISM strength. Vegetation and hydroclimate changes are primarily controlled by the summer inter-tropical insolation gradient (SITIG), peaking during mid-MIS 16. Conversely, late-MIS 16 ISM weakening suggests that SITIG forcing is overshadowed by the impact of maximum ice volume and millennial-scale variability. Three major dryland expansions reflect ISM responses to millennial ice rafting events and AMOC reductions.

Conclusions. This study highlights the complex interplay of forcings driving past glacial ISM variability, crucial for understanding its impact on Indian ecosystems.

Coastal ecosystem transformations since 1800 in a macro-tidal estuarine environment: messages from Bay of Brest sediments

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Background. The Bay of Brest is a macro-tidal estuarine environment that has been exposed to strong anthropogenic pressures over the past decades, especially in the aftermath of World War II. Therefore, it is considered as a regional pilot site for addressing coastal ecosystem transformations since ca. 1800.

Methods. We analysed sediment cores collected in 2 different BB areas more or less exposed to marine hydrodynamic processes: 1) Elorn sector and 2) Bay of Daoulas, in the inner BB close to the mouth of the River of Daoulas, aiming at deciphering past environmental changes at a high temporal resolution (sub-decadal) over the two past centuries. Working at a local spatial scale (BB) allows addressing robust correlations between driving forces and environmental changes, as previously demonstrated for the inner BB (Bay of Daoulas) with pluridisciplinary studies covering the last 150 years (Klouch et al., 2016, Lambert et al., 2018, Siano et al., 2021). Furthermore, new benthic foraminiferal analyses were obtained in the Bay of Daoulas core.

Results. Fossilized marine bioindicators (dinocysts and foraminifera) coupled with biomolecular tools (sedaDNA: Klouch et al., 2016, Siano et al., 2021) allow discussing past changes in protist communities, while pollen indicators and sedimentological proxies allow discussing changes in BB landscapes through time.

Conclusions. We refine the discussion of three main thresholds (1945, 1965 and 1985) discussed in Lambert et al., 2018 by completing palynological datasets with higher-resolution analyses on the Bay of Daoulas (2-years-resolution) and inedited information in the Elorn sector (Northern BB; Figure 1). All sedimentological and paleoecological data are finally discussed at the light of instrumental data (on recent periods) as well as historical chronicles to tackle main forcing factors responsible for coastal ecosystem transformations, such as trophic changes and degradation of BB's water quality associated with the recrudescence of toxic algal blooms since the 1980's.

References. Klouch KZ, Schmidt S, Andrieux-Loyer F, et al. (2016) Historical records from dated sediment cores reveal the multidecadal dynamic of the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* in the Bay of Brest (France). *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 92(7): 101.

Lambert C, Penaud A, Vidal M, et al. (2018) Human-induced river runoff overlapping natural climate variability over the last 150 years: Palynological evidence (Bay of Brest, NW France). *Global and Planetary Change*, 160: 109-122.

Siano R, Lassudrie M, Cuzin P, et al. (2021) Sediment archives reveal irreversible shifts in plankton communities after World War II and agricultural pollution. *Current Biology*, 31(12): 2682-2689.

**POLLEN BIOLOGY:
ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

Exploring the structural resilience of pollen grains: A comprehensive TGA-FTIR investigation

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Background. Pollen grains, essential for the survival of terrestrial plant life, have garnered significant interest, not just for their crucial ecological role but also for their beneficial effects on human nutrition. These benefits enter the human diet through bees collecting pollen grains while visiting flowers and creating pollen pellets. The outer layer of pollen grains, called exine, is composed of a biopolymer named sporopollenin, known for its thermal resistance, mechanical robustness, and chemical inertness. Due to these distinct properties, exine has been an important subject in various research fields, ranging from studies on organic microfossils and the exploration of dietary practices in ancient societies to contemporary advancements in material sciences. In the present study, we aimed to understand whether there is a variation in the chemical composition and thermal stability among different pollen types subject to cytoplasmic removal.

Methods. To achieve this goal, *Castanea* sp., *Echium* sp., *Jasione* sp., *Papaver* sp., *Helianthemum* sp., *Cistus* sp., and Amaranthacea raw pollen, together with their exines purified through defatting and acidolysis, were subjected to simultaneous thermal analysis (STA). The results were then correlated with Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) data to gain insights into their chemical structure.

Results. The STA results revealed four distinctive thermal degradation stages for the tested raw pollen types but only three stages for the isolated exines. The tested raw pollens exhibited a maximum thermal degradation temperature ranging from 518 to 548 °C, leading to a mass loss between 93% and 99%. In comparison, the exines of these pollen types demonstrated a lower temperature range of 436–457 °C, resulting in a mass loss between 80% and 98%. The data obtained in the FTIR spectra indicate that the structure of exines generally has a similar chemical composition: C=C vibration in the aromatic ring of sporopollenin, asymmetric stretching in carboxylate anions (COO⁻), and C–H stretching in the aromatic ring of the sporopollenin. Nevertheless, the purification method enhances the intensity of several peaks due to the removal of some pollen components, e.g., cellulose, pectin, or proteins. The FTIR data further validates the existence of fats, proteins, cellulose, and associated compounds throughout the degradation stages at various temperatures in the STA.

Conclusions. Altogether, our results indicate that the thermal stability of pollen grains or exine shells of various plant species do not differ significantly among themselves and are resistant to high temperatures due to their chemical structure with different aliphatic and aromatic domains. Besides, we anticipate the usefulness of the present data and analytical methods to understand and reconstruct the original chemistry of pollen grain.

Enhancing microspore embryogenesis in *Quercus suber*: The role of histone H4 acetylation

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Background. Cork oak (*Quercus suber* L.) is a tree with remarkable economic and ecological values threatened by deforestation, diseases, and challenging natural regeneration. Microspore embryogenesis is a type of somatic embryogenesis and a powerful *in vitro* regeneration process with many biotechnological applications in breeding, propagation, and conservation programs. In cork oak, somatic embryogenesis can be induced from microspores and from immature zygotic embryos, being both developmental processes very useful for *in vitro* regeneration of this tree species. Despite the great potential of microspore embryogenesis, the high levels of cell death and the low reprogramming rates limit its use. Understanding the regulatory pathway of cellular reprogramming and embryogenesis induction would improve its efficient manipulation. Increasing evidence indicates that epigenetic reprogramming plays a key role during induction and progression of somatic embryogenesis, through DNA methylation, but less is known about the involvement of histone modifications.

Methods. In this study, we have analysed microspore and somatic embryogenesis in *Q. suber*, and the dynamics of H4 acetylation, a relevant histone post-transcriptional modification. Changes in global levels of this epigenetic mark, and expression profiles of some of the regulating enzymes have been characterized. Additionally, the effect of SAHA, an inhibitor of histone deacetylases has been evaluated.

Results. Results showed that embryo development is associated with H4 acetylation, correlating with the upregulation of the histone acetyltransferases *QsHAC1-like* and *QsHAM1-like* in developing embryos, whereas the histone deacetylases *QsHDA2* and *QsHDA15* were repressed at this stage of development. Treatments with SAHA revealed changes in the bulked levels of H4 acetylation, inducing the expression of embryogenesis marker genes, as *QsSERK1-like*, and increasing the embryo production.

Conclusions. These results provide new insights into the role of histone epigenetic marks in the induction towards embryogenesis processes of forest species, where scarce information is available. Furthermore, they open the door to new epigenetic strategies to improve *in vitro* regeneration for reforestation programs.

References. Berenguer et al. (2017) *Front Plant Sci*, 8: 1161. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2017.01161.

Carneros et al. (2023) *Plants*, 12(7): 1542. doi: 10.3390/plants12071542.

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Sporopollenin, a new micro-carrier for food applications

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Background. Pollen grains play a crucial role in maintaining plant species that support biodiversity. Although they may appear macroscopically similar to flower dust, a closer examination reveals that they are structurally quite different from one another. Each pollen grain contains cytoplasmic content, including proteins, some of which are related to its allergenic properties. In this study, we explore three different types of bee-collected pollens from *Erica* spp, *Rubus* spp. and *Olea* spp., common in Northern Portugal, to produce micro-sized capsules able to be used as carriers for the controlled delivery of food preservatives.

Methods. Firstly, collected bee pollen samples were separated by their colours, and identified by palynology analysis. Then, using a multistep chemical procedure, the cytoplasmic content of the pollen grains was removed to produce empty pollen microcapsules, which were then characterised using different procedures such as protein content evaluation or microscopic analysis with SEM and CLSM. After characterisation, the empty microcapsules were loaded with common food preservatives such as nisin, lecithin (E322), sorbic acid (E200) but also with natural preservatives such as propolis extract, a rich mixture of bioactive substances that bees use to protect their hives. Two loading methods were used: passive loading and vacuum loading. After loading, encapsulation efficiencies were calculated.

Results. Bee pollen samples were successfully cleaned using chemical procedure. The protein content was dramatically decreased, as expected. The microscopic techniques revealed the presence of empty capsules without impact on the overall structure of the pollen grains. The apertures and the surface of the microcapsules did not show the presence of residual material. The loading procedure seems dependent on the loaded material, with values of 4-5% for the propolis extract, independent of the pollen types, for lecithin 33-71%, and for sorbic acid 5-8%. Comparatively, the vacuum loading seems more effective for loading than the passive method.

Conclusions. Our study is the first attempt to use pollen types as microcapsules for the controlling the delivery of preservatives for food applications. Although the goals seem attractive and the preparation of the pollen capsules accomplished, there are several issues to overcome, in particular with respect to the loading procedures and the control delivery of the preservatives.

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A review of pollen grain in Papaveraceae family based on a multidisciplinary study

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Background. The family Papaveraceae s.l. includes about 44 genera and 760 species, mostly herbaceous, distributed mainly in temperate regions of the northern hemisphere. Papaveraceae s.l., together with six other families, constitute the order Ranunculales Dumortier, situated in the clade of basal Eudicotyledons. In this communication, we review the pollen type from the Papaveraceae family from the perspective of molecular phylogeny and pollen ultrastructure. We mostly focus on the ontogenetic aspects of the ultrastructure of the pollen wall and aperture, its nutritional tissue and also the presence of multilamellar cytoplasmic bodies, both in the pollen grain and in the pollen tube. Finally, we highlight the importance of the genes involved in aperture formation and development.

Methods. Material from 111 representative species of Papaveraceae from 57 genera and 2 species of *Euptelea* (Eupteleaceae) were collected from various botanical gardens across Europe and treated to different methods for microscopy analyses (see Materials and Methods of Fernández et al. 2013, Suárez-Santiago et al. 2018).

Results. In the interapertural zones, three models (A, B, C) and a variant of model A (columellar infratectum) have been considered. The variant is related to the structuring of walls due to the absence of a tectum and the presence of a pila in some species of *Mecconopsis*. In relation to the apertural areas, we describe four development models. The tapetum of the species in this family is always secretory type, but it is differentiated between the non-orbicle-producing tapetum with the production of a greater number of elaioplasts and the orbicle-producing tapetum with abundant tapetosomes. The multilamellar bodies that we describe near the developing apertures and at the apex of the growing pollen tube, we have related to membranous growth at times of maximum activity of the pollen grain. We describe multilamellar bodies near the developing apertures and at the apex of the growing pollen tube. The role of the INP1 gene as a factor in the development of aperture is present in basal eudicots (EcINP1). After obtaining and testing inaperturate pollen.

Conclusions. We differentiated between species with orbicle-producing and non-orbicle-producing tapetum. In relation to the multilamellar bodies, two moments of maximum activity of membrane formation stand out and finally we emphasise that the presence of apertures is not essential for pollen grain germination.

References. Fernández, M. C., Pérez-Gutiérrez, M. A, Suárez-Santiago, V.N., Salinas-Bonillo, M. J, Romero-García, A. T. (2013) Multilamellar bodies linked to two active plasmalemma regions in pollen grains of *Sarcocapnos pulcherrima*. *Biol Plant*, 57: 298-304.

Suárez-Santiago, V. N, Fernández-Fernández, M. C., Pérez-Gutiérrez, M. A, Ben-Menni Schuler, S., Salinas-Bonillo, M. J., Romero-García, A. T. (2018). Morphological and ultrastructural diversity and character evolution of the pollen in the tribe Chelidonieae (Papaveraceae). *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.*, 258: 83-97.

Evolution of the apertural ultrastructure in pollen grains of the Orden Ranunculales

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Background. The Ranunculales order is phylogenetically situated in the first branches of the Eudicots as it belongs to the "basal Eudicots". It is the most numerous members of this clade: It represents two thirds of the species (4.445) grouped into 199 genera which corresponds to 7 families (Zang et al. 2017). It is considered as a monophyletic group, where the Eupteleaceae is at the base of the clade, the Circaeasteraceae is the sister group to the Lardizabalaceae. The rest of the families of the order form a sister group, where the Menispermaceae is the basal group and the Berberidaceae is related to the Ranunculaceae. Molecular studies within these families of the order have helped to better understand the relationships within the group. We have focused our studies on phylogenetic and palynological work in the family Papaveraceae (see the review by Romero-García & Fernández-Fernández, 2024), but now we want to extend them to the rest of the families of the order. The systematic value of pollen morphological characters for Optical Microscopy (OM) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is sufficiently recognized. Our research group has demonstrated the importance of ultrastructural characters (Transmission Electron Microscopy, TEM) in the taxonomy of the group. In the present study, we focus on the ultrastructural models of the apertures of the species of this order and try to explain the possible evolutionary patterns that have occurred in the group.

Methods. We have studied from the ultrastructural point of view 211 species representatives of 131 genera and 6 families of this order to TEM, using the conventional technique of fixation in glutaraldehyde and osmium tetroxide of fresh material from five European botanical gardens. We have studied by TEM 211 species belonging to 131 genera of the different families of the Order Ranunculales, using the conventional technique of fixation in glutaraldehyde and osmium tetroxide of fresh material from five European botanical gardens.

Results. The ultrastructure of the apertures is very similar in both colpus-type and pore-type models. We have found 4 models: model A, corresponding to ectoapertures, is the most widespread model in the order, although it presents two variants, there are cases with oncus of the exine (variant 1), with oncus of the intine (variant 2) and the presence of both types of oncus (variants 1 and 2). Model B is present in the species of 11 genera of the subfamily Fumaroideae and is characterised by the presence of fluffly material, model C is present in *Sarcocapnos* and *Ceratocapnos*, with an extremely developed exine and intine oncus. Finally, model D has endoaperture with digital shape structure and is found in *Bocconia* and *Macleaya*.

Conclusions. The mapping of the ultrastructural characters on the basis of the molecular phylogeny of the families of this order shows the existence of synopormorphies in the families Papaveraceae and Menispermaceae. The existence of endoapertures appears independently.

Reference. Zang et al. (2017). Evolution of angiosperm 749 pollen: 4. Basal eudicots. *Ann Missouri Bot Gard*, 102: 141-182. doi:10.3417/2015035.

Mineral Composition of Bee Pollen During *In Vitro* Digestion

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Background. Nutrition plays a pivotal role in maintaining human health, with essential minerals serving as fundamental components for metabolic processes. Insufficient intake of these minerals, among which at least 22 are vital, can predispose individuals to a spectrum of ailments ranging from chronic diseases to acute growth disorders and even fatal conditions. Bee pollen, owing to its rich mineral content, emerges as a significant natural reservoir. Notably, potassium, magnesium, sodium, calcium, and phosphorus are abundantly present in bee pollen. Herein, we aim to investigate the mineral composition of bee pollen samples under simulated oral, gastric, and intestinal digestion stages.

Methods. Six bee pollen samples from different botanical sources such as *Nigella* spp. (85%), *Helianthus annuus* (90%), *Salix* spp. (47%), multifloral bee pollen (Fabaceae: 43%, Rosaceae: 31%, Asteraceae: 25%, and Lamiaceae: 1%), multifloral bee pollen (Brassicaceae: 29%, *Trifolium* spp.: 15%, Asteraceae: 12%, *Campanula* spp.: 12%, Papaveraceae: 10%, Lamiaceae: 8%, Cistaceae: 6%, *Echium* spp.: 6%, and *Onobrychis* spp.: 1%), and multifloral bee pollen (Brassicaceae: 44%, Cistaceae: 16%, Rosaceae: 15%, *Salix* spp.: 7%, *Echium* spp.: 68%, *Cichorium* spp.: 6%, Papaveraceae: 5%, and Fabaceae: 1%) were evaluated by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) during *in vitro* digestion.

Results. The ICP-OES system allowed the identification of 15 mineral compounds as Ag, Ba, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Ti, V, and Zn. While the Ca, Mg, Fe, and Zn minerals were found at the highest concentration in digested samples, Ag, Co, Cr, Pb, Ti, and V minerals were not detected. Notably, Ca and Mn demonstrated heightened digestibility during the gastric stage compared to the oral and intestinal phases, while other minerals predominated in the intestinal phase. This underscores the varying absorption behavior and properties of bee pollen minerals, with implications for nutritional uptake.

Conclusions. Bee pollen thus emerges as a valuable natural source, particularly enriched in Ca and Mg minerals, contributing to dietary fortification and health promotion. The results further emphasize the significance of pollen grains not only for the continuity of terrestrial plants, but also for human nutrition via honeybees.

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Discriminating monofloral bee pollen through the phenolic profile

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Background. Bee pollen is the result of the combination of hundreds and even thousands of plant pollen harvested by bees, which they mix with their secretions and plant nectar and transport into the hives. Beekeepers can collect these pollen loads at the hive entrance with the use of pollen traps. Composed mainly by carbohydrates, proteins and lipids, followed by minor compounds such as minerals, vitamins and phenolic compounds, its botanical and geographical origin have a direct influence in its phytochemical composition. Phenolic compounds are abundant in plants, and a plethora of bioactivities are described for bee pollen, such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties. This work aims at using analytical tools for the discrimination of monofloral bee pollen based on its phenolic profile.

Methods. In the present study, the phenolic profiles of ten bee pollen types from Galicia, Spain, were characterized, including *Erica*, *Lytbrum*, *Echium*, *Actinidia*, *Cistus*, *Quercus*, *Allium*, *Campanula*, *Rubus*, *Trifolium*. The pollen loads were first separated by colorimetry and checked for botanical origin by microscopic analysis. After solid-liquid extraction with ethanol/water (80:20), the phenolic composition was assessed using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with diode array detection and electrospray mass spectrometry (HPLC-DAD-ESI/MS).

Results. The palynological analysis classified all the color-separated bee pollen loads as monofloral with a diversified presence of important flavonoid and phenylamides. The different monofloral pollen presented a unique phenolic profile, with some showing a high quantity of phenylamides, such as *Actinidia* pollen type, where the main compound was N¹-caffeyl-N⁵-*p*-coumaroyl-N¹⁰-feruloylspermidine (m/z 628); *Quercus* type with N¹,N⁵-di-*p*-coumaroyl-N¹⁰-caffeylspermidine (m/z 598) and N¹-*p*-coumaroyl-N⁵,N¹⁰-dicaffeylspermidine (m/z 614), *Trifolium* type with N¹,N⁵,N¹⁰-tricaffeylspermidine (m/z 630) and *Rubus* type also with N¹-caffeyl-N⁵-*p*-coumaroyl-N¹⁰-feruloylspermidine (m/z 628). The other samples showed high levels of glycosylated flavonoids, as follows: kaempferol-*O*-malonyl-hexoside (m/z 533) and kaempferol-3-*O*-hexoside (m/z 447) in *Campanula* type, kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside (m/z 593) and kaempferol-*O*-malonyl-hexosyl-deoxihexoside (m/z 679) in *Echium* type, Quercetin-*O*-malonyl-hexoside (m/z 549) and isorhamnetin-*O*-diglucoronide (m/z 669) in *Allium* type, coumaroyl quinic acid (m/z 337) in *Erica* type and a dimer of luteolin (m/z 571) in *Lytbrum* type.

Conclusions. For each monofloral bee pollen, it was possible to define a specific phenolic profile, and some of the detected compounds can be considered floral markers. Understanding the phenolic fingerprint of bee pollen not only aids in verifying its botanical source but also reveals its potential health benefits, as different floral origins may impart varying levels of antioxidants and other bioactive compounds to this natural superfood.

**POLLEN BIOLOGY:
POSTER COMMUNICATIONS**

Tiny but mighty: the Impact of 2D-Nanomaterials on Pollen Performance

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Background. Graphene-related 2D-nanomaterials (2D-NMs) have become ubiquitous in various everyday products and devices, raising concerns about their potential environmental impact upon disposal. Particularly, graphene oxide (GO) has exhibited significant adverse effects on plant reproductive processes (Candotto Candiel et al. 2020); however, the broader impact of GO and 2D-NMs on these crucial processes remains largely unexplored. Consequently, there is an urgent need to investigate the effects of diverse 2D-NMs on pollen performance and vigor, with implications for understanding potential hazards to sexual reproduction.

Methods. We assessed the impact of 2D-NMs on in vitro pollen performance and vigor using *Corylus avellana* L. Germination tests were conducted in standard media (Brewbaker & Kwack, 1963) with or without 2D-NMs at concentrations ranging from 0 to 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Pollen viability, germination rate, and pollen tube length were assessed using light microscopy and analyzed with ImageJ software. Cytoskeleton as analyzed through immunofluorescence, along with pollen tube cell wall components, *i.e.*, pectins, callose, and cellulose (Aloisi et al. 2017). The following 2D-NMs were tested: GO, potassium muscovite (Mica), hexagonal boron nitride (hBN), and molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2), all widely used in industrial processes as nanomaterials and promising for composite development.

Results. The length of control pollen tubes was on average 164.295 μm and all the tested 2D-NMs affected pollen tube elongation at highest dosages, *i.e.*, 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. GO and hBN affected pollen tube performance in a dose-dependent manner also at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, while no significant effects were observed with Mica and MoS_2 at these concentrations. The most effective was hBN, which drastically reduced by 80 % pollen tube germination and by 40 % pollen tube elongation at 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Despite pollen tube germination and elongation inhibition, no alterations in the actin filaments and microtubules were highlighted, nor were there alterations in the deposition of high and low methyl-esterified pectins, callose, and cellulose.

Conclusions. Through in-vitro experimentation, our findings reveal that the tested 2D-NMs exert a pronounced inhibitory effect on pollen germination and pollen tube growth. Notably for GO and hBN these effects were dose. This impairment occurs without discernible alterations to cytoskeleton organization or cell wall composition and structure. The underlying mechanism warrants further elucidation, prompting exploration of several inhibition hypotheses. One hypothesis deserving investigation pertains to the potential interference of oxygen functional groups inherent to 2D-NMs with the uptake of essential ions such as Ca^{2+} and H^+ , vital for pollen tube growth. Confirmation of this hypothesis could provide insight into the differential effects observed among various 2D-NMs on pollen performance.

References. Aloisi, I. et al. (2017). Spermine regulates pollen tube growth by modulating Ca^{2+} -dependent actin organization and cell wall structure. *Front Plant Sci* 8
Brewbaker, J. L., Kwack BH. (1963). The essential role of calcium ion in pollen germination and pollen tube growth. *American Journal of Botany* 50: 859-865.
Candotto Carniel, F. et al. (2020). Beyond graphene oxide acidity: Novel insights into graphene related materials effects on the sexual reproduction of seed plants. *Journal of Hazardous Material* 393: 122380.

Unveiling the pollen diet of a solitary bee in an urban garden

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Background. Interactions between flowering plants and pollinators are critical roles in maintaining terrestrial ecosystems. In particular, bees are essential for pollination services as they visit flowers to collect nectar and pollen grains. In urban areas, the majority of bee species collect pollen and nectar from a wide variety of native and exotic, ornamental, and invasive flowering plants, shrubs, and trees. Analysis and identification of pollen grains provide a record of the floral host and are important in promoting the integration of ecology into urban landscape design to support of plant-pollinator assemblages. In this study, we investigate the type of pollen that a solitary bee species, *Osmia bicornis*, collected for its offspring in an urban garden in Salamanca. This species is generalist, collecting pollen from a wide variety of plants and nesting in cavities by placing brood cells, which are provisioned with pollen and nectar.

Methods. The ASILVESTRA project (GIR IBAHYM-Oficina Verde USAL) has been developed in the garden in Salamanca since 2022, with the aim of proposing alternative management for green areas and promoting plant and animal biodiversity. In this context, different shelters for solitary bees were placed along the green area. In 2023, the nests from the shelters were removed and processed in the laboratory, and the pollen samples of *O. bicornis* were obtained from the post-emergence residues in the brood cells. For each pollen sample, we counted at least 500 pollen grains, and we used a palynological reference of the study area as well as an atlas and pollen keys for identification.

Results. We found 11 different pollen types in the nesting provisions of *O. bicornis* corresponding to the wide variety of flowering plant and tree species available during the nesting period. The most abundant pollen type was *Papaver* (Papaveraceae) with 51.8% of all pollen grains counted, followed by *Reseda* type (Resedaceae) with 26.5 %. We also identified pollen trees as *Quercus* (Fagaceae) (14.7%) and *Aesculus* (Sapindaceae) (6%). The remaining pollen types were only found in small amounts (< 1% of total).

Conclusions. Knowledge of the diet of species in urban areas is essential to inform decisions on conservation and management strategies for these environments.

Palynological and multivariate analyses in *Senecio doronicum* group (Asteraceae, Senecioneae) from Iberian Peninsula

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Background. This study explores the palynological diversity within the *Senecio doronicum* group from the Iberian Peninsula, a subgroup within the *Crociseris* section of the Asteraceae. These species are crucial for understanding ecological adaptations and evolutionary processes due to their varied morphological characteristics. Our research aimed to investigate the potential of pollen morphology for species delimitation within this group, based on previous reviews such as Hodálová & Mártonfi (1995); Pérez-Romero et al. (2009).

Methods. Pollen samples from five *Senecio* species (*S. doronicum*, *S. eriopus*, *S. lagascanus*, *S. lusitanicus*, *S. provincialis*), comprising 35 herbarium specimens, were analyzed. We employed light microscopy (LM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for detailed morphological studies. Pollen grains were acetolyzed to standardize surface visibility and measured for 30 grains per sample to determine average dimensions. Multivariate analyses, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Multidimensional Scaling (MDS), and Cluster Analysis, were utilized, focusing on 25 specific palynological characters. The Manhattan distance served as the association measure for continuous taxonomic variables.

Results. *Senecio doronicum* group exhibited consistent palynological features, such as isopolar and tricolporate pollen grains with variations including oblate-spheroidal to prolate shapes (Fig. 1A). Quantitative analysis highlighted significant differences in pollen dimensions: polar lengths ranged from 30.5 to 40.6 μm and equatorial widths from 28.7 to 40.1 μm . Notably, the SEM observations revealed distinct morphological ornamentation series at the spine bases and between spines, aiding in species differentiation (Fig. 1B).

Conclusion. The study successfully distinguished species within the *Senecio doronicum* group based on pollen morphology, significantly contributing to the systematic taxonomy of the genus *Senecio*. The findings underscore the diagnostic value of palynology in understanding species relationships and evolutionary traits within this botanical group.

Fig. 1. Pollen grains of *Senecio doronicum*. **A:** equatorial view (meridional optical section) by LM. **B:** spine by SEM.

References. Hodálová, I., Mártonfi, P. (1995). Pollen morphology in the *Senecio nemorensis* group (Compositae) from the Carpathians. *Comp. Newsl.*, 26: 61-70.

Pérez-Romero, R., Pérez-Morales, C., Valencia Barrera, R. M., Penas Merino, A. (2009). *Senecio lusitanicus* (Asteraceae, Senecioneae), a new combination for a species from Iberian Peninsula. *Comp. Newsl.*, 47: 19-23.

Optimisation of rapeseed pollen germination

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Background. *In vitro* pollen germination is a feasible but challenging task, which requires to accurately recreate the stigmatic environment in order to promote pollen tube emergence and elongation. Published germination protocols, however, are often vague and hardly repeatable. This issue affects even highly investigated plant species, such as rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.), despite *Brassica* being regarded as a model genus for pollen biology studies. In this work, we aimed at optimising storage and germination protocols for rapeseed, by comparing and implementing recently published methods and controlling all the concurring environmental variables.

Methods. Rapeseed plants were grown from seed in standard conditions inside a phytotron. At the rosette stage, the plants were vernalised at 4 °C for 40 days in a growth chamber, and then returned to the phytotron until flowering. Flowers with dehiscent anthers were collected daily. Fresh pollen was immediately transferred to a Petri dish using a soft brush and stored at -80 °C, while the anthers were dried under a heat lamp for 24 hours to release the remaining pollen. Dried pollen was then separated from the anthers through a sieve and stored at -80 °C. Both fresh and dried pollen were then thawed and tested for viability with MTT, and for germinability using different protocols. In particular, the germinability was assessed with different rehydration periods, temperatures, germination mediums, sucrose concentrations, and environmental conditions (light, shaking).

Results. Drying, freezing, and thawing did not impact on the viability of rapeseed pollen, which remained over 95% for both fresh and dried pollen. However, dried pollen, although viable, was no longer able to germinate in any condition (germination rate 0%). Fresh pollen instead showed low (around 5%) to null germination rates when incubated in germination medium without a previous rehydration, and higher germination rates after 30 minutes of rehydration at room temperature (21 °C). The three published germination mediums employed in this study (Boavida & McCormick, 2007; Sheoran et al., 2009; Morrison et al., 2016) achieved different results, the most efficient being the one suggested by Lohani and collaborators, when prepared with 16% sucrose (germination rate of 30%). Moreover, rapeseed pollen germination showed a high sensitivity to the ambient temperature, with low to null germination over 22 °C. On the contrary, light and shaking did not affect the germination rate significantly.

Conclusions. We demonstrated that, in order to preserve germinability, rapeseed pollen needs to be rapidly frozen soon after collection, without previous dehydration. Storing thin layers of fresh pollen at -80°C ensures a viability of up to 98%, and a germinability up to 30% when using Lohani's medium with 16% sucrose. This study underlined the importance to standardise all the environmental parameters in order to achieve optimal and repeatable pollen germination rates.

References. Boavida, L. C., McCormick, S. (2007). Temperature as a determinant factor for increased and reproducible *in vitro* pollen germination in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant Journal*, 52, 570-582.

Morrison, M. J., Gutknecht, A., Chan, J., Miller, S. S. (2016). Characterising canola pollen germination across a temperature gradient. *Crop and Pasture Science*, 67: 317-322.

Sheoran, I. S., Pedersen, E. J., Ross, A. R. S., Sawhney, V. K. (2009). Dynamics of protein expression during pollen germination in canola (*Brassica napus*). *Planta*, 230: 779-793.

The pollen from natural vegetation in the olive agroecosystem serves as a food resource for predators of olive pests

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Background. Adults of various predatory arthropods occurring in the olive agroecosystem rely on pollen from plants present inside and/or outside the crop as a food resource. Among them, green lacewings (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) stand out, whose larval stages prey on the olive moth *Prays oleae* (Bern.) (Lepidoptera: Praydidae) and the olive psyllid *Euphyllura olivina* (Costa) (Hemiptera: Psyllidae). The aim of this study was to identify groups of plants used as pollen resources for species belonging to both insect families: *Chrysoperla carnea* sl. (Stephens) (Chrysopidae), *Melanostoma mellinum* (L.), *Episyrphus balteatus* DeG, *Eupeodes corollae* (F.), and *Sphaerophoria scripta* (L.) (Syrphidae).

Methods. For this purpose, adult insects were captured throughout the year inside and/or outside olive groves in the northeast of Portugal, and pollen grains from the guts of the captured insects were identified after dissection in the laboratory.

Results. As a result, pollen from herbaceous (e.g., Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Apiaceae, or Plantaginaceae) and shrub (e.g., Fabaceae, Pinaceae, or Ericaceae) families, present inside and/or outside the olive grove, was identified as a food source for adults. In spring, a greater number of families were consumed than in summer and autumn. Some families, such as Asteraceae and Brassicaceae were used in spring, summer, and autumn, while others were consumed only in summer (Plantaginaceae or Rubiaceae) or autumn (Ranunculaceae or the species *Daphne gnidium* L.).

Conclusions. The results obtained contribute to the understanding of the occurring trophic relationships among the arthropod species reliant on pollen for food and to the selection of species for ecological infrastructures such as vegetative covers or adjacent vegetation plots aimed at improving populations of green lacewings and hoverflies in the olive agroecosystem.

List of authors

- Abel Schaad, D. 63, 81, 89
Acal, C. 22
Aguilera, A. M. 22
Alba Sánchez, F. 63, 81, 89
Alberte, C. 31
Alcalde-Eon, C. 29
Alcázar-Teno, P. 18
Alia, M. H. B. 61
Allain, E. 85
Aloisi, I. 25, 102
Alonso-Garcia, M. 91
Amigo, R. 31, 32
Amrani, N. 47
Anderson, R. S. 69, 85
Anupama, K. 91
Arenas Martín, K. 29
Ares, A. 54
Aylanc, V. 94
Azuara, J. 68
Baños-Picón, L. 103
Barbero-Barrera, M. M. 20
Barbier-Pain, D. 38
Barboni, D. 36
Bardón, R. 12
Bartolomé-Esteban, C. 50
Bassetti, M. 40
Bassetti, M. A. 68
Batista, N. C. 17
Beaufort, L. 69
Beauger, A. 85
Belmonte, J. 15
Bernal, J. 54
Berné, S. 68
Bertini, A. 65, 66
Bini, M. 75
Biz, S. 85
Blanca, H. 30
Borrel, F. 43, 44
Bosseboeuf, L. 92
Bourel, B. 36
Bouzas Sabater, M. 46
Braga, L. 64
Brandão, L. A. 17
Brighetti, M. A. 13, 16, 27
Burch Rius, J. 46
Cabrera, M. 56
Cano, D. 12
Cardoso, J. 57
Carmona, E. 30
Carneros, E. 95
Carracedo, V. 76
Carrera, L. 31, 32
Cartelle, V. 73, 82, 83, 84
Cascón, A. 12, 34
Castro-Parada, A. 73, 82, 83, 84
Catrain, M. 65
Cazás, N. 73, 82, 83, 84
Cerafogli, E. 42
Cervigón, P. 12
Charton, L. 66
Chicote Carreras, J. 51
Chouza, M. 60
Clò, E. 37
Combourieu-Nebout, N. 65, 66, 69, 85
da Cruz, A. R. 17
Daniau, A. L. 68, 87
Dávalos, V. 56
David, O. 39
De Franco, D. 13, 16, 27
De Gálvez Montañez, E. 14, 23
De la Paz, N. E. 95
De Linares, C. 15, 30
Defive, E. 85
Degasperri, N. 40
Del Duca, S. 25, 105
Denami, M. 58
Dennielou, B. 87
Desprat, S. 91
Di Menno di Bucchianico, A. 13, 16, 27
Dias, S. R. 17
Días-Lorenzo, D. A. 31, 32
Diéguez, A. 60
Diniz, M. B. 17
Doko, J. 61
Dufournet, L. 85
Eastwood, W. 72
Ehrhold, A. 39, 92
Ejarque, A. 5, 6, 69, 76, 85
Ertosun, S. 96
Escuredo, O. 48, 52, 53, 54, 60, 100
Eynaud, F. 74
Falcão, S. I. 52, 100
Farooq, Q. 18
Fauquette, S. 65
Feliciano, M. 33
Fernández Álvarez, A. 51
Fernández Fernández, M. C. 97, 98
Fernández González, D. 25
Fernández, A. 47
Fernández-González, D. 59
Fernández-González, F. 24
Fernández-González, M. 7, 31, 32
Fernández-Jiménez, S. 30
Fersi, W. 74
Florenzano, A. 25, 37, 40, 64, 75
Fontana, A. 40, 64
Fourcade, T. 67
Franco, D. 31

Freire, A. C. 94, 96
 Furia, E. 19
 Fuster, F. 12
 Gaddi, R. 16
 Galán, C. 18
 Galindo Ortiz, S. 20
 Gambin, B. 21
 García-Gil, S. 82, 83, 84, 73
 García-Llamas, C. 18
 García-Mozo, H. 18
 García-Rogado, M. R. 59
 García-Sánchez, A. 33
 Genet, M. 68, 87
 Georget, M. 68, 87
 Gervois, A. 38
 Ghorab, A. 47, 48, 53
 Gonçalves, F. A. 17
 González-Hernández, A. 81
 González-Porto, A. V. 50, 54
 Goslin, J. 92
 Gosseume, P. 85
 Goubert, E. 86, 92
 Gromig, R. 70, 71
 Gross, T. G. 85
 Guada, G. 31
 Gutiérrez-Bustillo, A. M. 12
 Harbane, S. 48, 53
 Hernández, A. 103
 Iovino, F. 78
 Iratçabal, V. 86
 Ishkokani, R. 88
 Izdebski, A. 70, 71, 72
 Jalali, B. 68
 Jiménez-Jiménez, E. 24
 Jiménez-López, G. 30
 Joannin, S. 65
 Johnson, J. 85
 Julià, R. 46
 Kenali, H. I. 61
 Kércia Martins, R. 20, 21
 Kim, J. H. 79
 Kolovos, E. 70, 71
 Kouli, K. 70, 71
 Lahaye, C. 38, 39, 67, 86, 92
 Lara, B. 22, 24
 Lardjane, S. 38
 Lebreton, V. 65, 66
 Leroux, E. 39
 Leys, B. 68
 Liakopoulos, G. C. 70, 71
 Lima, I. 57
 Lloret, L. 31
 López Sáez, J. A. 63, 81, 89
 López, E. 47
 López-Bultó, O. 43, 44
 López-Orozco, R. 18
 López-Pérez, A. 50
 López-Sáez, J. A. 106
 López-Victoria, D.R. 103
 Louwye, S. 88
 Luelmo Lautenschlaeger, R. 69, 85
 Mantilla Martínez, E. 49
 Mardones, P. 26
 Mardones, R. 26
 Martínez, P. 91
 Martínez-Bracero, M. 18
 Martínez-Carreño, N. 73, 82, 83, 84
 Martín-Hernández, R. 50
 Masci, L. 42, 70, 71
 Masi, A. 42, 70, 71, 72
 Matamala, K. 26
 Matías-Martínez, Y. 59
 Mazur, J. C. 36
 Menier, D. 86
 Mensing, S. 78
 Mercuri, A. M. 19, 25, 37, 40, 58, 64, 75
 Mertens, K. N. 86, 88
 Meyvich, P. 88
 Micheli, R. 40
 Miras, Y. 85, 69
 Moncel, M. H. 65
 Moner Coll, E. 46
 Montenegro, J. F. 90
 Morales, T. 18
 Moreno de la Fuente A. 51
 Moreno R. 18
 Morgado-Llamazares, N. 33
 Moricca, C. 42
 Moros, M. 70, 71
 Mouillot, F. 68, 87
 Moure, B. 31
 Muñoz García, M. 14, 23
 Muñoz Sobrino, C. 73, 82, 83
 Muñoz-Gómez, G. 24
 Muñoz-Sobrino, C. 84
 Mutlu, C. 99, 57
 N'Dah, D. 77
 Nadal, J. 76
 Nakib, R. 53, 54
 Naughton, F. 74, 91
 Navarro, D. 15
 Nicolas, C. 39
 Ochoa, D. 90
 Oliveira, D. 91
 Oliveira, G. A. 17
 Ortega Marcos, J. 51
 Oteros J. 18
 Ouelhadj, A. 48, 53
 Paganelli, F. 25
 Pailler, Y. 39
 Palli, J. 75, 78
 Paloma Cariñanos 30

Pardo, M. 26
 Pardo-Martin C. 50
 Paulet, Y-M. 92
 Peixoto, A. F. 94, 96
 Pèlachs, A. 76
 Penas, Á. 104
 Penaud, A. 39, 74, 86, 88, 92
 Perales, I. 47
 Peralta, T. 26
 Pereira, J. A. 106
 Peressin, M. 85
 Pérez Morales, C. 104
 Pérez Otero, R. 31
 Pérez-Badia, R. 22, 24
 Pérez-Obiol, R. 76
 Pérez-Romero, R. 104
 Peyron, O. 65, 66
 Philippe, A. 67
 Piana, L. 58
 Picornell A. 23, 14
 Piovesan, G. 75, 78
 Poncin, O. 39
 Prasad, S. 91
 Puebla, R. 12
 Puigdemunt, R. 15
 Raimonet, M. 92
 Recio, M. 14, 23
 Redondas Marrero, M. D. 20
 Rens, M. 85
 Revelles, J. 43, 44
 Rey, J. D. 31
 Ribeiro, H. 33
 Ribeiro, T. 33
 Ricucci C. 75
 Riera-Mora, S. 46
 Rifka, N. 48
 Roberts, N. 72
 Rodríguez de la Cruz, D. 29, 49, 51, 103
 Rodríguez Fernández, A. 25, 59
 Rodríguez-Flores, M. S. 48, 52, 53, 54, 60, 100
 Rodríguez-Rajo, F. J. 7, 31, 32
 Rodríguez-Torres, A. 24
 Rojo, J. 34, 13
 Romero García, A. T. 97, 98
 Romero-Morte J. 34, 12
 Rossignol, L. 74
 Ruggirello, F. 102, 105
 Ruiz Mata, R. 14, 23
 Russo Almeida, P. 57, 8
 Sabariego Moreno, K. 20
 Sabariego, S. 34, 56
 Sadori, L. 9, 10, 42, 70, 71, 78
 Saker Y. 53, 48, 52
 Sánchez Agudo, J. A. 51
 Sánchez Goñi, M. F. 67, 74, 79
 Sánchez Reyes E. 17, 20, 26, 33
 Sánchez-Espinosa, K. C. 31, 32
 Sánchez-Morales, M. 46, 76
 Santander, E. 56
 Santos, S. 106
 Sarantis, A. 70, 71
 Sardinero, S. 24
 Schmidt, S. 87
 Schneider, R. 91
 Seijo M. C. 48, 52, 53, 54, 60
 Senkul, Ç. 72
 Siano, R. 39, 92
 Siano, R. 92
 Sicre, M. A. 68
 Simms, A. 69, 85
 Simms, A. 85
 Slavin, P. 70, 71
 Stasolla, F. R. 42
 Stéphan, P. 39
 Suanno, C. 25, 102, 105
 Suárez Calvache, M. 63
 Suárez Santiago, V. N. 98
 Sutton, J. 92
 Sypiański, J. 70, 71
 Tejada, A. 90
 Tenor-Ortiz, M. J. 18
 Testillano, P. S. 95
 Tobajas, E. 103
 Tomás, A. 8
 Tossa Dognon, D. A. 61
 Tossou, G. M. 61
 Tossou, M. 77
 Toti, F. 65
 Toucanne, S. 74
 Travaglini A. 13, 16, 19, 27
 Trigo. M. M. 14, 23
 Vale, N. 94
 Valencia Barrera, R. M. 59, 104
 Valero, C. 39, 92
 Vardi, J. 43, 44
 Vega-Maray, A. M. 59
 Vidal, M. 38, 39, 92
 Vidras, G. 70, 71
 Vignola, C. 70, 71, 72, 78
 Vilas-Boas, M. 8, 52, 57, 94, 96, 99, 100
 Villa, M. 106
 Vinci, G. 64
 Vivó Codina, D. 46
 Voldoire, O. 85
 Wagner, B. 70, 71
 Wary, M. 74
 Yin, Q. 91
 Zanchetta, G. 75
 Zano, Mardjoua, B.A. 77
 Zanou, R. A. 61
 Zappa, J. 40
 Zorzi, C. 79, 91